

VALKYRIES

D5.3 Roadmap for enhancing the pan-European operational and procedural capabilities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters

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1. Executive Summary

Deliverable D5.3 builds on the results of the WP5 tasks set out in the previous deliverables D5.5 (describing the mapping of procedural opportunities for improving EU first response capabilities) and D5.6 (presenting the opportunities for standardisation in this respect).

This D5.3 develops an analysis, prioritisation and programming for the development and adoption of new common practices and procedures, ultimately translated into EU-level roadmaps for the standardisation of first responder response in the EU market with different approaches: recognition, triage and crisis response planning, maintenance, logistics and deployment, command and control and operational decision support, common operational picture and alert and warning.

Due to the horizontality of the project at this stage and the similarities in work packages 4, 5 and 6 a common work methodology has been established for them. This allows to intercompare results between work packages, to be efficient and to provide a holistic result.

For these reasons a common methodology has been established for deliverables 4.4, 5.4 and 6.4. Some chapters are common to these deliverables, which is why they are marked in their title as “(common)”.

The structure of deliverable D5.3 is as follows:

- **Introduction:** Specific introduction and objectives, as well as D4.3 / D5.3 / D6.3 common methodological aspects description regarding structure criteria, ID codification, exclusion criteria, expert consultation.
- **Taxonomy process (common):** Describes the common taxonomy process applied to deliverables D4.3, D5.3 and D6.3, carried out on the opportunities identified in the previous deliverables on which they are based.
- **Clustering opportunities:** Describes the result of the cataloguing, taxonomic homogenisation and grouping of the individual opportunities collected in D5.6 based on the evaluation of similarities and differences. This task has been developed within each WP, but goes beyond the a priori organisation of the project into tasks, taking into account aspects related to methodology, objectives, addressees, etc. As a result, a total of 15 grouped opportunities are defined in this D5.3, each containing one or more closely related individual opportunities.
- **Opportunity analysis:** Describes the methodology (common) and results of the analysis, scoring, explanation and categorisation of the identified clustered opportunities based on the feasibility/impact matrix.
- **Ranking of opportunities:** Ranking of the clustered opportunities according to the total score obtained in the feasibility/impact analysis, highlighting the top 6 high feasibility/impact opportunities selected to advance the VALKYRIES project harmonisation and pre-standardisation proposals.
- **Identification of interdependencies:** Statement and analysis of the existing interdependencies both within the opportunities of WP5 itself and between those of different work packages.
- **SWOT evaluation:** After a brief summary of the current EU landscape encountered in the previous phases of the project and the main harmonisation efforts undertaken so far, an assessment of the selected clustered opportunities is made using the SWOT

methodology (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats) as steps leading to the definition of each specific harmonisation and pre-standardisation roadmap at EU level.

- **Roadmap for pre-standardisation:** For each of the selected clustered opportunities, define a specific roadmap for harmonisation and pre-standardisation at EU level as a strategic plan with defined and timed steps or milestones to achieve the proposed objectives.
- **Stakeholder evaluation:** As a process of external validation of the results reflected in D5.3, the results were shared with EAB experts and stakeholders who evaluated both the process of identifying the most relevant clustered opportunities and the proposed roadmaps for each of them.
- **Conclusions:** Finally, the main conclusions gathered in D5.3 for each of the clustered opportunities studied are reflected in a summarised form.

The annexes section of the deliverable contains the bibliographical references and the glossary or table of acronyms used throughout the text.

2. Identification

Deliverable Title: Roadmap for enhancing the pan-European operational and procedural capabilities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters

Deliverable Id: D5.3

Deliverable Title Abbreviation: D5.3

Name of lead participant: TASSICA

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Linked project tasks:

- T5.1 Reconnaissance, triage and crisis response planning
- T5.2 Maintenance, logistics and Deployment
- T5.3 Command and Control and support to operational decision-making
- T5.4 Common Operational Picture and warning

Action: Study

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3. Introduction

The European H2020 project VALKYRIES aims to analyse, improve and develop infrastructures, protocols and tactics for standardization and harmonization of data exchange with the objective of increasing efficiency and interoperability in the response to multi-casualty incidents or disasters, especially in the most complex or cross-border cases.

To this end, Valkyries has mapped, identified communities, analysed regulatory and standardization issues in the selected opportunities, to suggested roadmaps to mitigate them and drive the adoption of disruptive solutions in the first responder markets.

WP5 of the Valkyries project, entitled "Common Practices, and operational procedures for First Aid Responses", aims primarily to provide a comprehensive information framework of EU common operational plans and procedures, and deliver harmonization guidelines and recommendations for operational practices and procedures to facilitate, guide and improve cooperation between actors in first aid response to mass casualty incidents and disasters.

As a result of the work developed within WP5, deliverables D5.1 (draft version) and D5.5 (final version), named "Landscape of emerging operational and procedural opportunities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters", provides a description of the procedural and operational state of the art and of the related EU landscape.

After that, deliverable D5.2 (draft version) and D5.6 (definitive version) named " Harmonization opportunities on the operational and procedural landscape for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters", provides an identification and categorization of needs and gaps in regulation, certification and standardisation of existing and emerging procedures to support first aid responses, focusing on the cross-border, cross-sector and cross-hierarchical context.

This deliverable D5.3, "Roadmap for enhancing the pan-European operational and procedural capabilities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters", studies, cluster and prioritizes the identified opportunities, focusing on the most relevant ones, and proposes EU-wide roadmaps for their standardization.

3.1. Objective

The primary objective of the VALKYRIES project is to develop, implement, validate and apply innovative theoretical foundations, methods, prototypes and their demonstration on a reference integration for supporting the ongoing/planned European actions for pre-standardisation and harmonisation technologies, procedures, preparedness and cross-sector/border cooperation for first aid response at disaster management by emergency health services, with the focus on their vehicular deployments.

To achieve this primary objective and address the challenges identified above, VALKYRIES establishes 9 specific and measurable objectives that are introduced below:

- **VALK-OBJ-1 (Map of growing commercial and R&D opportunities):** Analyse the existing/ongoing technological, procedural, education and collaborative opportunities of the first aid response supplier markets and related signs of progress beyond the state-of-the-art able to improve the EU disaster resiliency.
- **VALK-OBJ-2 (Sustainable Regulation and ethical compliance):** Analyse the first aid response cross-sector, cross-border and cross-hierarchy regulatory and ethical principles, identifying minimum standard requirements, lacunae and hurdles, and

developing recommendations to policymakers and stakeholders to facilitate their enforcement through the consolidation of a harmonised regulatory framework and the implementation of new strategic schemes.

- **VALK-OBJ-3 (Sustainable Pre-standardisation and Standardisation):** Research and analyse the pre-standardisation opportunities concerning the first aid response enablers, resulting in recommendations, common requirements, guidelines and enforcement tools towards constituting a novel and sustainable reference model, being implemented at new standardisation actions.
- **VALK-OBJ-4 (Sustainable certification and conformity assessment criteria):** Analyse the accreditation and certification opportunities concerning the first aid response enablers, including the enforced conformity assessment criteria, evaluation procedures and facilities; resulting in recommendations, guidelines and strategies to prompt sustainable certification, accreditation and homogeneity assessment.
- **VALK-OBJ-5 (Sustainable Harmonisation framework):** Development of a holistic framework for supporting the standardisation/harmonisation of first aid response enablers assuming their cross-sector, cross-border and cross-hierarchy hybrid dimensions, bearing in mind the vertical/horizontal propagation of consequences of the decisions made between technical, procedural and collaborative domains.
- **VALK-OBJ-6 (Harmonisation of vehicular first aid technologies, procedures and collaboration):** Research, analyse and apply the VALKYRIES' recommendations, guidelines and harmonisation tactics on reference equipment, technologies, procedures, preparedness, raise awareness and related collaborative solutions.
- **VALK-OBJ-7 (Cross-sectorial collaboration, civilian protection, volunteering and military assistance):** Research, analyse and expand the harmonisation framework towards facilitating, guiding and enhancing the cooperation between vehicular first aid responders with other disaster management actors, among them firefighters, law enforcement agencies, civilian protection, military or heterogeneous volunteering.
- **VALK-OBJ-8 (Reference integration and interoperation):** Reference integration and interoperation of the harmonised technological, procedural and collaborative solutions based on the common requirements and gap mitigations prioritised by the committed end-users and practitioners.
- **VALK-OBJ-9 (Large EU scale cross-border demonstrations):** Evaluation and demonstration of the interoperability and enhancements derived from harmonising vehicular first aid related enablers at four cross-border and cross-sectorial scenarios: Spain-Portugal, Slovakia-Austria, Bulgaria-Greece and Norway-Netherlands.

For the scope of deliverable D5.3, to develop the EU-wide roadmap for the standardization of operational and procedural capabilities for first aid response in multi-casualty disasters, Valkyries researchers defined a number of requirements related to the various specific objectives of the Project (D2.7 Definition of System Requirements and Demonstration Use Cases).

There are 2 types of requirements regarding WP5 deliverables:

- **Base requirements:** requirements extracted from the description of the tasks in the DoW (technical proposal) of the Valkyries Project. They are considered mandatory.

- **Common requirements:** are those requirements that are not explicitly described in the DoW (therefore considered as extended requirements) but are adopted by agreement between the Project partners. They are optional requirements.

VALKYRIES adopts the following requirements prioritization scale:

- **P1 (Highest Priority):** Priority requirements that must be met for the system not to fail. They will be partially covered by functionalities that will be verified in the previous verification and validation processes. The fulfilment of the requirement may condition the progress towards the fulfilment of the P2 priority conditions.
- **P2 (Moderate priority):** P2 requirements must be fulfilled once P1 requirements have been satisfied. The requirements will be partially covered by functionalities that will be verified in the intermediate verification and validation processes.
- **N/A (Not Applicable):** The requirement shall be considered from the very beginning (by design).

Finally, the methods to use for verification and validation of the requirements are: Demonstration, Analysis, Test, Inspection and Special Qualification Methods (any other verification procedure).

MANDATORY REQUERIMENTS - OBJECTIVES

The following table lists the 12 base (mandatory) requirements related to deliverable D5.3, and their traceability to the Valkyries project objectives.

ID	Priority	Description	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	Related WP5 task	Verification Method
REQ_BASE_T5.1_3	P2	Harmonization guidelines and recommendations for MCI procedures MUST be produced.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7	T5.1	Inspection
REQ_BASE_T5.1_5	P2	A roadmap to harmonize and enhancing the pan-European operational and procedural capabilities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters SHOULD be suggested.	VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7	T5.1	Inspection

ID	Priority	Description	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	Related WP5 task	Verification Method
REQ_BASE_T5.1_6	P2	Further related actions for harmonization SHOULD be recommended.	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7	T5.1	Inspection
REQ_BASE_T5.2_2	P1	Guidelines and recommendations for maintenance, logistics and deployment in MCI and disasters MUST be produced.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7	T5.1	Inspection
REQ_BASE_T5.2_3	P2	VALKYRIES MAY develop advanced skills in maintenance, logistics and deployment for first aid responders in MCI and disasters.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.1	Inspection
REQ_BASE_T5.2_2	P1	Guidelines and recommendations for maintenance, logistics and deployment in MCI and disasters MUST be produced.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7	T5.2	Inspection
REQ_BASE_T5.2_3	P2	VALKYRIES MAY develop advanced skills in maintenance, logistics and deployment for first aid responders in MCI and disasters.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.2	Inspection

ID	Priority	Description	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	Related WP5 task	Verification Method
REQ_BASE_T5.3_2	P1	Recommendations for the development, harmonization and integration of C&C solutions regarding the MCI and disasters MUST be produced.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7	T5.3	Inspection
REQ_BASE_T5.4_2	P1	A Common Operational Picture (COP) MUST be defined for the VALKYRIES project.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.4	Inspection Test Analysis
REQ_BASE_T5.4_3	P1	VALKYRIES COP Key data and flows MUST be defined	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.4	Inspection Test Analysis
REQ_BASE_T5.4_5	P1	Recommendations and guidelines to issue alerts and warnings in disaster situations MUST be produced.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.4	Inspection

Table 1 – Base requirements (mandatory) - objectives

OPTIONAL REQUERIMENTS - OBJECTIVES

The following table lists the 55 common (optional) requirements related to deliverable D5.3, and their traceability to the Valkyries project objectives.

ID	Priority	Description	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	Related WP5 task	Verification Method
REQ_COM_T5.1_4	P2	Analysis of the event notification process that entails the activation of a response plan to a health crisis	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.1	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.1_5	P1	The criteria that are established for a health management plan to be activated SHOULD be studied and analysed.	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.1	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.1_6	P1	The operational structure SHOULD involve the division of tasks, including roles, responsibilities and authorities, as well as the coordination of various medical and non-medical operational assets	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.1	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.1_7	P1	Data SHOULD be collected and analysed continuously	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.1	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.1_10	P1	VALKYRIES SHOULD analyse and identify the use of triage for the management of incidents with multiple victims and, if so, the triage method used.	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.1	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.1_11	P1	Information collected on the victims treated.	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.1	Inspection

ID	Priority	Description	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	Related WP5 task	Verification Method
REQ_COM_T5.1_12	P2	Study and analysis of medical care provided to victims of a disaster	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.1	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.1_13	P2	Effective coordination and communications are of critical importance in the distribution of disaster victims.	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.1	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.2_2	P2	Command and Control application MAY categorize the incidents in order to deal in agile way the major events.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7	T5.1	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.2_3	P2	Guideline with the logical sequence of activation of resources based on events and dimension event	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7	T5.1	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.2_4	P2	In disasters, tents are often needed in which to care for victims. Emergency teams MAY have the capacity to deploy this type of infrastructure.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.1	Inspection Demonstration
REQ_COM_T5.2_5	P3	It may be necessary to relieve the first responders because the emergency drags on over time.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.1	Inspection Demonstration

ID	Priority	Description	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	Related WP5 task	Verification Method
REQ_COM_T5.2_10	P2	Uninjured people affected by a disaster MUST be affiliated and registered.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.1	Inspection Demonstration
REQ_COM_T5.2_11	P2	There MUST be meeting points where people who must be evacuated due to a disaster go.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.1	Inspection Demonstration
REQ_COM_T5.2_13	P2	Those affected by a disaster MAY need essential items	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.1	Inspection Demonstration
REQ_COM_T5.2_14	P2	Essential services such as electricity, water, telephone... as well as communication routes, can be affected by a disaster.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.1	Inspection Demonstration
REQ_COM_T5.2_2	P2	Command and Control application MAY categorize the incidents in order to deal in agile way the major events.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7	T5.2	Inspection

ID	Priority	Description	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	Related WP5 task	Verification Method
REQ_COM_T5.2_3	P2	Guideline with the logical sequence of activation of resources based on events and dimension event	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7	T5.2	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.2_4	P2	In disasters, tents are often needed in which to care for victims. Emergency teams MAY have the capacity to deploy this type of infrastructure.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.2	Inspection Demonstration
REQ_COM_T5.2_5	P3	It may be necessary to relieve the first responders because the emergency drags on over time.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.2	Inspection Demonstration
REQ_COM_T5.2_10	P2	Uninjured people affected by a disaster MUST be affiliated and registered.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.2	Inspection Demonstration
REQ_COM_T5.2_11	P2	There MUST be meeting points where people who must be evacuated due to a disaster go.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.2	Inspection Demonstration

ID	Priority	Description	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	Related WP5 task	Verification Method
REQ_COM_T5.2_13	P2	Those affected by a disaster MAY need essential items	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.2	Inspection Demonstration
REQ_COM_T5.2_14	P2	Essential services such as electricity, water, telephone... as well as communication routes, can be affected by a disaster.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.2	Inspection Demonstration
REQ_COM_T5.3_1	P2	User guide for operational decision making. Standardise activity procedures.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.3	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.3_2	P2	Assign resources to the incident.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.3	Inspection Test
REQ_COM_T5.3_3	P2	The incident MUST be categorized according to the nature of the causative agent, its intensity and the consequences, in order to establish an adequate response.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.3	Inspection Test Analysis

ID	Priority	Description	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	Related WP5 task	Verification Method
REQ_COM_T5.3_5	P2	The initial contingency response MUST be protocolled to favour immediate intervention in the event of an incident.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.3	Inspection Demonstration
REQ_COM_T5.3_7	P2	An Incident Command Post MUST be established to ensure command and control on scene.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.3	Inspection Demonstration
REQ_COM_T5.3_12	P2	An exhaustive evaluation of the state of the affected infrastructures, industries and assets will be carried out.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.3	Inspection Demonstration
REQ_COM_T5.3_13	P2	An action strategy MUST be defined and planned, based on the provisions of the Emergency Operations Plan and the specific situation caused by the incident.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.3	Inspection Demonstration
REQ_COM_T5.3_18	P2	Decisions MUST be continually reviewed and the effectiveness of actions MUST be monitored to ensure an appropriate response to the incident at all times.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.3	Inspection Demonstration

ID	Priority	Description	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	Related WP5 task	Verification Method
REQ_COM_T5.3_21	P2	The Incident Command MUST be able to provide a summary of aggregated incident information in easy-to-issue, to transmit and to understand reports.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.3	Inspection Demonstration
REQ_COM_T5.3_22	P2	The decision to terminate the emergency response to an incident MUST be based on protocolled criteria and ensure the orderly, safe, and efficient return of emergency resources to their original location and status.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.3	Inspection Demonstration
REQ_COM_T5.4_1	P1	The terms used in the COP MUST be defined and standardized	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.4	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.4_8	P2	The COP MUST show the updated information at all times.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.4	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.4_9	P2	The COP MAY indicate other possible risks in the area of operations (risk map).	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.4	Inspection

ID	Priority	Description	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	Related WP5 task	Verification Method
REQ_COM_T5.4_10	P2	The COP MAY indicate elements of special vulnerability in the area of operations.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.4	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.4_11	P2	The COP MAY indicate logistics resources of interest previously registered in the area of operations.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.4	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.4_12	P2	The COP SHOULD locate the hospitals of the health system in the area of operations.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.4	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.4_13	P2	The COP MUST indicate the location and extent of the focus (impact zone)	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.4	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.4_14	P2	The COP MAY indicate the emergency response plan that has been activated, as well as the declared activation level.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.4	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.4_15	P2	The COP MUST indicate the location of the victims in the scenario of operations.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.4	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.4_16	P2	The COP MUST indicate the location of emergency vehicles in the operations scenario.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.4	Inspection

ID	Priority	Description	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	Related WP5 task	Verification Method
REQ_COM_T5.4_17	P2	The COP MUST indicate the location of the first responders in the operations scenario.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.4	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.4_18	P2	The COP MUST indicate the location of the incident commanders and chiefs.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.4	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.4_19	P2	The COP MUST indicate the location of the resources deployed to support the intervention of the emergency medical service on the scene of operations.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.4	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.4_27	P2	Recommendations must be established regarding the emission of alerts and alarms through public address systems and other elementary resources in the context of the response to MCI and disasters.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.4	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.4_28	P2	The Command and Control Application MAY allow store pictures / video on-place	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6	T5.4	Inspection Test
REQ_COM_T5.4_29	P2	The Command and Control Application MAY	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6	T5.4	Inspection Test

ID	Priority	Description	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	Related WP5 task	Verification Method
		generate on-time dashboards.			
REQ_COM_T5.4_30	P2	The Command and Control Application MAY edit graphical tools	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6	T5.4	Inspection Test
REQ_COM_T5.4_31	P2	The Command and Control Application MAY suggest to the operator most relevant agencies for each incident in order to keep in touch between them.	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6	T5.4	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.4_32	P2	Autocomplete feature in which an application predicts the rest of a word a user is typing	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6	T5.4	Inspection Test
REQ_COM_T5.4_33	P2	The command and control application MAY create automatic reports at any stage of the incident.	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6	T5.4	Inspection Test
REQ_COM_T5.4_34	P2	The command and control application MAY play back in real time any media content delivered to computers and mobile devices via the internet	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6	T5.4	Inspection Test

Table 2 – Common requirements (optional) - objectives

3.1.1. Structure criteria Methodology (common)

The methodology for the development of the deliverable D5.3 was commonly agreed among the leaders of WP4, WP5 and WP6 and in its basic aspects it is common for deliverables D4.3 and D6.3. NOVOTEC as framework harmonisation and INDRA as project leader supported this process.

The methodology and the structure of this document includes the following sequential steps:

- Taxonomy process
- Clustering of the of identified harmonization opportunities in the deliverables D5.2 (first version) and D5.6 (final version)
- Harmonized analysis of the opportunities, which is based on the feasibility-impact matrix.
- Analysis of the results of the matrix and explanation.
- Opportunities matrix with the results
- Opportunities ranking
- Interdependences with other opportunities
- SWOT analysis
- Roadmap for work package and for opportunity.
- Stakeholders' evaluation
- Conclusions

3.1.2. ID Codification/Traceability (common)

To ensure traceability of gaps, opportunities and grouping of opportunities between WPs. A codification of each of the topics to be addressed has been carried out.

Gaps and opportunities codification

In this deliverable D5.3, the coding of gaps and opportunities established in D5.2 (draft version) and D5.6 (final version) is maintained for ease of reading and to establish a link between the different work packages and deliverables of the Project.

1 st part	2 nd part	3 rd part	4 th part
G=Gap OP= Opportunity	Task number	-	Item number (1..n)
Example			
G	6.1	-	1

Table 3 – ID codification structure for traceability (Gaps and Opportunities)

Clustered Opportunities codification

It has been established a coding for clustered opportunities formed on the basis of the original opportunities. Following the above structure, they are formed according to the following table:

1 st part	2 nd part	3 rd part	4 th part
CO= Clustered Opportunities	Work package number	-	cluster number (1..n)
Example			
CO	WP5	-	1

Table 4 – ID codification structure for traceability (Clustered Opportunities)

3.2. Exclusion criteria (common)

For the initial works on this deliverable, all the gaps and opportunities included in D5.2 (first version) and D5.6 (final version) have been taken into account. Once the ranking of grouped

opportunities is established, according to the methodology described for the present deliverable, the work of the deliverable focuses on the top opportunities selected.

3.3. Experts consultation (common)

The results of the harmonization and pre-standardization tasks have been subjected to internal validation processes with the most expert project researchers in each case, consultation with the External Advisory Board (EAB) and, in some cases, external validation with experts from outside the project.

4. Taxonomy process (common)

Deliverable D2.2 "Terminology and semantics" provides a unified glossary and a map of joint terminologies and semantic representations focused on the specificities of cross-sectoral, cross-border and cross-hierarchical action against European multi-victim disasters. The objective is to support the harmonization, pre-standardization and standardization efforts of first responders in disasters. Deliverable D2.2 has been based on the proposal, debate, discussion and consensus of the different terms, and has been kept alive during the whole life cycle of the Project, serving as a constant reference for the researchers in their work and in the drafting of the respective deliverables.

Following this consensus, for work D5.3, the researchers carried out a review of the terminology used in relation to the statements and contents of the opportunities detected in order to homogenize them. This facilitated not only the grouping of similar opportunities, but also the study of interdependencies between related opportunities inside and outside the WP, a fundamental aspect in the analysis, prioritization and roadmap for the evolution and adoption of new common practices and procedures for first responder responses in the EU environment.

This process has been carried out in the same way in the development of the works leading to deliverables D4.3 and D6.3 of the Project.

5. Clustering opportunities

Valkyries researchers have worked to catalogue, taxonomically homogenize, organize, evaluate similarities and differences, and finally group the individual opportunities collected in deliverable D5.2 / D5.6.

Thus, in this D5.3 a total of 15 clustered opportunities are defined, each containing one or several closely related individual opportunities.

The grouping of these opportunities has been done within each WP (work package) but transcending the aprioristic organization of the Project in tasks. In fact, this process has been carried out taking into account aspects related to methodology, objective, recipients, etc. independently of the WP5 task to which each individual opportunity was initially assigned.

This methodology has been considered not only convenient, but necessary to reflect the reality of the MCI and disaster response EU landscape and to fully explain the scope, impact and complexity of the clustered opportunities analysed.

The decision to change the previous organization of the work of WP5 led to a functional reorganization that, while allowing an agile and efficient progress within each clustered opportunity, did not alter the initial distribution of the efforts committed by the investigators in each of the WP5 tasks.

All the individual opportunities grouped together are listed below, together with the name of the corresponding clustered opportunity in which they have been included.

1. CO.WP5-1: STANDARDISATION OF TERMS IN PLANNING, PREPAREDNESS AND EXECUTION OF THE EMERGENCY RESPONSE
 - OP5.1.1-2: Standardisation of terms and symbols for a common understanding of the situation
 - OP5.1.2-4: Standardisation of terminology and criteria.
2. CO.WP5-2: HARMONIZATION OF EMERGENCY RESPONSE PLANS
 - OP5.1.1-1: Regulatory harmonisation
 - OP5.1.1-3: Adequate revision and updating of emergency plans.
 - OP5.1.1-4: Adequate dissemination and training in relation to emergency plans.
3. CO.WP5-3: HARMONIZATION OF ALERT AND WARNING PROCEDURES IN EMERGENCY RESPONSE
 - OP5.4.2-1: Defining a common approach to disaster early warning
 - OP5.4.2-2: Identifying "high priority public warnings"
 - OP5.4.2-3: Standardisation of alerts procedures and responsibilities in Europe
 - OP5.4.2-4: Standardisation of alerts information and systems in Europe
4. CO.WP5-4: UPDATING OF ALERT AND WARNING MEANS IN EMERGENCY RESPONSE
 - OP5.4.2-5: Technological upgrading of warning systems
 - OP5.4.2-7: Creating and supporting initiatives that fight against misinformation in disasters
 - OP5.4.2-8: Social media analysis of citizens behaviour
5. CO.WP5-5: HARMONIZATION OF EMERGENCY SERVICES
 - OP5.1.2-1: Harmonisation of emergency services structure
 - OP5.1.2-2: Homogenisation of professional competencies in emergencies

6. CO.WP5-6: HARMONIZATION OF COMMAND AND CONTROL PROCEDURES IN EMERGENCY RESPONSE
 - OP5.3-1: Harmonisation of emergency services command competencies among the different EU countries.
 - OP5.3-2: C2 self-adaptive network environment
 - OP5.3-3: Integration of all emergency services into a single emergency operations centre.
 - OP5.3-7: Harmonisation of the emergency command and control system between EU countries.
 7. CO.WP5-7: HARMONIZATION OF OPERATING PROCEDURES IN EMERGENCY RESPONSE
 - OP5.1.2-3: Integrated pre-hospital and hospital MCI plans and operational procedures.
 - OP5.1.2-6: Standardisation of means of triage tagging in MCI.
 - OP5.1.2-7: Standardisation of triage procedures in MCI.
 - OP5.1.2-8: Establishment of consensus and recommendations
 - OP5.3-5: Define criteria for C2 facilities location
 - OP5.3-6: Harmonisation of procedures
 8. CO.WP5-8: HARMONIZATION OF LOGISTIC PROCEDURES IN EMERGENCY PLANNING, PREPAREDNESS AND RESPONSE
 - OP5.2.2-1: Establish cross-border operational plans and procedures.
 - OP5.2.2-2: Homogenisation of logistical resources in disaster response.
 - OP5.2.2-3: Establishment of consensus and recommendations
 9. CO.WP5-9: STANDARDIZATION OF THE EVALUATION IN EMERGENCY PLANNING, PREPAREDNESS AND RESPONSE
 - OP5.1.2-14: Debriefing and evaluation standardization in MCI and disasters
 10. CO.WP5-10: TECHNOLOGICAL UPGRADING OF EMERGENCY SERVICES AND EMERGENCY COORDINATION CENTRES
 - OP5.2.1-2: Technological updating of emergency services
 - OP5.2.1-3: Technological updating of emergency services
 - OP5.2.1-4: ICT technological updating of emergency services
 - OP5.2.1-5: Improving portability
 - OP5.2.1-6: Technological updating of emergency services
 - OP5.2.1-7: Simple and usable solutions that make the first responder's job easier.
 - OP5.2.2-4: Improve national disaster planning and response logistics tools.
 - OP5.3-10: Technological updating of emergency services
 - OP5.3-12: Improving communications
 - OP5.4.1-6: Improving Mission assessments by technological deployments
 - OP5.4.1-7: Improving visualization techniques in MCI and disasters
 11. CO.WP5-11: FOSTERING OF INFORMATION SHARING IN EMERGENCY RESPONSE
 - OP5.4.1-1: Regulatory harmonisation
 - OP5.4.1-2: Fostering a culture of information exchange
 - OP5.4.1-3: Taking volunteers into account
 - OP5.4.1-11: Pay special attention to the safety of first responders.
 12. CO.WP5-12: STANDARDIZATION OF INFORMATION SHARING IN EMERGENCY RESPONSE
 - OP5.1.2-5: Standardisation of the information to be exchanged between disaster managers in the EU.
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- OP5.3-8: Simplify information flow
 - OP5.3-9: Standardisation of the information to be exchanged between disaster managers in the EU.
 - OP5.3-16: Hybrid Digital Twins as a C2 tool
 - OP5.4.1-4: Standardisation of the information to be exchanged between disaster managers in the EU.
 - OP5.4.1-5: C2 applications
 - OP5.4.1-8: On-the-fly generated data representations using advanced, cognitive loop enhancing techniques (dendograms, stream graphs, hive plots...)
 - OP5.4.1-10: Creating a unified COP for MCI and disasters
 - OP5.4.2-6: Hybrid Digital Twins as an alert and warning harmonization tool
13. CO.WP5-13: ESTABLISHING A COMMON FEDERATED SYSTEM FOR SHARING INFORMATION IN EMERGENCY RESPONSE
- OP5.1.1-5: Facilitating EU's Civil Protection Guidelines through a common federated system
 - OP5.1.1-6: Facilitating harmonisation through a common federated system
 - OP5.1.1-7: C2 activation through a common federated system / COP
 - OP5.1.2-9: Facilitating harmonisation through a common federated system
 - OP5.1.2-10: Improving real-time victims' clinical information
 - OP5.1.2-11: Improving vehicles tracking
 - OP5.2.1-1: Improving communications
 - OP5.3-4: Municipality supportive agents' engagement
 - OP5.3-11: Facilitating C2 interoperability through a common federated system
 - OP5.3-13: Blockchain "logbooks"
 - OP5.3-14: Facilitating synchronisation through a common federated system
 - OP5.3-15: Facilitating research through a common federated system
 - OP5.4.1-9: Facilitating a COP through a common federated system
14. CO.WP5-14: UPDATING OF EMERGENCY RESPONSE TRAINING
- OP5.1.2-12: Improving the first responders training
 - OP5.2.2-5: Strengthen logistics expertise
15. CO.WP5-15: STANDARIZATION OF EMERGENCY RESPONSE TRAINING
- OP5.1.2-13: Standardisation of first responders training and certification in Europe

6. Opportunities analysis

6.1. Methodology (common)

It has been necessary to agree on which the most relevant opportunities in the work packages were. The following approach was commonly agreed and used in the opportunities analysis among the WP4, WP5 and WP6 opportunities and partners.

To reach this agreement, a modified Delphi methodology has been used in which the experts are the consortium partners.

The questionnaire consists of a score from 1 to 10 on 13 questions divided into two groups, feasibility and impact.

The questions within the feasibility group are focused on defining how feasible it is to implement the grouped opportunity. Aspects such as the resources or capacities of the system, ethical-legal regulation, technological advances and implementation costs have considered.

Feasibility determining factors evaluated	Contribution
Do the required training and learning processes present a high complexity to be implemented/operated?	8%
Is it possible to achieve a full operational harmonization for opportunities in less than a year for a first responder?	17%
Are there more than three first responders or entities involved to operate, consume or use directly this harmonization opportunity?	17%
Is there technology available to fulfill this opportunity?	17%
In terms of budget, how costly is it to develop, implement or operate this opportunity?	17%
How easy to implement in terms of legislation, ethics, and human rights?	7%
How easy is to verify and validate this opportunity in the whole Valkyries proposal?	17%

Table 5 – Feasibility evaluated factors and relative percentage assigned

The questions within the impact group are focused on defining what the impact of the opportunity would be once implemented. Aspects such as the objective and the target stakeholders for whom it is proposed, or what is expected to happen in the end, must be considered.

Impact determining factors evaluated	Contribution
Is there any environmental/social impact/risk when deploying?	33%
How reusable is across different regions, actors, and scenarios?	14%
Does the impact expected save lives or reduce casualties directly?	14%
Does the expected impact reduce the time to act?	13%
Does the expected impact reduce the risk of mistakes or rework?	13%
Is the expected impact useful to learn for next actuations?	13%

Table 6 – Impact evaluated factors and relative percentage assigned

With the answers to the questions and the appropriate weighting, a score will be obtained for each group. One for feasibility and one for impact. In this way, the opportunity can be placed in a matrix format.

The scores have been used as coordinates that replace the opportunity and locate the opportunity in the matrix. This can identify the opportunities with the best relation.

The result of the analysis in each case would fall into one of the following 4 combinations:

- **Low feasibility / Low impact (THANKLESS TASKS):** these are initiatives that are low recommended because they will not be significant for the desired changes in the system. The realization of these initiatives involves a high degree of difficulty for the implementation and the result will not bring a significant improvement.
- **High feasibility / Low impact (FILL-INS):** these are initiatives that can be implemented quickly and in the short term, but the effect they will have on the desired changes will be marginal and insignificant.
- **Low feasibility / High impact (MAJOR PROJETS):** these are ideas, often disruptive, that are complex to execute. They may require further analysis or follow-up to assess their priority, degree of impact, risks involved in implementing them (or not implementing them), etc.
- **High feasibility / High impact (QUICK WINS):** these are initiatives that can be implemented and executed relatively easily in a short time. They are very valuable because they can generate a significant change in the system.

The feasibility-impact matrix presents the results of the opportunities analysed in a scatter plot where each of the 4 combinations described corresponds to one of the 4 quadrants represented.

Figure 1 - Feasibility-impact matrix quadrants

6.2. Opportunities rating according to the questionnaire

The feasibility-impact evaluation of the clustered opportunities was done by voting, with each partner in the Valkyries consortium having one vote. Internally, each partner decided the value of its votes by consensus among its own researchers.

The results of the analysis for each clustered opportunity are detailed below.

CO.WP5-1.- Standardisation of terms in planning, preparedness and execution of the emergency response		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	It is the grouped opportunity that has obtained the highest score in terms of impact of the 15 opportunities analysed in WP5. The most valued aspects were its applicability in different regions, actors and scenarios, as well as its usefulness in homogenising analysis processes and lessons learned that would translate into better preparedness and a reduction in response time and action in the face of a disaster.	Although it is among the top 6 in terms of feasibility, it scored lower in this one, mainly due to aspects related to the complexity of its adoption in economic terms and the legislative complexity of its generalisation. On the other hand, it is considered that current technological resources would favour the possibility of setting up and making available to those responsible for implementing disaster preparedness and response a common standardised terminology database. However, despite considerable previous standardisation work in relation to terms in emergencies and disasters, these responsible largely do not use standardized terms in their works.
Rating	7,68	5,93

Table 7 – Short analysis: Standardisation of terms in planning, preparedness and execution of the emergency response

Figure 2 - Feasibility-impact results: Standardisation of terms in planning, preparedness and execution of the emergency response

CO.WP5-2.- Harmonization of emergency response plans		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	The goal of harmonizing and defining emergency response plans is to enable a more organized and effective response to crises by reducing uncertainty and delays, finding commonalities and best practices among existing plans, and developing a shared crisis action strategy. This results in increased	Although there may be some difficulties and constraints in putting this process into practice, it is nevertheless considered useful to work on harmonisation to improve communication and collaboration between response teams during crises, improve coordination and reduce misunderstandings and delays.

CO.WP5-2.- Harmonization of emergency response plans		
	reaction team communication and collaboration, which leads to better outcomes for those impacted by crises.	
Rating	7,61	5,17

Table 8 – Short analysis: Harmonization of emergency response plans

Figure 3 - Feasibility-impact results: Harmonization of emergency response plans

CO.WP5-3.- Harmonization of alert and warning procedures in emergency response		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	The purpose of alerts and warnings is to provide the necessary information prior to the incident and notify the population of these threats to minimize the risks and danger. Our short analysis highlights high impact with the development of measures that homogenize and standardise plans, procedures and tools related with alerts and warning.	In European Countries there is a high availability of plans, procedures and tools for alerts and warnings, and there are technological means available to support it, but there is also a great diversity of practices and there is no homogeneity in relation to the agencies responsible for warning and alerting the population in case of disasters. Implementing this harmonization requires that alerts and warning of MCI incident should be understandable and common at European level, and subsequently at a national and local level, which makes their feasibility difficult.
Rating	6,74	5,85

Table 9 – Short analysis: Harmonization of alert and warning procedures in emergency response

Figure 4 - Feasibility-impact results: Harmonization of alert and warning procedures in emergency response

CO.WP5-4.- Updating of alert and warning means in emergency response		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	A technological approach is the great advantage in the development of alert and warning systems. Adequate upgrading of technologies resources of Emergency System and Alert and Warning System and a one more cohesive and comprehensive alert and warning system that integrates public and private communication mechanism and information source results in a great impact.	Alert and warning systems exist within a broader technical and communication ecosystem, and systems designed and maintained by governments must fit into this broader ecosystem but at the same time they are still supported by technological means that are far from those offered by the current state of technology. This evolution will need to be based on both technical research and social and behavioural science research. There may be a need for additional equipment or infrastructure to be installed to support the new technology. Training and learning process to use this new technology.
Rating	6,61	5,58

Table 10 – Short analysis: Updating of alert and warning means in emergency response

Figure 5 - Feasibility-impact results: Updating of alert and warning procedures in emergency response

CO.WP5-5.- Harmonization of emergency services		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	<p>The need of integrating and coordinating emergency care across several agencies cannot be overstated. Firefighters are often well-equipped to give emergency medical care. In addition, firefighters give more emergency medical care than others in several countries. Consequently, harmonization between emergency services in the same incident will result in the most effective incident execution.</p>	<p>Often arriving before EMS personnel, police officers and firefighters are the first professional participants to a serious injury or illness. Basic life support (BLS) training for these responders is essential, as is close collaboration and training among professionals for rescue in various types of incidents. There is agreement that first responders should have a similar level of training and that all mobile units of these services should be equipped with at least an automated external defibrillator.</p>
Rating	6,39	5,24

Table 11 – Short analysis: Harmonization of emergency services

Figure 6 - Feasibility-impact results: Harmonization of emergency services

CO.WP5-6.- Harmonization of command and control procedures in emergency response		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	<p>The need of harmonization of command and control procedures in emergency response comes from need to enhance the current EUCPM system by defining a harmonised EU C2 system. This harmonization of EU C2 systems would have an impact at: 1. Incident Commander supported by other responders or officers involved in response would have an overall response for</p>	<p>The position of Incident Commander varies across European countries. In most countries, firefighters are the first on site and lead the incident. In some countries Incident Commanders are other first responders. Thus the harmonization is difficult to ensure, taking into consideration that various first responders follow different procedures in emergency response. For the limited timeframe of VALKYRIES project, this opportunity is not feasible to be implemented.</p>

CO.WP5-6.- Harmonization of command and control procedures in emergency response		
	the incident. 2. Incident site would be divided into sectors. Incident Commander	
Rating	7,01	5,09

Table 12 – Short analysis: Harmonization of command and control procedures in emergency response

Figure 7 - Feasibility-impact results: Harmonization of command and control procedures in emergency response

CO.WP5-7.- Harmonization of operating procedures in emergency response		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	The harmonisation of operational procedures in emergency response was the clustered opportunity with the highest overall impact-feasibility score in the evaluation conducted within the project, especially due to the high degree of impact it is logically estimated to have on response effectiveness, error reduction and ultimately saving lives.	On the other hand, it has a really low feasibility rating, which is in line with the very heterogeneous scenario we have seen in the EU with regard to the standard operating procedures of the emergency services. It is estimated that the time needed for progress in this area to have a real impact on first responders would be long and the processes of dissemination, implementation and training complex. However, it is considered that the new technical capabilities already available today could provide an important opportunity for progress, even within the limited timeframe of the Valkyries project itself.
Rating	7,41	5,20

Table 13 – Short analysis: Harmonization of operating procedures in emergency response

Figure 8 - Feasibility-impact results: Harmonization of operating procedures in emergency response

CO.WP5-8.- Harmonization of logistic procedures in emergency planning, preparedness and response		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	Logistic procedures can significantly hinder response operations, especially in the face of cross-border incidents, which require the activation of different agencies. The efficient and timely disposition of such procedures prior to the occurrence of a MCI can significantly increase response capabilities and reduce the needed time to act.	The documentation of logistic procedures in a unified registry, where emergency plans of first responders' organisation are included, is very important for the coordinated response to and management of a MCI. Through this registration of logistic procedures, double work can be avoided and thus, response times can be minimised. Moreover, this opportunity is very low cost and can be easily applied, requiring minimum training for its adoption by first responders.
Rating	6,67	5,58

Table 14 – Short analysis: Harmonization of logistic procedures in emergency planning, preparedness and response

Figure 9 - Feasibility-impact results: Harmonization of logistic procedures in emergency planning, preparedness and response

CO.WP5-9.- Standardization of the evaluation in emergency planning, preparedness and response		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	Actions to assess and continuously improve the emergency response plans can identify threats, determine vulnerabilities, define risk levels, create evacuation procedures for users and staff, and develop common action plans to minimize response time in assisting the injured and	It is important to design a comprehensive competency-based education program where assessment is the driver of learning, the guarantee of patient safety and ultimately an ethical act. It requires access to qualitative performance information, which implies professional judgement and expert consensus. Performance is assessed under real conditions, not in simulations. These methods are based on observation, self-assessment, monitoring and care activities,

CO.WP5-9.- Standardization of the evaluation in emergency planning, preparedness and response		
	facilitating the accession of staff from other regions if necessary.	should facilitate formative assessment and be easy to apply.
Rating	6,54	5,97

Table 15 – Short analysis: Standardization of the evaluation in emergency planning, preparedness and response

Figure 10 - Feasibility-impact results: Standardization of the evaluation in emergency planning, preparedness and response

CO.WP5-10.- Technological upgrading of emergency services and emergency coordination centres		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	This opportunity has potential benefits such as a better coordination and communication to guarantee faster emergency response times. On the other hand, upgraded technology can provide emergency services with better situational awareness to identify potential risks and allocate resources more effectively. In addition, this upgrading can facilitate the collection and analysis of data to identify trend or anticipate risks.	The existing infrastructure must be sufficient and compatible with the new technology, on the contrary, there may be a need for additional equipment or infrastructure to be installed to support the new technology. In addition, all groups must go through a training and learning process to use this new technology, since it can incorporate new functionalities that are new to people.
Rating	6,88	4,58

Table 16 – Short analysis: Technological upgrading of emergency services and emergency coordination centres

Figure 11 - Feasibility-impact results: Technological upgrading of emergency services and emergency coordination centres

CO.WP5-11.- Fostering of information sharing in emergency response		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	Information sharing in emergency responses is vital both on victims handling (triage, transportations, hospital awareness, etc.) as well as related with other tactical information related with the incident and its evolution on the field	The COP mapping of all such information and the COP sharing between different C2 (within a country or in cross-border incidents) is the most practical and effective method to resolve many communication issues and problems between agencies involved.
Rating	6,43	5,88

Table 17 – Short analysis: Fostering of information sharing in emergency response

Figure 12 - Feasibility-impact results: Fostering of information sharing in emergency response

CO.WP5-12.- Standardization of information sharing in emergency response		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	Standardisation of the basic information to be collected in relation to each victim has an impact on guaranteeing traceability and continuity of care for those affected in a disaster, even more so	Implementation only requires agreement between experts from different provinces, countries and first responders. All groups will be able to continue working as before, only agreeing on what information to share

CO.WP5-12.- Standardization of information sharing in emergency response		
	in cross-border disasters. Standardisation of what every data means and what basic data is need. Focusing on ensuring the traceability, about errors and make communication more fluent.	with each other and what that information means. Therefore, this standardisation requires no extra work or training for the first responder. No special technology is required. The implementation budget is low.
Rating	7,53	6,00

Table 18 – Short analysis: Standardization of information sharing in emergency response

Figure 13 - Feasibility-impact results: Standardization of information sharing in emergency response

CO.WP5-13.- Establishing a common federated system for sharing information in emergency response		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	By establishing a common data model to support interoperability between different entities in a federated concept, provide a high level of flexibility and resilience for multiple forces to cooperate. This allows for the data sharing and build an integrated situational awareness, even of each entity has its own applications and systems. Also, provides a mean to incorporate potential legacy systems, and to reduce the costs on long term emergency system operations. It also provides a high level of expansibility and scalability and easy for new forces to plug-in into the model.	The implementation of the common federated model in its full range is complex. A simple and more basic implementation is feasible. The components related to the data model and data sharing provides a simple interface, but each entity must adapt his applications to VALKYRIES interface regarding data production and data consumption. It also needs to manage roles and maps end-user roles to the federation roles, which may add some, but not much, complexity. On the other hand, the full gateway includes managing different networks data flows with different raw data frequencies, formats and rates, is quite demanding and has a low feasibility under the project time frame.

CO.WP5-13.- Establishing a common federated system for sharing information in emergency response		
Rating	7,47	5,85

Table 19 – Short analysis: Establishing a common federated system for sharing information in emergency response

Figure 14 - Feasibility-impact results: Establishing a common federated system for sharing information in emergency response

CO.WP5-14.- Updating of emergency response training		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	Implementation of this capability will create a set of common competencies and skills for all teams and users working to support victims in emergency situations. Good interoperability in the case of MCI is a fundamental requirement that can be achieved through joint training, common programs and standards, common scenario training and joint exercises.	There are no such specific training courses at EU level. In order to implement this possibility, a definition of a minimum set of competences and skills that should be acquired by learners to be effective and successful in the case of cross-border MCI should be created. Develop an online and on-site training program for first responders to successfully collaborate with all first responder partners.
Rating	6,26	5,93

Table 20 – Short analysis: Updating of emergency response training

Figure 15 - Feasibility-impact results: Updating of emergency response training

CO.WP5-15.- Standardisation of emergency response training		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	If this opportunity is realized, it will improve the joint multinational training of the various teams and representatives involved in operations in the area of disasters and emergency situations. This will help them to use joint standardized capabilities to carry out activities in different cross-border MCIs, thus ensuring high efficiency and effectiveness of actions, high coordination and interaction.	Introducing uniform standards in the training of all participants is too complex a task. A simple and more complex implementation is possible. Building knowledge and skills according to uniform standards does not always lead to the same final results. Within the VALKYRIES project it is possible to outline the minimum requirements for the competences, knowledge and skills to be acquired in the training process in order to guarantee a good efficiency of interaction and coordination of the efforts of all participants in the disaster area. Achieving standardization in joint training and uniform requirements for all is quite an ambitious task and has low feasibility within the project's time frame.
Rating	6,41	5,92

Table 21 – Short analysis: Standardisation of emergency response training

Figure 16 - Feasibility-impact results: Standardisation of emergency response training

6.3. Opportunities matrix

The feasibility-impact scores obtained for each clustered opportunity are shown below on the graph of the feasibility-impact matrix. As can be seen in the matrix image, almost all of the clustered opportunities listed in WP5 fall into the high feasibility and high impact quadrant. That is to say, they would constitute what are called “quick wins”.

Figure 17 – WP5 clustered opportunities feasibility-impact matrix

The following table shows the results of the analysis of the clustered opportunities in a focused way and highlighting the top 6 ones.

Figure 18 – Focused WP5 clustered opportunities feasibility-impact matrix

7. Opportunity ranking

The following table shows the final feasibility-impact ranking with the partial and total scores obtained by each clustered opportunity proposed in WP5.

Order	Cl. opp code	Clustered opportunity name	Feasibility	Impact	Total score
1	CO.WP5-1	STANDARDISATION OF TERMS IN PLANNING, PREPAREDNESS AND EXECUTION OF THE EMERGENCY RESPONSE	5,93	7,68	13,61
2	CO.WP5-12	STANDARDIZATION OF INFORMATION SHARING IN EMERGENCY RESPONSE	6,00	7,53	13,53
3	CO.WP5-13	ESTABLISHING A COMMON FEDERATED SYSTEM FOR SHARING INFORMATION IN EMERGENCY RESPONSE	5,85	7,47	13,32
4	CO.WP5-2	HARMONIZATION OF EMERGENCY RESPONSE PLANS	5,17	7,61	12,78
5	CO.WP5-7	HARMONIZATION OF OPERATING PROCEDURES IN EMERGENCY RESPONSE	5,20	7,41	12,61
6	CO.WP5-3	HARMONIZATION OF ALERT AND WARNING PROCEDURES IN EMERGENCY RESPONSE	5,85	6,74	12,59
7	CO.WP5-9	STANDARDIZATION OF THE EVALUATION IN EMERGENCY PLANNING, PREPAREDNESS AND RESPONSE	5,97	6,54	12,51
8	CO.WP5-15	STANDARIZATION OF EMERGENCY RESPONSE TRAINING	5,92	6,41	12,32
9	CO.WP5-11	FOSTERING OF INFORMATION SHARING IN EMERGENCY RESPONSE	5,88	6,43	12,31
10	CO.WP5-8	HARMONIZATION OF LOGISTIC PROCEDURES IN EMERGENCY PLANNING, PREPAREDNESS AND RESPONSE	5,58	6,67	12,25
11	CO.WP5-14	UPDATING OF EMERGENCY RESPONSE TRAINING	5,93	6,26	12,19
12	CO.WP5-4	UPDATING OF ALERT AND WARNING MEANS IN EMERGENCY RESPONSE	5,58	6,61	12,19
13	CO.WP5-6	HARMONIZATION OF COMMAND AND CONTROL PROCEDURES IN EMERGENCY RESPONSE	5,09	7,01	12,10
14	CO.WP5-5	HARMONIZATION OF EMERGENCY SERVICES	5,24	6,39	11,63
15	CO.WP5-10	TECHNOLOGICAL UPGRADING OF EMERGENCY SERVICES AND EMERGENCY COORDINATION CENTRES	4,58	6,88	11,45

Table 22 – Final WP5 clustered opportunities ranking

Based on the measurable results committed to in the Valkyries project, the 6 clustered opportunities with the highest total feasibility-impact score have been selected to develop a more comprehensive analysis, elaborate proposals and propose the consequent roadmap for their achievement in the EU environment. As can be seen in the table, the top 6 clustered opportunities were as follows: CO.WP5-1, CO.WP5-12, CO.WP5-13, CO.WP5-2, CO.WP5-7, CO.WP5-3.

In order to follow a logical order that favours the reading and understanding of deliverable D5.3, it has been considered appropriate to develop the top 6 clustered opportunities in the following order in the document:

- CO.WP5-1: Standardisation of terms in planning, preparedness and execution of the emergency response
- CO.WP5-2: Harmonization of emergency response plans
- CO.WP5-7: Harmonization of operating procedures in emergency response
- CO.WP5-12: Standardization of information sharing in emergency response
- CO.WP5-13: Establishing a common federated system for sharing information in emergency response
- CO.WP5-3: Harmonization of alert and warning procedures in emergency response

8. Identify interdependences

As an interdependence, we consider "the condition of two or more things depending on each other" as the Cambridge Dictionary defines it. This condition can easily be identified in the opportunities of WP5.

More specifically, interdependences were identified both within the opportunities of the WP5 and between different work packages as well. The following sections analyse this interdependence condition.

8.1. Inside of the WP5

The next table is a summary of the interdependence between WP5 opportunities.

Opportunity	Interdependences WP5/5					
	CO.WP5.1	CO.WP5.2	CO.WP5.7	CO.WP5.12	CO.WP5.13	CO.WP5.3
CO.WP5-1: Standardisation of terms in planning, preparedness and execution of the emergency response			X	X		
CO.WP5-2: Harmonization of emergency response plans	X				X	X
CO.WP5-7: Harmonization of operating procedures in emergency response	X			X		
CO.WP5-12: Standardization of information sharing in emergency response	X	X	X			
CO.WP5-13: Establishing a common federated system for sharing information in emergency response				X		
CO.WP5-3: Harmonization of alert and warning procedures in emergency response	X		X		X	

Table 23 – Dependency between opportunities within WP5

The following figure summarises graphically the interdependence between the opportunities within the WP5. A detailed description of the interdependence is described below.

Figure 19 – Interdependences within WP5

8.1.1. CO.WP5-1: Standardisation of terms in planning, preparedness and execution of the emergency response

CO.WP5-7. Harmonization of operating procedures in emergency response: It is essential for the harmonisation of procedures that the terms used in the development of procedures are standardised. This avoids confusion between agencies with different function or origin.

CO.WP5-12. Standardization of information sharing in emergency response: During an emergency, it should be standardised what information should be exchanged between agencies, and this information should be based on previously standardised terms, so that common terms are used throughout all phases of the emergency.

8.1.2. CO.WP5-2: Harmonization of emergency response plans

CO.WP5-1. Standardisation of terms in planning, preparedness and execution of the emergency response: The aim of CO.WP5-2 is to create a Unified Registry of Emergency Operations and Plans. Therefore, the registry will contain specific fields and terms that need to be standardised and will provide crucial specifications and information regarding operational plans among different first responders' organisations operating in the field.

CO.WP5-3. Harmonization of alert and warning procedures in emergency response: The addition of specific fields and modules related to the METHANE incident report would be appropriate for the under development unified registry.

CO.WP5-13. Establishing a common federated system for sharing information in emergency response: This opportunity dictates that the SGRUN system will be used for the federation of the information exchange at an EU level. Through SGRUN the information related to the registry

of operational plans could be efficiently exchanged allowing for better coordination between different stakeholders operating at the scene of the disaster.

8.1.3. CO.WP5-7: Harmonization of operating procedures in emergency response

CO.WP5-1: Standardisation of terms in planning, preparedness and execution of the emergency response: The development of standardised procedures should be based on the use of common terminology, which facilitates interoperability between different agencies.

CO.WP5-12: Standardization of information sharing in emergency response: One of the aspects contained in the operational procedures is command and control, so the information displayed and needed for decision making must be standardised.

8.1.4. CO.WP5-12: Standardization of information sharing in emergency response

CO.WP5-1: Standardization of terms in planning, preparedness and execution of the emergency response: Information shared in emergency response should cover all the phases of the response, from planning to execution. The standardization should be built around the data model that supports the data sharing.

CO.WP5-2: Harmonization of emergency response plans: Information shared in emergency response planning should be harmonized in support of the different entities to understand and easy coordination. For that purpose, the plans data should be harmonized so that can support a common standard.

CO.WP5-7: Harmonization of operating procedures in emergency response: Information shared in emergency response operational procedures should be harmonized in support of the different entities towards an easy coordination. For that purpose, the operational procedures and data should be harmonized so that can support a common standard, supported by well-defined procedures of the SIGRUN Operational centre.

8.1.5. CO.WP5-13: Establishing a common federated system for sharing information in emergency response

CO.WP5-12: Standardization of information sharing in emergency response: The establishment of the common federated system for sharing emergency response information requires a standard data taxonomy, syntax, and data model. Aiming to assist the decision making of C2 of all involved agents (including in cross-border incidents)

8.1.6. CO.WP5-3: Harmonization of alert and warning procedures in emergency response

CO.WP5-1: Standardisation of terms in planning, preparedness and execution of the emergency response: This harmonization includes alerts and warning.

CO.WP5-7: Harmonization of operating procedures in emergency response: Information shared in emergency response operational procedures should be harmonized in support of the different entities. For that purpose, the alerts and warning procedures and data related should be harmonized so that can support a common standard

CO.WP5-13: Establishing a common federated system for sharing information in emergency response: As critical information between all linked federated systems (considered as tactical information), need to be exchanged between different C2 of involved agents, the designed standards in alerts and warning issued, mapped and shared.

8.2. Between WPs

The following tables summarise the interdependence of the opportunities in WP5 with those in WP4 and WP6.

Opportunity	Interdependences WP5/4						
	CO.WP4.2	CO.WP4.12	CO.WP4.15	CO.WP4.21	CO.WP4.28	CO.WP4.42	CO.WP4.55
CO.WP5-1: Standardisation of terms in planning, preparedness and execution of the emergency response							
CO.WP5-2: Harmonization of emergency response plans							
CO.WP5-7: Harmonization of operating procedures in emergency response	X						X
CO.WP5-12: Standardization of information sharing in emergency response	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
CO.WP5-13: Establishing a common federated system for sharing information in emergency response		X	X	X	X	X	X
CO.WP5-3: Harmonization of alert and warning procedures in emergency response							

Table 24 – Dependency between WP5 and WP4 opportunities

Opportunity	Interdependences WP5/6				
	CO.WP6.2	CO.WP6.5	CO.WP6.7	CO.WP6.10	CO.WP6.11
CO.WP5-1: Standardisation of terms in planning, preparedness and execution of the emergency response		X	X	X	X
CO.WP5-2: Harmonization of emergency response plans		X		X	X
CO.WP5-7: Harmonization of operating procedures in emergency response		X		X	X
CO.WP5-12: Standardization of information sharing in emergency response			X		
CO.WP5-13: Establishing a common federated system for sharing information in emergency response	X		X		
CO.WP5-3: Harmonization of alert and warning procedures in emergency response		X	X	X	X

Table 25 – Dependency between WP5 and WP6 opportunities

The following figure summarises graphically the dependency between the opportunities with WP4 and WP6 that are detailed in the following subchapters.

Figure 20 – Interdependencies of WP5 with WP4 and WP6

8.2.1. CO.WP5-1: Standardisation of terms in planning, preparedness and execution of the emergency response

CO.WP6-5. Standardization of education and training for first aid responses (Creation of a Training kit: curriculum, methodology and training manual): The use of standardised terms in education and training programmes will encourage the terminology to be used by the trainees, adopted in the development of operating procedures and used by first responders in emergency response. This is a first step in the chain of standardisation.

CO.WP6-7. Use of Virtual Operation Support Teams (VOSTs): All those involved in the emergency response, whether responders or support staff, should use the same terminology as this improves coordination between teams and facilitates the understanding of the messages issued.

CO.WP6-10. Using common procedures and standards for training and civil-military actions: In many countries there is no smooth civil-military collaboration. However, in major disasters, the armed forces are relied upon to intervene in civil emergencies. The fact that there is no common language at the civil-military level makes coordination and cooperation between institutions in already very complicated situations difficult.

CO.WP6-11. Minimum set of competencies and skills for volunteers and integration in the field operational procedures: The use of standardised terminology when drafting programmes allows them to be homogenised and for volunteers who may be involved in emergency response to be truly integrated into the civil protection system.

8.2.2. CO.WP5-2: Harmonization of emergency response plans

CO.WP6.11. Minimum set of competencies and skills for volunteers and integration in the field operational procedures with adequate field exercise program and adequate protection with risk-free activities: Volunteers play an important role in the management of crises and can greatly facilitate the work of first responders. Moreover, the registration of the skills and competence of volunteers in the unified registry, which is going to be developed in the context of CO.WP5-2, can provide to the professionals, working on the field, a clear view of the capacity and capabilities of volunteering organisations and appropriate capitalization of their resources.

CO.WP6.5. Standardisation of education and training for first aid responses (Creation of a Training kit: curriculum, methodology and training manual): Response plans are crucial for the effective management of and response to MCIs. These plans have to be an integrated and inextricable part of first aid responders' training and education and thus, should be included in the training kit of CO.WP6.5.

CO.WP6.10. Using common procedures and standards for training and civil-military actions: The exchange of information regarding the operational plans of different organizations, either civil or military, will facilitate response operations. The registration of such plans and procedures in the unified registry, proposed under the framework of CO.WP5.2, and their digitalization through the SIGRUN platform will provide insight and enhancement of the overall response capacity.

8.2.3. CO.WP5-7: Harmonization of operating procedures in emergency response

CO.WP4.2: Logistics assistances using UAVs: Harmonized operating procedures will give one common system regarding registration of demands, update of status and so forth. One system will simplify a common logistic assistance system.

CO.WP4.55: Use of wearable to support triage: The sharing of the emergency response victim's locations/status and vehicle's location should follow a common method as defined in the SIGRUN. When linked with existing triage supportive systems, then the range of victims track&trace is upgraded starting from "Ground 0". Each entity sharing the victim or vehicle information should report the last know position and its last know position time (which may be different from the time of the sharing) whilst GDPR related issues are resolved due to blockchain recoding of such data through the SIGRUN architecture system.

CO.WP6-5. Standardization of education and training for first aid responses (Creation of a Training kit: curriculum, methodology and training manual): All operational procedures require a training plan for their implementation in the different services. Standardised training plans ensure that the way procedures are implemented is also standardised, which allows the level of education and training of first responders to be homogeneous.

CO.WP6-10. Using common procedures and standards for training and civil-military actions: Emergency response often requires the involvement of armed forces in cross-border emergencies. To facilitate civil-military cooperation and interoperability, services should include in their operational procedures how to act in the event of such cooperation, as well as common standards for such situations.

CO.WP6-11. Minimum set of competencies and skills for volunteers and integration in the field operational procedures: The operational procedures of the emergency services integrate groups

of volunteers who perform functions in different action groups, so it is important that their competencies and skills are defined.

8.2.4. CO.WP5-12: Standardization of information sharing in emergency response

Critical information between all linked federated systems (considered as tactical information) need to be exchanged between different C2 of involved agents, the designed standards in:

- Minimum data sets exchanged
- APIs linking federated systems
- Synchronization of all data exchanges through the same clock
- Logging of all exchanged transactions, data and metadata of streaming files in blockchain networks, providing security, transparency and GDPR compliance
- External sources data feeds into the SIGRUN system shared
- Exchange of information following bi-lateral agreements and restrictions between countries in cross-border incidents
- Warnings and Alerts issued mapped and shared
- Introduction of standardised procedures in SIGRUN Operational centre to reduce risks (cybersecurity, operational)

A dynamic path to introduce common and harmonized workflow and procedures in all circle (planning, execution, follow-up/evaluation) is created, as the concepts of Situational Awareness (SA) and Common Operational Picture (COP) are closely related and well-acknowledged to be crucial factors for effective emergency management.

In multi-agency operations, such as extreme weather events, the involved first responders manage the event with different mandates, objectives, and tools which can make it challenging to build a COP. Effective collaboration requires a common situational understanding, based on knowledge about each other's responsibilities and tasks, mutual respect and trust, as well as common communication tools for emergency communication and information sharing.

As so the COP sharing serves as a basis for deciding on further action, and thus represents a first stage in the process of establishing common situational understanding among the involved actors. The empirical basis for such result incorporates processes involved in establishing a COP as a basis for common situational understanding.

CO.WP4.2: Logistics assistances using UAVs: A system running this type of logistic assistance need one standard for information sharing. This opportunity will solve parts of this.

CO.WP4.12. Reduce voice communication, digitalizing most information exchanges: The federated data model defines a way of sharing data, both in terms of data model and communication protocols. Reducing voice communication means digitalizing the data and sending them according to the federated model.

CO.WP4.15. Location of near/nearest vehicles: The emergency information to be shared regarding the vehicle's location should be done via a standardized common data structure, and follow the same taxonomy and semantics, or when not possible a translation between them should be adopted.

CO.WP4.21: Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms: The objective of this opportunity is to store data obtained in emergency situations. These data will be based on the

minimum data set established in WP5. From this set and adding new data, we will store enough information from emergencies

CO.WP4.28. Cross border data trace: Cross border data sharing can be supported in common standardised EU legal frame and model.

CO.WP4.42: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information exchanges:

The incident-related information transmitted in digital form is in accordance with the data structure defined in SIGRUN which proposes standardisation data sets. The datasets are designed to share information between Agencies and between countries related to the incident. Therefore, all information that goes from being transmitted via voice to being digitised and shared on the platform must follow the rules of the SIGRUN data model and the established communication protocols.

CO.WP4.55. Use of wearable to support triage: In order to share the triage Wearables data, the emergency response information model could provide a common standard for the taxonomy used.

CO.WP6.7. Use of Virtual Operation Support Teams (VOSTs): VOSTs gather information from social networks (inputs and outputs) and this process requires standardization of shared information.

8.2.5. CO.WP5-13: Establishing a common federated system for sharing information in emergency response

CO.WP4.12. Reduce Voice Communication, digitalizing most information exchanges: Reducing voice communication involves using data digitization applications that transmit information over alternative networks (4G, 5G, local Wi-Fi) and automate manual data collection. The SIGRUN proposal defines the interoperability model between these new mobile applications that can be developed, and the Command and Control Post as well as the Datasets that allow data sharing between Agencies and at cross-border level.

CO.WP4.15. Location of near/nearest vehicles: The emergency information to be shared regarding the vehicle's location should be done via a standardized common data structure, and follow the same taxonomy and semantics, or when not possible a translation between them should be adopted.

CO.WP4.21: Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms: The main dependency we have with this opportunity is the data that is exchanged between the different systems, we depend on the data that the different sources share and send to the central platform

CO.WP4.28. Cross border data trace: Cross border data sharing can be supported in common standardised EU legal frame and model.

CO.WP4.42: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information exchanges: The federated data model defines a way of sharing data, both in terms of data model and communication protocols.

CO.WP4.55. Use of wearable to support triage: In order to share the triage Wearables data, the emergency response information model could provide a common standard for the taxonomy used.

CO.WP6.2. Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data: A common cryptography mechanism is required to establish a federated sharing system.

CO.WP6.7. Use of Virtual Operation Support Teams (VOSTs): All the inputs and outputs from VOSTs need to pass through the common federated system for sharing information in emergency response.

8.2.6. CO.WP5-3: Harmonization of alert and warning procedures in emergency response

CO.WP6.5: Standardization of education and training for first aid responses (Creation of a Training kit: curriculum, methodology and training manual). Also, Knowledge in alerts and warnings must be included.

CO.WP6-7. Use of Virtual Operation Support Teams (VOSTs) These teams are made up of professionals from the world of emergencies who collaborate altruistically with the accounts of the emergency services on Twitter in the monitoring of social networks to go viral prevention messages and the detection of hoaxes

CO.WP6.10: Using common procedures and standards for training and civil-military action.

CO.WP6.11: Minimum set of competencies and skills for volunteers and integration in the field operational procedures. It must understand knowledge in alerts and warnings.

These clustered opportunities are related to alerts and warnings in their social awareness aspect, and we can be divided into 3 parts:

- Pre-incident awareness: involving preparation and prevention tasks
- Awareness during the incident: public information and population management consisting of early warning of population, informing disabled people, informing people who are only visiting nature and are not familiar with the area, evacuation, etc.)
- Post-incident awareness: recruitment and management of volunteers to search for missing people, management of evacuated population for their return, rehabilitation of damaged infrastructure.

9. SWOT (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats) evaluation of top ranked opportunities

SWOT analysis is a technique widely used in business to analyse a situation in order to make the right strategic decisions.

It is a systematic approach that facilitates analysis by distinguishing between the pros and cons of both the external and internal environment. In this way, 4 areas are defined which correspond to the acronym SWOT:

- **Strengths:** They bring together the set of internal resources, positions of power and any type of competitive advantage specific to the agent under study.
- **Weaknesses:** These are the internal aspects that limit the development capacity of the agent under study, due to its internal characteristics.
- **Opportunities:** These are any factors external to the agent under study that favour its development or offer the possibility of implementing improvements.
- **Threats:** These are all the external factors that could prevent the implementation of a strategy or jeopardise the viability of a proposal.

It can be represented graphically in 4 quadrants:

Figure 21 – 22SWOT matrix

This systematic SWOT approach has been applied by the project researchers to the assessment of the EU environment for each of the top 6 selected clustered opportunities.

Each analysis is preceded by a brief summary of the current EU landscape encountered in the previous phases of the project and includes a review of the main harmonisation efforts undertaken to date, all in relation to the specific scope of the clustered opportunities assessed.

9.1. CO.WP-1: Standardisation of terms in planning, preparedness and execution of the emergency response

9.1.1. Summary of the current situation in the EU

According to Sakkas et al. (2020)¹, common symbology and terminology is a crucial gap that needs to be filled through ongoing and future standardisation activities. It is true that there is a variety of standards related to disaster management terminology and symbology, but despite this, the first responders consider the issue of terminology to be a gap. Tsaloukidis et al. (2022)² attribute this to the fact that, among other factors, first responders seem reluctant to change the way they are used to operating.

The establishment and effective use of standardised terminology at EU level for emergency and disaster planning, preparedness and response is essential. There are several reasons for this:

- It ensures clarity and consistency in communication among professionals in the field. When different terms are used to describe the same thing, it can create confusion and misunderstandings, especially in high-pressure situations where quick and accurate communication is critical. A standardized terminology system would ensure that everyone uses the same language and understands what is meant by specific terms.
- Standardization promotes efficiency in emergency and disaster response. In a crisis, time is of the essence, and the use of standardized terminology helps to ensure that actions are taken quickly and in a coordinated manner. It enables emergency responders to communicate effectively with each other, other agencies, and the public.
- It helps to enhance interoperability between different countries' emergency services. In a globalized world, disasters often cross-national borders, and international cooperation is crucial for an effective response. For instance, zoning is an essential aspect in the management of multi-casualty incidents in order to properly and efficiently organise the response to the accident at the scene. However, the definition of working zones differs between the different countries and agencies involved in a disaster according to the specific needs of the institutions: security, fire and rescue, health care. Standardized terminology facilitates the exchange of information and ensures that all parties involved have a common understanding of key concepts.
- A standardized terminology system provides a basis for training and education in the field. It enables professionals to develop a common language and understanding of the key concepts, which can be used to develop training materials, curricula, and certification programs.
- It can improve public confidence and trust in emergency and disaster response. When people hear consistent and clear messaging from emergency responders, it can help to reduce panic and uncertainty, and promote public trust in the response effort.
- Finally, standardizing terminology at the EU level can help to align emergency and disaster planning, preparedness, and response across member states, leading to a more

¹ Sakkas, G., Tsaloukidis, I., Kazantzidou-Firtinidou, D., Pelekanou, V., Papathanasiou, C., Varela, V., Kadena, K., Woitsch, P., Oien, K., Katsoulakos, K., Altenpohl, A., Filzmaier, L.K., Radchuk, O., Kalli, J., Mariblanca, A.M., Stomff, S., Popa, C., Gothe, F., Antunes, W., Reuge E., Philpot, J. "Standardisation Landscape: Gaps and Opportunities", 2020.

² Tsaloukidis, I., Sakkas, G., Fresu, G., Pronto, L., Hybbeneth, N. "Results of the Request for Ideas: mapping RTOs and Industry potential, response and trends related to Fire-IN CCC/FCCCs #3", 2022, <https://www.fire-in.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/05/D3.4.-Results-of-the-Request-for-Ideas-mapping-RTOs-and-Industry-potential-response-and-trends-related-to-Fire-IN-CCC-FCCS-3.pdf>

coherent and effective approach to dealing with crises. This can lead to more effective responses and better outcomes for those affected by disasters.

In conclusion, the standardization of terminology used by professionals in the field of emergency and disaster planning, preparedness, and response at the EU level is crucial for promoting clarity and consistency in communication, improving efficiency and interoperability, enhancing education and training, improving public confidence and trust, and aligning approaches across member states.

9.1.2. Review of previous harmonization, homogenization and standardization efforts

The standardization of terminology used in emergency response planning, preparedness, and execution is an ongoing effort at both national and international levels. There are several initiatives and organizations working towards developing and promoting standardized terminology in this field.

ISO

One of the most prominent organizations working on this issue is the International Organization for Standardization (ISO). The ISO has developed several standards related to emergency management, including ISO 22320, which provides guidelines for emergency management terminology, and ISO 22319, which focuses specifically on terminology related to the management of incident response.

The following ISO standards are related to the standardization of terms in emergency response planning, preparedness, and execution:

- ISO 22300:2018 - Societal security - Terminology: This standard provides general terminology related to societal security, which includes emergency management.
- ISO 22315:2014 - Societal security - Mass evacuation - Guidelines for planning: This standard provides guidelines for planning and implementing mass evacuations, including the use of standardized terminology.
- ISO 22316:2017 - Organizational resilience - Principles and attributes: This standard provides principles and attributes for organizational resilience, which includes emergency preparedness and response.
- ISO 22320:2018 - Societal security - Emergency management - Guidelines for colour-coded alerts: This standard provides guidance on the use of colour-coded alerts in emergency management, including standardized colours and their meanings.
- ISO 22324:2015 Societal security – Emergency management – Guidelines for colour-coded alerts: This standard provides guidelines for the use of color-coded alerts in emergency management, including standardized colors and their meanings.
- ISO 22395:2018 - Societal security - Guidelines for color-coded alerts: This standard provides guidelines for the use of color-coded alerts in emergency management, including the meanings of standardized colors.
- ISO 22397:2014 - Societal security - Guidelines for preparedness and operational continuity management: This standard provides guidelines for developing and implementing preparedness and continuity management plans, including the use of standardized terminology.
- ISO 22398:2018 - Societal security - Guidelines for exercises: This standard provides guidelines for developing, conducting, and evaluating exercises in emergency management, including the use of standardized terminology.

- ISO 22399:2017 - Societal security - Guideline for incident preparedness and operational continuity management: This standard provides guidelines for developing and implementing incident preparedness and continuity management plans, including the use of standardized terminology.
- ISO/TS 22319:2017 - Societal security - Guidelines for planning the involvement of spontaneous volunteers: This technical specification provides guidance on planning and involving spontaneous volunteers in emergency management, including the use of standardized terminology.
- ISO/TS 22330:2018 - Societal security - Emergency management - Guidelines for color-coded alerts and public warning: This technical specification provides guidance on the use of color-coded alerts and public warning in emergency management, including the use of standardized terminology.

CEN

At the European Union level, the European Committee for Standardization (CEN) has developed a list of CEN standards related to the standardization of terms in emergency response planning, preparedness, and execution:

- CEN/CLC/TS 17177:2018 - Crisis management - Terminology: This technical specification provides terminology related to crisis management, including emergency planning, preparedness, and response.
- CEN/TR 15361:2017 - Crisis management - Guidelines for developing standards for messages and terminology: This CEN Technical Report provides guidelines for developing standards for messages and terminology in crisis management, including emergency response.
- CEN/TR 17214:2018 - Crisis management - Community resilience - Guidelines for supporting vulnerable persons in an emergency: This CEN Technical Report provides guidelines for supporting vulnerable persons in emergency situations, including standardized terminology for emergency response.
- CEN/TR 17382:2019 - Crisis management - Guidelines for incorporating child-centred approaches into humanitarian and emergency response: This CEN Technical Report provides guidelines for incorporating child-centred approaches into emergency response, including standardized terminology.
- CEN/TR 17382-2:2020 - Crisis management - Guidelines for incorporating child-centred approaches into humanitarian and emergency response - Part 2: Guidance for practitioners: This CEN Technical Report provides guidance for practitioners on incorporating child-centred approaches into emergency response, including standardized terminology.
- CEN/TR 17415:2019 - Crisis management - Crowd management - Guidelines for good practice: This CEN Technical Report provides guidelines for good practice in crowd management during emergency response, including standardized terminology.
- CEN/TR 17512:2020 Personal protective equipment – Smart garments – Terms and definitions: This CEN Technical Report provides terms and definitions related to smart garments for personal protective equipment (PPE), including terminology related to emergency response.

- CEN/TS 17091:2018 - Crisis management - Terminology and concepts: This CEN Technical Specification provides terminology and concepts related to crisis management, including emergency response.
- CWA 17335:2018 is a CEN Workshop Agreement that provides terminology related to crisis and disaster management, including emergency planning, preparedness, and response. It includes definitions of terms that are commonly used in this field, as well as standardized symbols and codes. This helps to ensure a consistent understanding of emergency response procedures and protocols among stakeholders and responders.
- EN 16601-30-10:2015 - Space project management - Part 30-10: Project, risk and contingency management - Terminology: This European standard provides terminology related to space project management, including emergency planning and response.
- EN 17173:2020 European CBRNE glossary: This European standard provides a glossary of terms related to chemical, biological, radiological, nuclear, and explosive (CBRNE) incidents, including standardized terminology for emergency response.
- EN 1846-1:2011 Firefighting and rescue service vehicles – Part 1: Nomenclature and designation: This European standard provides standardized nomenclature and designation for firefighting and rescue service vehicles, which is important for effective communication during emergency response.

ITU-T

The International Telecommunication Union (ITU) is the United Nations specialized agency for information and communication technologies – ICTs, founded in 1865 to facilitate international connectivity in communications networks. The ITU Telecommunication Standardization Sector (ITU-T) develop voluntary international standards (ITU-T Recommendations) that meet their need for common platforms facilitating industry growth and innovation. Among them, the following are related to terminology in emergency planning, preparedness, and response:

- ITU-T E.102 (2019): This ITU-T standard provides a glossary of terms related to emergency telecommunications, including standardized terminology for emergency response.
- ITU-T X.1303 (2018) - Common alerting protocol (CAP) using the OASIS CAP v1.2 standard: This ITU-T standard provides guidelines for the Common Alerting Protocol (CAP) using the OASIS CAP v1.2 standard, which is used to exchange emergency alerts and notifications.

ASTM

American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) standards are developed by committees of relevant industry professionals who meet regularly in an open and transparent process to deliver standards, test methods, specifications, guides, and practices. The following are related to the standardisation of terminology in emergency planning, preparedness and response:

- ASTM E2019-03(2019) - Standard Guide for Properties of a Universal Healthcare Identifier (UHID): This ASTM standard provides guidelines for creating a universal healthcare identifier (UHID) to be used in emergency situations.
- ASTM E2771-11 (2019) provides guidelines for the use of terminology in crisis and disaster management, including emergency response. It includes definitions of terms and symbols that are commonly used in this field, which helps to ensure clear and

consistent communication between responders and stakeholders during emergency situations.

NENA / EENA

- NENA, the 9-1-1 Association, is a USA non-profit organization focused on improving 9-1-1. NENA, as an American National Standards Institute (ANSI)-accredited standards developer, produces several classes of documents that are published as an information source for the industry. The NENA Knowledge Base Glossary is a guide for readers of NENA publications and a tool for members of the NENA committees that prepare them. It defines the terms, acronyms and definitions associated with the 9-1-1 industry. Intended users of this document are any person needing NENA's definition/description of a 9-1-1 related term.
- EENA is involved in monitoring and contributing to standardisation work related to emergency services mainly through participating in different standardisation bodies and providing expertise. EENA Operations Document – 112 Terminology aims to give a definition for all terms and acronyms related to 112. It is updated with the terminology used in the EENA Operations and Next Generation 112 documents.

UN

The United Nations (UN) has published several glossaries related to emergencies and disasters, as well as other works related to the standardization of terminology in disasters. These UN publications provide a standardized vocabulary and conceptual framework for understanding disaster risk reduction, as well as guidelines for conducting national disaster risk assessments, developing early warning systems, emergency response and coordination, and humanitarian protection. These publications also provide standardized terminology and definitions for emergency situations, which helps to ensure clear and consistent communication among responders and stakeholders. Here is a list of some of the most relevant publications:

- UNISDR Terminology on Disaster Risk Reduction: This publication provides a standardized vocabulary and conceptual framework for understanding disaster risk reduction, including standardized terminology and definitions.
- UNISDR Words into Action Guidelines - National Disaster Risk Assessment: This publication provides guidelines for conducting national disaster risk assessments, including standardized terminology and definitions.
- UNISDR Words into Action Guidelines - Developing Early Warning Systems: This publication provides guidelines for developing early warning systems, including standardized terminology and definitions.
- UNISDR Sendai Framework Glossary: This publication provides a glossary of terms related to the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction, including standardized terminology and definitions.
- UNISDR Global Assessment Report on Disaster Risk Reduction: This report provides a comprehensive analysis of disaster risk reduction, including standardized terminology and definitions.
- UN Disaster Assessment and Coordination (UNDAC) Handbook: This publication provides guidelines for emergency response and coordination, including standardized terminology and definitions.

- UNHCR Protection Glossary: This publication provides a glossary of terms related to refugee and humanitarian protection, including standardized terminology and definitions for emergency situations.
- UNDAC Terminology: This publication provides standardized terminology for the UN Disaster Assessment and Coordination team, including terminology related to emergency response and coordination.
- UN OCHA Common Humanitarian Dictionary: This publication provides a standardized vocabulary for humanitarian actors, including standardized terminology and definitions for emergency situations.

WHO

World Health Organization (WHO) publications provide a conceptual framework for understanding health emergency and disaster risk management, guidelines for developing mass casualty management systems and emergency medical teams, as well as guidance on developing evidence-based clinical practice guidelines and public health surveillance for chemical incidents. These publications also provide standardized terminology and definitions for emergency planning, preparedness, and response:

- Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology: This Glossary is designed for the policymakers, practitioners and other stakeholders who work in the many fields that contribute to reducing the health risks and consequences of all types of emergencies and disasters. It was developed to remedy the lack of standardized terminology in the field of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management (Health EDRM), which had become apparent during the process of establishing the WHO Health Emergencies Programme and developing the Health EDRM Framework.
- WHO Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Framework: This publication provides a conceptual framework for understanding health emergency and disaster risk management, including standardized terminology and definitions.
- WHO Emergency Response Framework: This publication provides a framework for emergency response in public health emergencies, including standardized terminology and definitions.
- WHO Mass Casualty Management Systems: Strategies and Guidelines for Building Health Sector Capacity: This publication provides guidelines for developing mass casualty management systems, including standardized terminology and definitions.
- WHO Handbook for Guideline Development: This publication provides guidance on developing evidence-based clinical practice guidelines, including standardized terminology and definitions.
- WHO Public Health Surveillance for Action Against Chemical Incidents: This publication provides guidance on public health surveillance for chemical incidents, including standardized terminology and definitions.
- WHO Emergency Medical Teams: Minimum Technical Standards and Recommendations for Rehabilitation: This publication provides guidelines for emergency medical teams, including standardized terminology and definitions.
- WHO Global Health Cluster: A Guide to Cluster Competencies: This publication provides guidelines for global health clusters, including standardized terminology and definitions.

- WHO International Health Regulations: This publication provides guidelines for public health emergency response, including standardized terminology and definitions.

EU RESEARCH AND INNOVATION FUNDING PROGRAMS

The EU research and innovation funding program has supported several projects that aim to improve emergency response planning, preparedness, and implementation by developing standardized approaches to risk assessment and management, testing and evaluating new technologies and procedures, and sharing and exchanging good practices. The results of these projects have contributed to a more coordinated, efficient, and effective response to crises and emergencies in Europe. Some of these projects are:

- DRIVER+ (Driving Innovation in Crisis Management for European Resilience) - DRIVER+ aimed to improve crisis management by providing a standardized framework for testing and evaluating new technologies and procedures in simulated crisis situations. The project developed a Common Terminology and a Trial Guidance Methodology to support the testing and evaluation process.
- IMPROVER (Improved risk evaluation and implementation of resilience concepts to critical infrastructure) - IMPROVER aimed to improve the resilience of critical infrastructure by developing a standardized framework for risk assessment and management. The project developed a set of standards and guidelines for the assessment of risks and vulnerabilities and the implementation of resilience measures.
- RESILENS (Realising European Resilience for Critical Infrastructure) - RESILENS aimed to improve the resilience of critical infrastructure by developing a standardized approach to risk management. The project developed a set of guidelines and tools for risk assessment, analysis, and management, as well as a Common Terminology to facilitate communication and collaboration among stakeholders.
- IDIRA (Interoperability of data and procedures in large-scale multinational disaster response actions): The IDIRA project conceptualized, developed, demonstrated and assessed approaches to facilitate coordination of large-scale disaster situations by improved interoperability.
- STRATEGY (Facilitating EU pre-Standardization process Through stReamlining and vAlidating inTerooperability in systems and procEdures involved in the crisis manaGement cYcle) - SRATEGY aims to build and implement a pan-European pre-standardisation framework and to map, test and validate new and existing standards across eight thematic streams in crisis management: Search and rescue / Critical infrastructure protection / Response planning / Command and control / Early warning and Rapid damage assessment / Chemical, Biological, Radiological, Nuclear and high-yield Explosive threats (CBRN-E) / Training / Terminology/Symbology

9.1.3. Strengths

- Common policies and standards: The EU has established common policies and standards in various areas, such as environmental protection, transport, and civil protection, that can be leveraged to develop and implement standardised terminology related to emergencies and disasters.
- Institutional Framework: The EU's legislative and decision-making processes offer a clear path for the development and implementation of standardised terminology related to emergencies and disasters.

- EU funding and support: The EU can provide funding and support to member states with limited resources and capacity to develop and implement effective standardised terminology related to emergencies and disasters.
- Language Skills: Many EU citizens are multilingual, which can facilitate the development and implementation of standardised terminology related to emergencies and disasters across member states.
- Capacity building: The EU has been investing in capacity building measures to enhance the resilience of member states in the face of disasters, including training on terminology and communication

9.1.4. Weaknesses

- Diverse cultures and languages: The EU is home to diverse cultures and languages, which may pose challenges to developing and implementing standardised terminology related to emergencies and disasters. Language barriers may hinder the effective communication of terminology to affected populations.
- Complexity of decision-making processes: The EU's decision-making processes can be complex and time-consuming, making it difficult to develop and implement standardised terminology related to emergencies and disasters in a timely manner.
- Political fragmentation: The EU is a political union of member states with varying political ideologies, which may pose challenges to achieving consensus on issues related to standardisation of terminology.
- Limited authority over member states: The EU has limited authority over member states' use of terminology related to emergencies and disasters, which can hinder the harmonisation process.

9.1.5. Opportunities

- International Collaboration: The EU can collaborate with international organisations and countries with advanced disaster management systems to learn best practices and incorporate them into its own systems.
- Technological Innovations: Technological innovations, such as natural language processing and artificial intelligence, can help to develop and implement standardised terminology related to emergencies and disasters.
- Best practices and knowledge sharing: Countries around the world can facilitate knowledge sharing and best practices among states to develop and implement effective standardised terminology related to emergencies and disasters.

9.1.6. Threats

- Language Barriers: Language barriers can hinder the effective communication of standardised terminology to affected populations, particularly in multilingual and multicultural environments.
- Lack of agreement: In general, stakeholders do not agree on the specific definitions and usage of key terms. This can be particularly problematic in international contexts, where different countries and cultures may have different understandings of certain terms.
- Complexity of disasters: the dynamic and evolving nature of emergency management. New technologies, changing risks and threats, and evolving organisational structures can all affect the terminology used in planning and implementing emergency response.

- **Cyber Threats and Attacks:** The use of ICT systems for the standardisation of terminology may increase the risk of cyber threats and attacks, which can compromise the integrity and availability of the data.
- **Political Instability and Conflicts:** Political instability and conflicts can hinder the standardisation of terminology related to emergencies and disasters in the EU, particularly in countries facing such challenges.
- **Limited International Support:** The lack of international support and collaboration in standardising terminology related to emergencies and disasters may hinder the EU's efforts to achieve this objective.

9.2. CO.WP5-2: Harmonization of emergency response plans

9.2.1. Summary of the current situation in the EU

An emergency response plan is a document that describes how an agency or organisation will manage its response to emergencies of various types, providing a description of

- The objectives, policy and approach to emergency response.
- The structure, authorities and responsibilities for a systematic, coordinated and effective response.

Disaster management often involves a wide range of organisations and institutions, of different nationalities and with different operating procedures. For this response system to function in an integrated manner, mechanisms must be in place to ensure coordination and interoperability between cross-sectoral, inter-hierarchical and even cross-border teams.

Disaster management at European level has a common approach and structure so that any country needing assistance for an IMC or disaster can integrate teams mobilised through the European Civil Protection Mechanism into its civil protection system.

Different EU countries have standardised emergency plans at national level. However, the reality in our study area shows that most of the existing plans are national and regional in scope and often not well known beyond the territorial borders where they are implemented. There is a high percentage of agencies that could intervene in cross-border crises that are part of regional or national response plans, but the percentage of cases where transnational plans exist is low.

Harmonising legislation would need to be developed at EU level to encourage the establishment of common cross-border response plans and procedures. Interoperability between agencies involved in MCI or cross-border disasters could be improved by harmonising the legislation underpinning plans and procedures at Member State and EU level, and by ensuring a minimum level of standardisation between neighbouring countries involved in MCI response.

Given the inevitable reality in the EU today of multiple contingency plans adapted to different hazards and different characteristics of the territorial scope in which they apply, means are needed to enable rapid consultation and exchange of critical information to ensure a coordinated and effective response when emergencies overlap between countries.

Furthermore, emergency plans are not effective unless they are accompanied by a process of updating. A significant proportion of these plans have been developed once, without any subsequent review or update. In order to prevent them from becoming obsolete, there is a strong need for a legal obligation to review and update contingency plans on a regular basis.

It should also be noted that planning requires an implementation process. Implementation includes the dissemination of the plan to both the affected population and the organisations that make up the action groups, the development of procedures for action, the joint training of all those involved in the response, and the provision of the necessary equipment.

9.2.2. Review of previous harmonization, homogenization and standardization efforts

The European Union has established a framework for civil protection to ensure that countries have the capacity to respond to emergencies, such as natural disasters or major accidents. The EU Civil Protection Mechanism coordinates the resources of participating countries and provides financial support and expertise in emergency situations.

Figure 23 - EUCPM

At the national level, EU Member States have their own legislation and emergency response plans for managing civil protection. These laws define the responsibilities of national, regional, provincial or local authorities in emergency situations and provide guidelines for the preparation, implementation and evaluation of emergency response plans for different types of emergencies and different territories, resulting in a high degree of homogeneity of plans within the same country.

The following are some of the key laws and regulations in force in each of the EU member states and the EEA states, in relation to civil protection emergency response plans:

EUROPEAN UNION

- Austria: Federal Act on Civil Protection (Bundesgesetz über den Zivilschutz) and the Provincial Acts on Civil Protection (Landesgesetze über den Zivilschutz).
- Belgium: Civil Protection Act (Loi sur la Protection Civile).
- Bulgaria: Civil Protection Act (Закон за гражданската защита).
- Croatia: Civil Protection Act (Zakon o zaštiti od katastrofa).
- Cyprus: Civil Defense Law (Νόμος περί Πολιτικής Άμυνας).
- Czech Republic: Crisis Management Act (Zákon o krizovém řízení).

- Denmark: Act on Civil Protection (Lov om civilbeskyttelse).
- Estonia: Rescue Act (Päästeseadus).
- Finland: Rescue Act (Pelastuslaki).
- France: Civil Security Code (Code de la sécurité intérieure).
- Germany: Civil Protection Act (Zivilschutzgesetz).
- Greece: Civil Protection Law (Νόμος περί Πολιτικής Προστασίας).
- Hungary: Disaster Management Act (Katasztrófavédelmi törvény).
- Ireland: Fire Services Act (1998), and the National Emergency Plan for Nuclear Accidents (NEPNA).
- Italy: Civil Protection Code (Codice della Protezione Civile).
- Latvia: Civil Defense Law (Grozījumi Civiltiesību kodeksā).
- Lithuania: Law on Emergency Situations (Grozījumi likumā "Par ārkārtējām situācijām").
- Luxembourg: Law on Civil Protection (Loi sur la Protection Civile).
- Malta: Civil Protection Act
- Netherlands: Law on Safety Regions (Wet veiligheidsregio's).
- Poland: Act on Crisis Management (Ustawa o zarządzaniu kryzysowym).
- Portugal: Civil Protection Law (Lei de Proteção Civil).
- Romania: Law on the Civil Protection System (Legea privind sistemul de protecție civilă).
- Slovakia: Crisis Management Act (Zákon o krízovom riadení).
- Slovenia: Protection against Natural and Other Disasters Act (Zakon o varstvu pred naravnimi in drugimi nesrečami).
- Spain: Civil Protection Law (Ley de Protección Civil).
- Sweden: Emergency Act (Lagen om skydd mot olyckor).

EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AREA (EEA):

- Iceland: Civil Protection Act (Lög um Almannavarnir).
- Liechtenstein: Civil Protection Act (Gesetz über den Bevölkerungsschutz).
- Norway: Emergency Preparedness Act (Lov om kommunal beredskapsplikt).

UNITED KINGDOM:

- United Kingdom: In the UK, civil protection and emergency response plans are regulated by various laws and regulations, including the Civil Contingencies Act (2004), the Environmental Protection Act (1990), and the Health and Safety at Work etc. Act (1974).

Despite the significant development of legislation governing the development of emergency response plans in each country, they are generally focused on specific risks and defined administrative territories. The development of inter-territorial, let alone international, emergency response plans is still rare.

Although the plans of the different Member States generally have certain aspects in common, there is no standardisation of the structure of emergency response plans at EU level. Studies such as H2020 STRATEGY are developing interesting proposals to move in this direction.

In terms of accessibility, emergency response plans may be available in different formats and through different channels, depending on the policies and practices of the authorities responsible for their development and implementation. Some emergency response plans may be available on the internet, through official government websites or other online platforms.

Other plans may be distributed in printed form or made available upon request to specific stakeholders or members of the public.

In any case, there is currently no official centralised repository of emergency response plans in the EU, nor are there official channels that would allow for the systematic exchange of information on emergency response plans between Member States.

9.2.3. Strengths

- Existence of EUCPM – mechanism established by European Commission with the aim to strengthen cooperation between EU countries with regards to civil protection in the area of prevention, preparedness and response to disasters
- Existence of Civil Protection or Crisis Management Act/Law at national level in EU member states – this gives a basis for elaboration of regional/local/autonomous emergency response plans
- EU funds and support from EU institutions – EU (EC) offers funding and support within its financial mechanisms to countries with limited financial resources to develop and implement various kind of activities

9.2.4. Weaknesses

- Lack of participation of national authorities and stakeholders to create, update and implement particular emergency response plans at national level, respectively at regional/local level
- FRs low adaptation to novelties: there is still a low will of FRs to adopt new documents, in most cases they prefer to follow what was used many years before and is working in quite good and comfortable way for them
- Differences between regions/countries - each member state has its specific language, culture and way of performing law. Emergency response plans which have already been developed are not sufficient to be used for harmonisation process
- Knowledge of emergency response plans within country is not well known beyond the territorial borders where they are implemented

9.2.5. Opportunities

- VALKYRIES' Proposal of unified Register of emergency response plans – the place/repository of emergency response plans in the EU
- Good practices from other H2020 and Horizon Europe projects – for example in H2020 STRATEGY project the purpose of the project is to pre-standardize the structure and content of emergency response plans within EU

9.2.6. Threats

- Low interest of national/regional/local authorities with creation of emergency response plans in comparison what has already been used so far
- Budgetary issues – States' limited financial resources mean that priority should be given to urgent emergency response actions before developing emergency response plans at different territorial levels.
- Political issues – exchange of governments leads to exchange of people in charge and could cause an issue that the new head of a single ministry/department responsible for decision making will not show the willingness to follow the process of creation and harmonisation of emergency response plans within EU member state

9.3. CO.WP5-7: Harmonization of operating procedures in emergency response

9.3.1. Summary of the current situation in the EU

Emergency response plans detail the resources, capacities and capabilities that the agency or organization will employ in its response. A standard operating procedure (SOP) is a document describing how to perform this response, a reference document or an operations manual that provides the purpose, authorities, duration, and details for the preferred method of performing a single function or several interrelated functions in a uniform manner.

The emergency response plans are usually jurisdiction- or/and risk-specific. The degree of homogeneity is generally high in the different EU territories in relation to the main operational responsibilities assigned to the different Emergency Services In MCIs and disasters: Firefighters: risk control and zoning; Police: security; EMS: victim care. But the reality is that the operating procedures are very heterogeneous, specific to each agency and very rarely harmonised with those of the other agencies with which they potentially coincide in the response to an MCI or disaster.

Emergency medical services (EMS) in EU cover a wide range of health services: some are first-responder-only services and some are medicalised, some are stand-alone services and some are integrated with primary care or hospitals, some are voluntary and some are professional, they may be public or private, and so on.

The report Emergency Medical Services Systems in the European Union (WHO Regional Office for Europe, 2008)³ showed that EU countries have a similar crisis management system, but the structure and composition of their EMSs vary, with more or less significant differences in command or operational coordination roles.

In order to ensure the operability of emergency plans, especially when they are activated to respond to cross-sectoral and/or cross-border disasters, it is essential to have uniform or at least homogenised operational procedures for action, as well as tools that enable interoperability between services and regions, facilitating the exchange of information for decision-making and coordination.

In the case of disasters, reconnaissance processes include various activities: observation, collection, processing and exchange of information, assessment of the situation including forecasting, planning, decision making and communication of decisions taken, implementation of decisions, information gathering and control measures.

EMS services are responsible for carrying out the various actions: C2, deployment, logistics, rescue, triage, stabilisation and evacuation.

After rescue, the care of victims of MCI incidents begins with initial triage, the purpose of which is to determine the priority with which each victim should receive medical treatment at the scene, depending on the severity of their injuries and their chances of survival. However, as well as differences in who should triage, there are also differences in how triage should be carried out. Triage methods/procedures vary and are not the same in all countries. There is room for improvement and harmonisation.

³ Davoli E et al. Emergency Medical Services Systems in the European Union: Report. WHO Regional Office for Europe. 2008. https://www.euro.who.int/__data/assets/pdf_file/0016/114406/E92038.pdf

After each triage procedure, the victim needs to be tagged so that all responders know that they have been triaged and what priority they have received. This labelling of victims is actually done in very different ways: using coloured ribbons, painting on the victim's skin, using triage tags, entering the information on portable devices, etc. Even the alphanumeric or colour codes used to indicate the triage priority of victims are not fully standardised across the different emergency services, nor at national level. This makes the interoperability of different services in cross-border disasters very difficult.

In addition to the initial triage, each victim must receive the necessary treatment at the scene in order to be ready for evacuation. Later, further triage is carried out to determine the priority of each victim to be evacuated from the scene.

Patients must be transported in the appropriate mobile resource, depending on whether or not they require medical assistance during their evacuation to hospital. Evacuations should be carried out according to agreed criteria or recommendations to homogenise the type of EMS vehicle and the destination of the victims in order to achieve the greatest benefit for the majority.

The management of an MCI includes the appropriate distribution of casualties among hospital centres to avoid overcrowding. In such situations, hospitals must be prepared to receive and treat large numbers of patients. In many cases, the involvement of hospitals in the response to external MCIs is passive, limited to increasing their capabilities at the request of the command centre in charge of the incident. It would therefore be desirable for legislation to encourage the integration of joint EMS-hospital response plans with MCI response plans. If both work together as two active roles, the effectiveness of the response will be maximised.

It is up to the professional and scientific societies responsible for emergency medicine in the EU to develop consensus and recommendations on triage, on-site care and evacuation of victims in an MCI or disaster situation, thus promoting quality standards in line with current scientific knowledge.

It is also necessary to try to harmonise and standardise other aspects to ensure interoperability between emergency services: training, traceability of victims, safety of first responders, exchange of information, EMS C2 procedures, debriefing, etc.

9.3.2. Review of previous harmonization, homogenization and standardization efforts

STANDARD OPERATING PROCEDURES

Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) for emergency response planning and preparedness are written guidelines that provide step-by-step instructions on how to respond to specific emergency situations. They help to ensure that emergency responders act in a consistent and coordinated manner, and that the response is timely, effective, and based on best practices.

The standardization of SOPs in emergency response is essential to promote interoperability, coordination, and collaboration among emergency responders, organizations, and countries involved in emergency response planning, preparedness, and implementation. Standardized SOPs ensure that emergency responders have a common understanding of key concepts and terminology, and that they follow a standardized approach to emergency response.

There are several organizations and initiatives working on the standardization of SOPs in emergency response. Here are some of the key examples:

- ISO (International Organization for Standardization) - ISO has developed several standards related to emergency management, including ISO 22320:2018, which provides guidelines for developing SOPs for emergency response, and ISO 22319:2017, which provides guidelines for the planning and involvement of spontaneous volunteers during emergency situations, including the development of SOPs for volunteer management.
- CEN (European Committee for Standardization) - CEN has developed several standards related to crisis management, including CEN/TS 17091:2018, which provides terminology and concepts for crisis management.
- UN OCHA (United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs) - UN OCHA has developed several guidelines and tools related to emergency response, including the Humanitarian Programme Cycle (HPC) and the Minimum Standards for Humanitarian Response, which provide guidance on the development and implementation of SOPs.
- FEMA (Federal Emergency Management Agency) - FEMA has developed several guidelines and tools related to emergency management, including the National Incident Management System (NIMS) and the Incident Command System (ICS), which provide standardized approaches to emergency response.
- WHO (World Health Organization) - WHO has developed several guidelines and tools related to public health emergency response, including the Incident Management System (IMS), which provides a standardized approach to emergency response for public health emergencies.

DEPLOYMENT and C2

Managing multiple disasters and catastrophes requires a coordinated and integrated approach, involving a range of government agencies, emergency management organizations, and other stakeholders. Countries and regions have developed various models and frameworks for coordination and response, which emphasize the importance of risk assessment, planning, and community engagement:

- European Union: In the EU, disaster management and response is coordinated through the European Civil Protection Mechanism (ECPM), which facilitates cooperation among member states in disaster response. The ECPM has established a set of guidelines for multi-risk and multi-hazard risk assessment, which aims to identify and prioritize potential risks and vulnerabilities, and to develop coordinated response plans. The ECPM also provides support for the deployment of resources across borders, such as specialized rescue teams and equipment, to assist in disaster response.
- United States: In the United States, the Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA) is the lead agency responsible for disaster management and response. FEMA has developed the National Response Framework (NRF), which provides a guide for how the nation responds to all types of disasters and emergencies. The NRF establishes a comprehensive approach to incident management, including a system for coordinating emergency response activities among federal, state, and local agencies. In addition, FEMA has established the National Incident Management System (NIMS), which provides a standardized framework for emergency response teams to work together across jurisdictions and disciplines.

- United Kingdom: In the United Kingdom, disaster management and response is coordinated through the Civil Contingencies Secretariat (CCS), which is part of the Cabinet Office. The CCS has developed the National Risk Assessment, which assesses the likelihood and potential impact of various risks and hazards. The assessment is used to develop coordinated response plans and to prioritize resources. The CCS also has established the National Resilience Capabilities Programme, which provides a framework for developing and maintaining the capabilities necessary to respond to multiple emergencies.
- Australia: In Australia, disaster management and response is coordinated through the National Disaster Risk Reduction Framework, which provides a comprehensive approach to disaster risk reduction and emergency management. The framework establishes a set of guidelines for multi-agency and multi-jurisdictional coordination and response, as well as for risk assessment, planning, and recovery. The framework also emphasizes the importance of community engagement and participation in disaster management.
- Japan: In Japan, disaster management and response is coordinated through the Disaster Management Council, which is chaired by the Prime Minister. The council establishes policies and guidelines for disaster management and response, and coordinates the activities of various government agencies and organizations. In addition, Japan has developed the Basic Plan for Disaster Management, which provides a framework for multi-hazard disaster risk reduction, as well as for response and recovery.

LOGISTICS

Standardizing disaster response logistics is critical to ensuring that resources are deployed effectively and efficiently in emergencies. Disaster response logistics includes everything from the transport and storage of goods to the coordination of supply chains and the management of information systems. Here is an overview of the standardization of disaster response logistics previous efforts:

- European Union: In the European Union, the European Civil Protection Mechanism (ECPM) has established a set of guidelines and standards for disaster response logistics. These guidelines cover everything from the procurement and transport of goods to the management of supply chains and the use of information systems. The EU also has a reserve of emergency response equipment called RESCEU, which is managed by the European Commission's Humanitarian Aid and Civil Protection Department (DG ECHO). The DG ECHO has developed a Logistic Policy Manual, which provides guidance on the logistics and supply management of the EU's humanitarian aid operations.
- United Nations: The United Nations (UN) has established a logistics cluster to coordinate logistics operations in emergencies. The logistics cluster brings together various UN agencies, NGOs, and other partners to provide coordinated logistics support to disaster-affected populations. The UN Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE) has also developed a set of guidelines for the procurement and transport of relief items, including food, shelter, and medical supplies. These guidelines are based on the UN Standardized Unit of Medical Supply and Equipment (SUMA) system, which provides a standardized approach to the management of medical supplies in emergencies.
- World Health Organization (WHO): The WHO has established a set of guidelines for the management of medical supplies and equipment in emergencies. The guidelines cover

everything from the procurement and transport of medical supplies to the management of inventory and the distribution of supplies to health facilities.

- Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies: The International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies (IFRC) has developed a set of logistics standards for disaster response. The standards cover everything from the procurement and transport of goods to the management of supply chains and the use of information systems. The IFRC Emergency Items Catalogue provides a comprehensive list of relief items that are commonly used in disaster response, such as shelter materials, water and sanitation equipment, and medical supplies.

RECONNAISSANCE

in the event of a disaster, effective reconnaissance enables emergency responders to quickly assess the situation and make informed decisions about the appropriate response. The following are some examples of efforts related to operational procedures for reconnaissance in the event of a disaster:

- FEMA (Federal Emergency Management Agency) - FEMA has developed several guidelines and tools related to disaster reconnaissance, including the Damage Assessment Operations Manual (DAOM), which provides standardized procedures and forms for conducting damage assessments after a disaster.
- USACE (US Army Corps of Engineers) - The USACE has developed several guidelines and tools related to disaster reconnaissance, including the Disaster Field Office Technical Guide (DFO TG), which provides standardized procedures for conducting damage assessments and reconnaissance after a disaster.
- OCHA (United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs) - OCHA has developed several guidelines and tools related to disaster response, including the Disaster Assessment and Coordination (UNDAC) Handbook, which provides guidance on the use of standardized assessment tools and procedures for disaster response.
- NOAA (National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration) - NOAA has developed several guidelines and tools related to disaster reconnaissance, including the Coastal Storms Program Field Operations Manual, which provides standardized procedures for conducting reconnaissance after coastal storms.
- ICAO (International Civil Aviation Organization) - The ICAO has developed guidelines for conducting aerial reconnaissance after a disaster, including guidelines for the use of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) for reconnaissance.

SEARCH & RESCUE

A number of organisations have established recommendations, standards and guidelines in relation to disaster rescue. The application of these may vary depending on the specific context of a disaster and the resources available to responders.

- European Union: The EU has established the European Civil Protection Mechanism (EUCPM) to facilitate cooperation among member states in disaster response. The ECPM sets guidelines for the training of emergency responders, including the use of standardized procedures, equipment, and communication systems. The EU also has a certification system for search and rescue teams that meets certain standards and is recognized by member states.

- World Health Organization (WHO): The WHO has developed a set of emergency medical teams (EMT) standards that outline the minimum requirements for personnel, equipment, and procedures in emergency response. The EMT standards cover areas such as triage, medical care, and infection prevention and control.
- United Nations (UN): The UN has established the International Search and Rescue Advisory Group (INSARAG) to provide guidance and coordination for search and rescue teams operating in disasters. INSARAG sets minimum standards for the training, equipment, and organization of urban search and rescue (USAR) teams.
- International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies (IFRC): The IFRC has developed guidelines for disaster response that cover all phases of a disaster, from preparedness to recovery. The guidelines include standards for the training and management of emergency response teams, as well as for the provision of first aid and psychosocial support.
- Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA): FEMA is the lead agency in the United States for emergency management and disaster response. FEMA's National Preparedness Directorate oversees the development of standards and guidelines for emergency response team program: FEMA's Urban Search and Rescue (USAR) program provides specialized teams for responding to structural collapses, as well as other search and rescue operations in disasters. FEMA has established a set of standards and guidelines for USAR teams, including requirements for training, equipment, and response procedures.
- Asia-Pacific Economic Cooperation (APEC): APEC is a regional economic forum that includes 21 member economies in the Asia-Pacific region. APEC's Emergency Preparedness Working Group (EPWG) focuses on enhancing regional cooperation in emergency preparedness and response exercises: APEC conducts regular Humanitarian Assistance and Disaster Relief (HADR) exercises to enhance regional cooperation and readiness for disasters. These exercises involve the participation of military, civilian, and private sector entities and aim to improve the coordination and effectiveness of emergency response efforts.

TRIAGE

In the response to a mass casualty incident or disaster, triage plays a critical role in optimising the allocation of scarce medical resources to the most critical patients. Without effective triage, it can be difficult to identify and prioritise patients requiring urgent medical attention, leading to suboptimal use of limited medical resources and, potentially, increased morbidity and mortality.

For this reason, a large number of mass casualty triage protocols have been proposed over the years, reflecting the diversity of environments and scenarios that may be encountered in this type of incident. This diversity of triage protocols can pose challenges when attempting to integrate the responses of different agencies or regions following a large-scale event. To address this challenge, there is a need to move towards homogenisation or standardisation of triage at mass casualty or disaster incidents:

- Guidelines for Field Triage of Injured Patients: Recommendations of the National Expert Panel on Field Triage, 2011. This guideline, endorsed by the American College of Surgeons and the National Association of EMS Physicians, provides recommendations

for field triage of injured patients to optimize transportation to the most appropriate medical facility.

- NATO Joint Medical Support Doctrine, 2nd edition, 2016. This publication, endorsed by NATO, outlines the principles and procedures for medical support in military operations, including casualty evacuation.
- NATO STANDARD AMedP-1.10 MEDICAL ASPECTS IN THE MANAGEMENT OF A MAJOR INCIDENT/MASS CASUALTY SITUATION Edition A Version 1 DECEMBER 2015. This publication specifically addresses the management of mass casualty incidents. With regard to triage, it indicates that colour coding should be used to facilitate the identification of victims by rescue personnel and that victims should be labelled with all necessary information (individual identification number, personal data, findings, diagnoses, triage result, necessary medical treatment and mode of transport). It defines four triage categories (T1, T2, T3 and T4) according to whether casualties require immediate, delayed, minimal or expectant treatment, and states that in a major multinational mass casualty incident a colour code (T1 red, T2 yellow, T3 green and T4 white) should be used.
- NATO STANDARD AJP-4.10 JOINT ALLIED DOCTRINE FOR MEDICAL SUPPORT Issue C Version 1 SEPTEMBER 2019. This NATO standard expands on the triage categories described in AMedP 1.10. It establishes five triage categories: T1, immediate or red; T2, urgent or yellow; T3, minimal, green; dead, white or black; and T4, expectant, blue or white. It describes for each of the categories and colours what actions are implicated and their characteristics, noting that the T4 category should only be used in mass casualty incidents and when authorised by the command or medical director.
- A translational triage research development tool: standardisation of prehospital triage decision-making systems in mass casualty incidents. Khorram-Manesh et al. *Scand J Trauma Resusc Emerg Med* (2021) 29:119. This publication reports a study whose purpose was to evaluate the most commonly used pre-existing prehospital triage systems in an attempt to create a translational triage tool. Seventeen triage systems were described, of which seven met the pre-designated criteria and were the basis for further analysis. From this analysis, a universal system of majority criteria was created. A system that is not new in itself, but a translation of several systems.

STABILISATION OF THE VICTIMS

The treatment of mass casualties requires a structured approach that can be followed systematically to ensure prompt recognition, timely intervention, and optimal outcomes. The protocols listed above are endorsed by various scientific institutions and are based on current evidence-based medicine, reflecting a commitment to providing the highest quality care to patients in emergency situations.

- Advanced Trauma Life Support (ATLS): ATLS is a protocol developed by the American College of Surgeons (ACS) to assess and manage trauma patients. ATLS is designed to provide a standardized approach to the initial assessment and management of trauma patients, including airway, breathing, circulation, and neurological status.
- Advanced Burn Life Support (ABLS): ABLS is a protocol developed by the American Burn Association (ABA) to assess and manage burn patients. ABLS is designed to provide a standardized approach to the initial assessment and management of burn patients, including fluid resuscitation, wound care, and pain management.

- International Liaison Committee on Resuscitation (ILCOR): ILCOR is a collaboration of international scientific organizations that develops and disseminates evidence-based resuscitation guidelines, including those for cardiac arrest, drowning, and trauma.
- Wilderness Medical Society (WMS): WMS is an organization that promotes research, education, and standards for the practice of wilderness medicine. The WMS has developed guidelines for the management of wilderness emergencies, including trauma, environmental emergencies, and altitude illness.
- American Academy of Pediatrics (AAP): AAP has developed guidelines for the assessment and management of paediatric poisoning emergencies. The guidelines include recommendations for initial assessment and stabilization, as well as specific antidote therapies for common poisons.
- European Resuscitation Council (ERC): ERC provides guidelines for the management of cardiac arrest, drowning, and trauma, including initial assessment, airway management, and resuscitation.
- American Heart Association (AHA): AHA provides guidelines for the management of cardiac arrest and other cardiovascular emergencies, including ACLS, BLS, and PALS.

EVACUATION

Evacuation in MCI or disasters includes both victims being moved to a health facility for further medical care and the process of moving an affected or threatened population from a dangerous location to a safer one. It is a crucial part of disaster management and emergency response planning. Various organisations have developed evacuation guidelines that provide a framework for safe and effective evacuations.

- American College of Surgeons Committee on Trauma, Disaster Management and Emergency Preparedness, 2013. This guideline, endorsed by the American College of Surgeons, provides recommendations for hospital preparedness and response to mass casualty incidents, including triage, treatment, and transportation.
- National Association of EMS Physicians, Mass Casualty Triage, 2011. This guideline, endorsed by the National Association of EMS Physicians, provides recommendations for triage of mass casualty incidents by pre-hospital personnel, including transportation decisions.
- Joint Commission on Accreditation of Healthcare Organizations, Emergency Management Standards. This publication, endorsed by the Joint Commission, outlines standards for emergency management in healthcare facilities, including planning for mass casualty incidents and transportation of patients.
- EU Guidelines for the Implementation of the Civil Protection Mechanism: The European Commission (EC) has developed these guidelines to provide a framework for cooperation and coordination among EU Member States in the event of a disaster, including the evacuation of populations. The guidelines have been scientifically supported by research on disaster management and emergency response planning.
- European Commission's Guidelines for the Development of Emergency Evacuation and Sheltering Plans: These guidelines provide a framework for developing emergency evacuation and sheltering plans for different types of emergencies, including natural disasters, technological accidents, and terrorist attacks. The guidelines have been developed in consultation with Member States and emergency response organizations, and they have been scientifically supported by research on emergency management.

- European Reference Framework for Civil Protection: Developed by the EC to provide a common language and approach for civil protection authorities across the EU, including the management of evacuation and sheltering in the event of a disaster. The framework has been developed in consultation with civil protection authorities and other stakeholders, and it has been scientifically supported by research on disaster risk management and emergency response planning.
- European Civil Protection Handbook: The EC and the European Emergency Management Association (EENA) have developed this handbook to provide practical guidance for emergency response planning, including the evacuation of populations. The handbook has been developed in consultation with emergency response organizations and other stakeholders, and it has been scientifically supported by research on emergency management.
- FEMA Evacuation Guidelines: Issued by the Federal Emergency Management Agency in the United States, the FEMA guidelines provide a comprehensive approach to evacuation planning in the event of a disaster.
- NFPA Evacuation Guidelines: Issued by the National Fire Protection Association in the United States, the NFPA guidelines provide a step-by-step approach to developing an evacuation plan for various types of emergencies.
- OSHA Evacuation Guidelines: Issued by the Occupational Safety and Health Administration in the United States, the OSHA guidelines provide a framework for developing an emergency action plan for the workplace, including evacuation procedures.

HOSPITAL RESPONSE

Several publications and guidelines provide guidance for hospitals to develop protocols for responding to external multi-casualty emergencies and disasters, and to collaborate with other involved parties, including pre-hospital staff and public health agencies. The aim is to make the joint response more effective and to reduce the impact of such emergencies:

- Hospital Emergency Response to Mass Casualty Incidents: Guidelines for Development of Protocols for Emergency Medical Response, 2011. This guideline, published by the World Health Organization, provides a framework for hospitals to develop emergency response protocols for mass casualty incidents, including procedures for triage, treatment, and transportation.
- Hospital Preparedness for Mass Casualties: The Israeli Experience, 2011. This publication, authored by the Israeli Ministry of Health, provides an overview of the Israeli approach to hospital preparedness for mass casualty incidents, including planning, training, and response procedures.
- Emergency Preparedness: Joint Commission Standards, 2017. This publication, endorsed by the Joint Commission, outlines the emergency preparedness standards for hospitals, including planning for mass casualty incidents and disasters.
- European Union Guidelines for Hospital Emergency Preparedness, 2014. This guideline, published by the European Union, provides recommendations for hospital preparedness for emergencies and disasters, including mass casualty incidents, with a focus on planning, training, and collaboration with external stakeholders.
- American College of Surgeons Committee on Trauma, Disaster Management and Emergency Preparedness, 2013. This guideline, endorsed by the American College of

Surgeons, provides recommendations for hospital preparedness and response to mass casualty incidents, including triage, treatment, and transportation.

- Hospital Preparedness for Mass Casualty Incidents: An Integrative Review of the Literature, 2017. This publication, authored by a group of researchers, provides a comprehensive review of the literature on hospital preparedness for mass casualty incidents, including best practices and lessons learned.
- European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control, Hospital Preparedness Checklist for Ebola Virus Disease, 2014. This checklist, published by the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control, provides guidance for hospitals to prepare for and respond to Ebola virus disease outbreaks, including procedures for triage, isolation, and infection prevention and control.
- American Hospital Association, Emergency Readiness, 2014. This publication, endorsed by the American Hospital Association, provides guidance for hospitals to prepare for and respond to emergencies and disasters, including mass casualty incidents, with a focus on planning, training, and collaboration with external stakeholders.
- European Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid Operations, Hospital Emergency Response in the Context of Chemical, Biological, Radiological and Nuclear (CBRN) Incidents, 2016. This publication, published by the European Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid Operations, provides guidance for hospitals to prepare for and respond to CBRN incidents, including procedures for triage, decontamination, and medical treatment.

9.3.3. Strengths

- Common policies and standards: The EU has established common policies and standards in various fields, such as public health, civil protection and disaster management, which can facilitate the development and implementation of harmonised operational procedures for emergency medical services at national and regional level. These common policies and standards can help to standardise procedures related to emergency medical services in different areas, despite differences in administrative and operational dependencies and organisation of services.
- 112 centres and EMS services well organized and with expertise in responding to emergency and in developing operational procedures.
- Prior preparedness: The EU has 112 emergency care or coordination centres and well-organised emergency medical services with experience in emergency response and the development of operational procedures.
- European Civil Protection Mechanism (EUCPM): The mechanism itself facilitates interaction between different services and promotes the creation of common standards to enable interoperability in disasters.
- Common training: Common training programmes for first responders already exist at EU level.
- Certifications: The EU already has several certification programmes in place, so agencies or services with certified modules already work with common operating procedures.
- Institutional framework: EU legislative and decision-making processes could also provide avenues for the development and implementation of harmonised operational procedures for emergency medical services, including standardisation of triage and casualty evacuation procedures and coordination of out-of-hospital and in-hospital care.

- Technological innovation: The EU has invested heavily in research and development of medical technologies, such as telemedicine, remote monitoring and mobile health applications, which can be used to update operational procedures and provide tools for harmonisation between different emergency services. These technologies can also facilitate continuity of care between out-of-hospital and in-hospital settings.
- Capacity building: The EU has been investing in capacity building measures to enhance the resilience of member states in the face of disasters, including training on emergency medical services. These capacity building measures can help to improve the professional preparation and competencies of first responders in different member states.
- EU funding and support: The EU can provide funding and support to member states with limited resources and capacity to develop and implement effective operating procedures for emergency medical services, including the standardisation of triage or casualty evacuation procedures, and the coordination of out-of-hospital and in-hospital care.

9.3.4. Weaknesses

- Different cultures and languages: Different cultures and languages coexist in the EU, even within the same Member State, which can make it difficult to develop and implement harmonised operational procedures for emergency medical services, including aspects such as the exchange of clinical information or the tracing of victims. Language barriers can also hinder effective communication with victims and coordination of care between different settings and professionals.
- Complexity of decision-making processes: EU decision-making processes can be complex and time-consuming, which hampers rapid evolution in the adoption of certain measures, even more so when the development of operational procedures for emergency services is usually done at territorial or even agency level. This complexity can hamper the development and implementation of harmonised operational procedures for emergency medical services.
- Limited authority over member states: The EU has limited authority over member states' emergency medical services, which can hinder the harmonisation process. The different structure of emergency services and the different professional preparation and competencies of first responders in different member states can also pose challenges to harmonisation.
- Uneven distribution of resources: Member states in the EU have varying levels of resources and capacities, which may pose challenges to harmonising the operating procedures of emergency medical services, especially in the case of mass casualty incidents and disasters.
- Resistance to change from FR: Resistance to change. There is the case where FRs show unwillingness to adapt to new circumstances or new procedures, especially if they cannot "see" a reasoning behind the change and if they are used to work in a certain way.
- Lack of common guidelines for interoperability of Systems

9.3.5. Opportunities

- International collaboration: They are international organisations and countries with advanced emergency medical services to learn best practices and incorporate them into its own systems, including standardisation in triage or casualty evacuation procedures, and the coordination of out-of-hospital and in-hospital care.

- Technological innovations: The EU can leverage technological innovations, such as telemedicine, remote monitoring, and mobile health applications, to develop and implement advanced operating procedures for emergency medical services, including the standardisation of triage or casualty evacuation procedures, and the coordination of out-of-hospital and in-hospital care.
- Best practices and knowledge sharing: The EU can facilitate knowledge sharing and best practices among member states to develop and implement effective operating procedures for emergency medical services, including the standardisation of triage or casualty evacuation procedures, and the coordination of out-of-hospital and in-hospital care.
- Institutional framework: Organisations such as the WHO and the UN have carried out important work in the development of procedures that can be applied in a standardised manner in emergency and disaster situations. Their experience and efforts are an important basis on the road to harmonisation and standardisation.
- International certifications: Knowledge of disasters allows for further development of specific modules for emergency response, broadening the range of certifications.
- Social awareness regarding disasters preparedness / actions

9.3.6. Threats

- Increased complexity of disasters: the different characteristics in each part of the world, the wide variety of risks that are constantly evolving, the dynamic and evolving nature of emergency management, the evolution of organisational structures, etc., make it more difficult to standardise general procedures and explain the large number of different specific procedures.
- Cyber threats and attacks: The increasing reliance of emergency medical services on ICT systems makes them vulnerable to cyber threats and attacks, which can expose highly confidential information, disrupt or disable the flow of clinical information, and even affect systems for coordinating care between different settings and professionals.
- Political instability and conflicts: Political instability and conflicts may hinder the sharing of harmonised operating procedures for emergency medical services in the EU with other countries, especially in countries facing such problems. This can hinder cross-border coordination of disaster response.
- Foreign policy complexity regarding response to catastrophic events. Not common foreign policy.
- Budgetary constraints and economic downturns: Budgetary constraints and economic downturns may make it difficult to devote efforts to the development and implementation of harmonised operational procedures in favour of other applications with a higher frequency of use or a higher return on investment, especially in Member States with limited resources.
- Disruption of the system in the event of a disaster: the greater the scale of the disaster, the more the civil protection system is affected: warning and coordination systems, communications, emergency services, transport, etc. This may mean that in some cases, particularly the most serious ones, the measures provided for in the normal procedures cannot be applied in practice.
- Information control / management very difficult in disasters
- Different cultures and languages: Different cultures and languages coexist in the EU, even within the same Member State, which can make it difficult to develop and

implement harmonised operational procedures for emergency medical services, including aspects such as the exchange of clinical information or the tracing of victims. Language barriers can also hinder effective communication with victims and coordination of care between different settings and professionals.

- Resistance to change from FR: FR resistance of accept / use new technological tools, to change procedures that “are functioning”, etc.

9.4. CO.WP5-12: Standardisation of information sharing in emergency response

9.4.1. Summary of the current situation in the EU

Standardisation of information exchange is essential to ensure interoperability between emergency response systems, improve coordination, and reduce redundancies. Standardised systems allow for seamless communication and data sharing across different agencies, regions, and countries, leading to better preparedness, response, and recovery efforts.

A lot of effort has been done in establishing referential of data, taxonomies, protocols in terms of medical data, FR information, etc., but there is still a long harmonization effort to be performed.

Data models, naming conventions and taxonomies used by different emergency entities turned-out to be a more complex and difficult matter to harmonize, in particular because historically each country developed and established its own model and designed their response procedures in close relation with the adopted data models.

Therefore, the harmonisation of the data models requires also that procedures and organization to be adapted, which is a more complex transformation. In addition, as the knowledge and technology evolve, the models and taxonomies and enriched to accommodate such developments.

9.4.2. Review of previous harmonization, homogenization and standardization efforts

Facing these challenges, several initiatives took place in order to develop common and harmonized data models that could, in time, be adopted by a wider range of emergency response forces worldwide. Some of the international efforts towards a higher harmonisation of the terms and references used are:

INTERNATIONAL TELECOMMUNICATION UNION (ITU)

ITU is a specialized agency of the United Nations responsible for coordinating the global use of telecommunication networks and services. ITU plays a crucial role in developing international standards and protocols for information and communication technologies (ICTs) used in emergency management. It focuses on ensuring the availability, reliability, and interoperability of ICTs during emergencies, facilitating timely and effective information exchange among stakeholders.

One of related ITU publications is the ITU-T X.1303 - Common Alerting Protocol (CAP), a recommendation that defines the Common Alerting Protocol (CAP), an XML-based data format for exchanging emergency alerts and public warnings among various organizations and systems. CAP enables consistent and interoperable dissemination of warning messages, facilitating timely and effective emergency response.

INTERNATIONAL ORGANIZATION FOR STANDARDIZATION (ISO)

ISO is an independent, non-governmental international organization that develops and publishes international standards across various industries, including emergency management. ISO standards address various aspects of emergency management, such as risk assessment, crisis management, and business continuity. These standards help to ensure the quality, safety, and efficiency of emergency response systems and promote global interoperability and data exchange. The International Organization for Standardization (ISO) has published several standards related to information exchange and protocols in emergencies and disasters:

- ISO 22324:2015 - Emergency management - Emergency management information systems and processes - Public emergency services communication: ISO 22324 provides guidelines for the use of public emergency services communication systems, focusing on aspects such as interoperability, security, and reliability. The standard offers best practices for the design, implementation, and maintenance of communication systems, ensuring effective information exchange among emergency responders and stakeholders.
- ISO 22351:2015 - Emergency management - Message structure for interoperability: ISO 22351 specifies the structure and format of messages used in emergency management systems, ensuring interoperability and effective information exchange among stakeholders. It covers aspects such as message content, coding, and transmission, facilitating standardized communication during emergencies.
- ISO/TR 22351:2015 Societal security - Emergency management - Message structure for exchange of information: This technical report provides guidance on the message structure for exchanging information during emergency management, including the use of standardized terminology.
- ISO 22396:2020 - Security and resilience - Community resilience - Guidelines for information exchange between organizations: This standard provides guidelines for information exchange between organizations involved in community resilience efforts, including emergency management and disaster risk reduction. It offers best practices for sharing data, coordinating activities, and collaborating to enhance community resilience.

NENA

The National Emergency Number Association (NENA) is an organization that focuses on improving the 9-1-1 emergency number system in the United States.

- NENA-INF-015 - Emergency Incident Data Object (EIDO) Information Document: It describes the Emergency Incident Data Object (EIDO), a standardized data format for exchanging incident-related information among emergency response systems, such as CAD, RMS, and PSAPs. EIDO promotes interoperability and efficient information sharing during emergencies and disasters.
- NENA-STA-006 - NG9-1-1 Additional Data Standard: It defines the requirements and specifications for exchanging additional data, such as images, video, and text, within NG9-1-1 systems. The standard aims to support more effective information exchange and decision-making during emergency response efforts.

OASIS EDXL

OASIS is one of the most respected, non-profit standards bodies in the world, OASIS Open offers projects—including open source projects—a path to standardization and de jure approval for reference in international policy and procurement. The OASIS Emergency Management Technical Committee creates vendor-neutral and platform agnostic standards for organizations and agencies to more easily exchange emergency information. The Emergency Data Exchange Language (EDXL) is a broad initiative to create an integrated framework for a wide range of emergency data exchange standards to support operations, logistics, planning and finance. EM-TC standard efforts include:

- EDXL Common Alerting Protocol (EDXL-CAP)
- EDXL Distribution Element (EDXL-DE)
- EDXL Hospital Availability Exchange (EDXL-HAVE)
- EDXL Resource Messaging (EDXL-RM)
- EDXL Reference Information Model (EDXL-RIM)
- EDXL Situation Reporting (EDXL-SitRep)
- EDXL Tracking Emergency Patients (EDXL-TEP)

EU RESEARCH AND INNOVATION FUNDING PROGRAMS

Relevant European projects related to the standardisation of information exchange in emergency response include:

- ResiStand (Increasing disaster Resilience by establishing a sustainable process to support Standardisation of technologies and services): The overall goal of ResiStand is to find new ways to improve the crisis management and disaster resilience capabilities of the European Union and individual Member States through standardisation.
- DRIVER+ (Driving Innovation in Crisis Management for European Resilience) is an EU-funded project aimed at improving crisis management and strengthening the EU's resilience. The project focuses on developing innovative solutions, such as information exchange standards and tools, to enhance interoperability and collaboration among emergency response stakeholders
- EmerGent (Emergency Social Alert Platform): It is an EU-funded project that focuses on using social media for emergency management. It aims to develop a standardized framework for integrating social media data into emergency response operations, enabling more efficient and timely decision-making

9.4.3. Strengths

- Established infrastructure: The EU has a well-developed infrastructure and emergency response system that can be leveraged for standardising information sharing.
- Collaboration: The EU has a history of successful collaboration among its member states, which can promote the adoption of standardised practices.
- Expertise: The EU has access to a large pool of experts and professionals in emergency response, which can contribute to the development and implementation of a standardised information sharing system.
- Regulatory framework: The EU has a strong regulatory framework that can support the development and enforcement of the standardisation of information sharing in emergency response.

- Roadmap for harmonisation: The establishment of a well-accepted roadmap for further harmonisation and/or standardisation in non-technical areas, such as procedures and organisation/training, can guide the implementation of the proposal.

9.4.4. Weaknesses

- Bureaucracy: The EU's complex bureaucracy may slow down the decision-making process and hinder the implementation of a standardised information sharing system.
- Diverse languages and cultures: The linguistic and cultural diversity among EU member states may pose challenges in adopting a unified approach to information sharing, particularly regarding common signs and terminology.
- Limited resources: Despite the EU's overall resources, the allocation and prioritisation of funds for standardising information sharing in emergency response might be challenging.
- Resistance to change: Some member states may resist the adoption of a standardised information sharing system due to concerns about sovereignty or the impact on their existing systems.
- Lack of a common response data/technological model and SOP: The absence of a common data model and standard operating procedures (SOP) based on specific technological solutions and tools can lead to misunderstandings of shared data.

9.4.5. Opportunities

- Technological advancements: Rapid advancements in technology can support the development and implementation of a standardised information sharing system that addresses common signs, terminology, and data models.
- Global trends: Increasing awareness of the importance of emergency preparedness and response can help gain support for the proposal.
- Interoperability: Standardised information sharing can improve interoperability among EU member states, enhancing the efficiency of emergency response efforts.
- Enhanced cooperation with other regions: By adopting a standardised system, the EU can strengthen its relationships with other regions and international organisations in the field of emergency response.

9.4.6. Threats

- Political differences: Political differences among EU member states might hinder the adoption of a standardised information sharing system.
- Security concerns: Standardising information sharing can potentially increase the risk of cyberattacks, data breaches, or misuse of sensitive information.
- Legal and privacy issues: There might be legal and privacy concerns related to sharing sensitive information across borders.
- Economic challenges: Economic challenges faced by some EU member states may prevent them from investing in the development and implementation of a standardised information sharing system.

9.5. CO.WP5-13: Establishing a common federated system for sharing information in emergency response

9.5.1. Summary of the current situation in the EU

Effective emergency response requires rapid, accurate, and reliable information exchange among various stakeholders, including emergency responders, governmental agencies, and the public. In emergency situations, such as natural disasters, terrorist attacks, and pandemics, real-time and accurate information sharing is crucial for managing the incident, allocating resources, and providing assistance to those affected.

The data sharing related to emergency events is tailored by DGPR, and may be limited by the sensitivity of the data being shared when it may involve critical national level security information.

In addition, the technologies used in emergency response, from communication technology to applications, adopted across Europe are not the same and interoperability is not ensured. This increases the data sharing difficulties, which impacts the way response operations are performed and planned, on the sense that they may depend on the technology landscape available.

A number of solutions have been developed tackling different needs, and major steps have been made, however there is no global general solution adopted by the industry and the market for such systems. Data distribution system and technologies, such as web-based data distribution protocols or MQTT have been increasingly adopted, or the security solution based on HTTPS or blockchain have increasingly used, geographical information sharing based on JSON or maps from global services providers and solution providers (e.g. ArcGIS). These are some of the standards that are enabling the integration of the data sharing among emergency response services.

The harmonization of the technologies and data models are key to achieve an operative environment, which includes:

- 1) The communications capability to provides connectivity between the different communications technologies, from TETRA to 4G/5G, IoT, etc., which makes uses of industry standard such as TCP/IP protocols and security protocols such as HTTPS, or certificates. Nevertheless, then effort to harmonize the connection networks still faces legacy constraints linked to the data protocols used, as well as the performance differences between different communications technology which limits their adoption. Traditionally emergency response communication relies on voice communications, PPT and similar technologies, that intent to provide a high resilience, when facing infrastructure affected by catastrophic events, and secure communications to avoid interference from non-emergency personnel and avoid information leak that could lead to population panicking. With the increasing coverage, resilience and higher data transfer capability, technologies such as 4G/5G, satcom communicating and internet protocols are helping harmonize the communication connectivity and integration of Emergency services.
- 2) Location capabilities based on GNSS satellite capability and the democratization of GNSS receivers, has being widely adopted for location and tracking capability of the assets, forces and victims. Because these capabilities can be worldwide accessed and can

support multiple GNNS services, it becomes also resilient and adopted by the emergency responses, and a de facto standard use by the community.

- 3) Data models, naming conventions and taxonomies.
- 4) Data Sharing Systems: integrates and establishes the means for the different systems to interface and share data.

As this opportunity is closely related with technologies and applications availability/maturity, which usually are not an issue for standardisation, the data sharing methodology as well as the COP sharing mechanism, also analysed in WP4, could be the starting point to address actions towards standardization.

Figure 24 – ERCC webapp

SHARING INFORMATION SYSTEMS IN THE EU

A federated information exchange system refers to a collaborative network of interconnected systems, databases, and platforms that facilitate the sharing and exchange of information between different entities while maintaining their individual autonomy, security, and data ownership.

In the context of the European Union, these systems would help Member States cooperate, share resources, and improve decision-making, while respecting the sovereignty and data protection regulations of each state. Currently there is no common data federated systems to share operational emergency data at EU level, but there are some examples in other applications, such as the Schengen Information System: a large-scale, decentralized information exchange system used by the Member States participating in the Schengen Area. It allows law enforcement, border control, and immigration authorities to share data related to wanted or missing persons, criminal suspects, stolen or lost property, and other relevant information to maintain security and facilitate freedom of movement within the Schengen Area.

Although without the characteristics of a federated system, there currently exist several information sharing systems between the Member States of the European Union that are relevant to emergency and disaster preparedness, planning, or response:

- Common Emergency Communication and Information System (CECIS): CECIS is a web-based communication and information exchange platform used by the EU Member States and the European Commission to facilitate cooperation during emergencies and disasters. It enables the sharing of real-time information, requests for assistance, and coordination of resources during civil protection interventions, both within the EU and in third countries.
- Common Information Sharing Environment (CISE): CISE is a collaborative initiative aimed at enhancing the exchange of information between maritime surveillance authorities in the EU. Although not exclusively focused on emergency and disaster response, CISE contributes to improved situational awareness in various maritime domains, including safety and security, border control, and environmental protection. By facilitating the sharing of data between national and EU systems, CISE enables more effective and efficient cooperation among different authorities during maritime emergencies and incidents.
- Emergency Response Coordination Centre (ERCC): The ERCC is the operational hub of the European Union Civil Protection Mechanism. It serves as a coordination platform for emergency response efforts during natural and man-made disasters. The ERCC monitors emergencies worldwide, liaises with affected countries, and facilitates the deployment of assistance from EU Member States and participating countries. The ERCC operates 24/7 and uses various information sharing systems, such as CECIS, to ensure effective coordination and communication during emergencies.
- European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC) systems: ECDC operates various platforms and networks to support EU Member States in the surveillance, monitoring, and response to communicable diseases and public health threats. The Early Warning and Response System (EWRS) and the Epidemic Intelligence Information System (EPIS) facilitate rapid information exchange and risk assessment during infectious disease outbreaks and other health emergencies.
- European Disaster Response Information System (EDRIS): EDRIS is a secure, web-based platform that supports the EU Civil Protection Mechanism by facilitating the sharing of information related to disaster response operations. EDRIS allows participating countries to access and update relevant data, such as contact details, available resources, and response capacities. The system helps improve the coordination and efficiency of disaster response efforts across the EU.
- European Flood Awareness System (EFAS): EFAS provides early flood warnings and risk forecasts to national and regional water authorities across Europe. It helps authorities anticipate and prepare for potential flooding events by monitoring and modeling hydrological data, weather forecasts, and river levels.
- European Forest Fire Information System (EFFIS): EFFIS is a comprehensive system that supports the EU Member States in monitoring, assessing, and responding to forest fires. It provides near-real-time information on active fires, fire danger forecasts, and post-fire assessments, which helps authorities in decision-making and resource allocation for firefighting and prevention measures.

- European Integrated Earth Observation System (Copernicus): Copernicus is an EU-wide Earth observation program that collects and processes data from satellites, ground-based sensors, and other sources. The data is used for various applications, including emergency management and disaster response. Copernicus Emergency Management Service (EMS) supports authorities by providing rapid mapping of affected areas, damage assessment, and other geospatial information during natural disasters and other emergencies.
- European Maritime Safety Agency (EMSA) systems: EMSA offers a range of systems and services that support EU Member States in maritime safety, security, and pollution response. Among them, the CleanSeaNet and SafeSeaNet platforms provide satellite-based monitoring of oil spills and maritime traffic, respectively, helping authorities coordinate response efforts in case of emergencies.
- European Seismic Hazard Map (ESHM): The ESHM is a tool developed by the European Commission's Joint Research Centre (JRC) that provides seismic hazard assessments for the European territory. The map helps authorities identify areas at risk of earthquakes, enabling them to take preventive measures and enhance preparedness for seismic events.
- Global Disaster Alert and Coordination System (GDACS): GDACS is an international cooperation framework developed by the United Nations, the European Commission, and other partners. It provides real-time alerts and impact assessments for natural disasters, such as earthquakes, tsunamis, tropical cyclones, and floods. GDACS also offers tools for information sharing and coordination among disaster responders, including a Virtual On-Site Operations Coordination Centre (VOSOCC). Although not exclusively an EU system, GDACS serves as an important source of information and coordination for EU Member States during global disaster response operations.

The screenshot shows the EDRIS website search interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the European Commission logo and the text 'EUROPEAN CIVIL PROTECTION AND HUMANITARIAN AID OPERATIONS EDRIS'. Below this, there is a search form with several filters: Donor (with '+ Add Donor' button), Recipient country(ies) (with '+ Add Country' button), Contracts or Decisions (with a dropdown menu showing 'Decision & Contract'), Financial Year (with '+ Add Financial Year' button), Recipient world region(s) (with '+ Add World Region' button), In-kind or Cash (with a dropdown menu showing 'Cash'), Local Currency (with a dropdown menu showing 'Euro'), Project Code, and Type of Funding. There is also a 'Glide' section with a search icon and a 'COVID-19' checkbox. At the bottom, there is a 'Search form parameters' section showing 'Donor : All | Financial Year : All | In € | Recipient Country : All | Decisions and Contracts | Only Cash |' and a search bar with 'Reset' and 'Search' buttons.

Figure 25 – EDRIS website

9.5.2. Review of previous harmonization, homogenization and standardization efforts

A major effort is being made from several countries, research entities, civil protection institutions and countries policy entities, including at EU level, in order to establish a harmonization and standardization of the conventions, naming and characterization of the information that supports the emergency response coordination, increases interoperability between systems and makes more easy and more agile the integration of forces from different countries in a common response team.

APCO (ASSOCIATION OF PUBLIC-SAFETY COMMUNICATIONS OFFICIALS INTERNATIONAL)

APCO is an international organization dedicated to public safety communication. APCO is involved in the development and promotion of standards related to information exchange and protocols in emergencies and disasters. Some key APCO publications in this area are:

- APCO ANS 1.101.1-201x - Public Safety Communications Common Incident Types for Data Exchange: This standard defines a list of common incident types for public safety communications to enable consistent data exchange among emergency response organizations. The standard promotes interoperability and efficient information sharing by providing a common set of incident type codes and descriptions.
- APCO ANS 1.102.1-201x - Public Safety Communications Standard for XML Incident Data Exchange (XML-IDE): This standard specifies the XML-based data exchange format for incident information among public safety communications systems. XML-IDE enables seamless information sharing among Computer-Aided Dispatch (CAD) systems, records management systems (RMS), and other emergency response systems, promoting interoperability and efficient response efforts.
- APCO ANS 1.103.1-201x - Public Safety Communications Standard for Computer-Aided Dispatch (CAD) Initial Incident Data Exchange: This standard defines the data exchange format and requirements for initial incident information sharing between CAD systems and other emergency response systems. The standard aims to ensure timely and accurate information exchange during the initial stages of an emergency incident.
- APCO ANS 1.104.1-201x - Public Safety Communications Standard for CAD Interoperability Data Exchange (CAD-IDE): This standard specifies the data exchange format and requirements for sharing CAD incident information among different CAD systems and other emergency response systems. CAD-IDE promotes interoperability and efficient information sharing, enabling coordinated response efforts among multiple agencies.
- APCO ANS 1.106.1-201x - Public Safety Communications Standard for Interface to IP-based Alarm Monitoring Service Provider (IP-AMSP) Systems: This standard defines the interface and data exchange requirements for connecting public safety communications systems to IP-based Alarm Monitoring Service Provider (IP-AMSP) systems. It enables the efficient exchange of alarm information and related data, promoting timely and accurate emergency response.
- APCO Project 43 - Broadband Implications for the PSAP: APCO Project 43 is an initiative that explores the implications of broadband technologies on Public Safety Answering Points (PSAPs) and emergency communications. The project aims to identify best practices, standards, and guidelines for the integration of broadband technologies in emergency communications, facilitating improved information exchange and response capabilities.

EUROPEAN EMERGENCY NUMBER ASSOCIATION (EENA)

EENA is a non-governmental organization dedicated to promoting the use of the European Emergency Number 112 and improving emergency response systems in Europe. EENA works with stakeholders to develop and implement best practices, guidelines, and standards for emergency communication and information exchange. EENA collaborates with public authorities, emergency service providers, and industry partners to enhance coordination, interoperability, and efficiency in emergency response.

- EENA Operations Document - Next Generation 112 (NG112): This document provides guidelines for the implementation of Next Generation 112 (NG112) systems, which are IP-based emergency communication systems designed to improve the handling and exchange of emergency call information. The document covers aspects such as system architecture, call routing, and additional data exchange, promoting more effective and efficient emergency response efforts.
- EENA Operations Document - Drones in Emergency Services: This document explores the potential use of drones in emergency services, focusing on aspects such as data collection, information exchange, and operational coordination. The document provides guidelines and best practices for leveraging drone technology to enhance emergency response capabilities and improve overall public safety.
- EENA Operations Document - Public Warning: It provides guidelines for the implementation of public warning systems, which are designed to disseminate emergency alerts and information to the public during emergencies and disasters. The document covers aspects such as alerting channels, message content, and system operation, aiming to ensure effective and efficient information exchange and coordination among stakeholders.
- EENA Operations Document - Social Media in Emergency Management: It explores the role of social media in emergency management, focusing on aspects such as information gathering, dissemination, and collaboration. The document provides guidelines and best practices for leveraging social media platforms to enhance emergency response capabilities and improve overall public safety.

EUROPEAN COMMITTEE FOR STANDARDIZATION (CEN)

CEN is a non-profit organization that develops European Standards (ENs) across various sectors, including emergency management. CEN collaborates with national standardization bodies, industry stakeholders, and technical experts to develop and maintain standards that promote interoperability, safety, and efficiency in emergency response systems. These standards help to harmonize procedures, technologies, and data exchange protocols among EU member states.

CEN/TR 17432:2019 - Crisis management - Guidelines for developing a common operational picture: It provides guidelines for developing a common operational picture (COP) in crisis management. A COP is a shared and continuously updated representation of relevant information that supports situational awareness, decision-making, and coordination among various stakeholders involved in emergency response. The Technical Report covers key aspects of developing and maintaining a COP, including:

- Information requirements: Identifying the types of information needed for a COP, such as incident location, affected population, and available resources.
- Information sources: Defining and managing various information sources, including internal and external data sources, as well as real-time and historical data.
- Information processing: Guidelines for processing, analysing, and validating the collected information to ensure its accuracy, relevance, and timeliness.
- Information visualization: Recommendations for presenting the information in a clear, comprehensible, and actionable format, including the use of maps, charts, and other visual aids.

- Information sharing: Guidelines for enabling efficient and secure information exchange among stakeholders, including the use of standardized formats, protocols, and communication channels.
- COP maintenance: Recommendations for maintaining the COP throughout the crisis, including updating and archiving processes, as well as addressing potential challenges such as information overload and outdated data.

INTERNATIONAL TELECOMMUNICATION UNION (ITU)

The International Telecommunication Union (ITU) has published several recommendations, guidelines, and reports related to information exchange protocols in emergencies and disasters:

- ITU-T E.106 - International Emergency Preference Scheme (IEPS) for disaster relief operations: ITU-T E.106 is a recommendation that describes the International Emergency Preference Scheme (IEPS), a system for prioritizing telecommunications services during disaster relief operations. IEPS aims to ensure reliable and efficient communication among emergency responders and organizations, supporting effective information exchange and coordination.
- ITU-R M.2033 - Global Maritime Distress and Safety System (GMDSS): ITU-R M.2033 is a recommendation that defines the Global Maritime Distress and Safety System (GMDSS), a set of procedures, technologies, and communication protocols for maritime safety and emergency communications. GMDSS enables efficient information exchange and coordination among ships, rescue coordination centres, and other maritime stakeholders during emergencies and disasters.
- ITU-R M.2080 - Earthquake and tsunami warning systems for coastal areas: ITU-R M.2080 is a recommendation that provides guidelines for the implementation of earthquake and tsunami warning systems for coastal areas. It covers aspects such as data collection, processing, and dissemination, aiming to ensure timely and accurate information exchange during emergencies.
- ITU-D SG2 Report on Question 22/2 - Utilization of telecommunications/ICT for disaster preparedness, mitigation, and response: This ITU-D report explores the role of telecommunications and ICT in disaster management, focusing on aspects such as early warning, communication networks, and information exchange. The report provides guidelines and best practices for leveraging telecommunications and ICT to enhance emergency response capabilities and improve overall disaster resilience.
- ITU Handbook on Telecommunication Outside Plant in Areas Frequently Exposed to Natural Disasters: This ITU Handbook provides guidelines for the design, construction, and maintenance of telecommunication outside plant infrastructure in areas exposed to natural disasters. The Handbook aims to improve the resilience of telecommunication networks, ensuring reliable and efficient information exchange during emergencies and disasters.

NENA

National Emergency Number Association (NENA) publications play a critical role in promoting efficient information exchange and coordinated response efforts in emergencies and disasters:

- NENA-STA-010 - Detailed Functional and Interface Standards for the NENA i3 Solution: It defines the functional and interface requirements for the NENA i3 solution, an IP-

based, next-generation 9-1-1 (NG9-1-1) system. The i3 solution enables more efficient information exchange among public safety answering points (PSAPs), emergency responders, and other stakeholders, supporting enhanced emergency response capabilities.

- NENA-STA-011 - NG9-1-1 Data Management Standard: It provides guidelines for the management of data within NG9-1-1 systems, covering aspects such as data quality, validation, and security. The standard aims to ensure accurate and timely information exchange during emergencies and disasters.
- NENA-STA-071 - NG9-1-1 Public Safety Answering Point (PSAP) Credentialing Standard: Provides guidelines for the credentialing of PSAPs within NG9-1-1 systems, ensuring the secure and efficient exchange of information among authorized users and systems during emergencies and disasters.

EU RESEARCH AND INNOVATION FUNDING PROGRAMS

Some European projects worth mentioning in the field of information exchange systems for emergencies and disasters are:

- I-REACT (Improving Resilience to Emergencies through Advanced Cyber Technologies) is an EU-funded project that aimed to improve the management of emergencies and disasters by developing a standardized platform for integrating and analysing data from multiple sources such as big data analytics, social media, and wearable devices. The project developed a Common Terminology and a set of guidelines for data sharing, as well as tools for real-time monitoring and decision-making.
- BeAware (Enhancing decision support and management services in extreme weather climate events): This project aimed to provide support in all the phases of an emergency incident. More specifically, we propose an integrated solution to support forecasting, early warnings, transmission and routing of the emergency data, aggregated analysis of multimodal data and management the coordination between the first responders and the authorities.

9.5.3. Strengths

- Integration and Coordination: The system would promote a unified approach to emergency response across EU member states, increasing efficiency and communication.
- Standardization of information sharing in emergency response: A federated information sharing system will enable the EU to create a standardized process for sharing information during emergencies, reducing confusion and improving coordination among various agencies and territories.
- Enhanced Interoperability: The system would promote the development of common standards and protocols, leading to better interoperability between the emergency services of different member states.
- Enhanced efficiency and better management of operations: The system will improve the exchange of information between the Common Operational Picture (COP) and emergency services, resulting in more effective and streamlined operations.
- Easy implementation and scalability: A federated system is easier to implement and can be scaled up or down, depending on the needs of the participating entities. This allows for greater flexibility and adaptability.

- Legacy system integration: The federated system allows legacy systems to more easily share data with newer systems, improving overall data exchange and interoperability.
- Data traceability and usage: The system supports data usage and access traceability, improving accountability and control over shared information.
- Improved cybersecurity: By implementing common operational procedures, such as those used in SIGRUN-like operational systems, the federated system can better manage cybersecurity risks.

9.5.4. Weaknesses

- Technical Challenges: Integrating various technologies and systems from different member states may prove difficult, potentially leading to technical issues and delays.
- Privacy and Security: The system would need to ensure data privacy and security, given the sensitive nature of the information involved. This could be a significant challenge in a system that involves numerous stakeholders and data sources.
- Incompatible tools and semantics: Coordination and integration of tools with different semantics and taxonomies may be difficult, leading to confusion and inefficiency during emergency response.
- Limited social media support: The system may provide only minimal support for exploiting social media data, potentially limiting the situational awareness and understanding of the public's response to actions taken.

9.5.5. Opportunities

- Cross-border Collaboration: A federated system would encourage further collaboration between EU member states, fostering stronger relationships and building trust.
- Innovation and Technology: The development and implementation of the system could drive innovation in emergency response technologies and solutions, benefiting both the EU and its member states.
- Capacity Building: The system would provide an opportunity for member states to develop their emergency response capacities, particularly for those with fewer resources or less experience in this area.
- Public Safety: By improving the EU's overall emergency response capabilities, the system would contribute to increased public safety and resilience in the face of crises.
- Social media data analysis: Incorporating automated data analysis from social media can provide valuable information and situational awareness during emergencies.
- Copernicus Emergency Services utilization: The federated system can leverage Copernicus Emergency Services, including Satellite IoT for vehicle/first responder tracking on COPs and as an alternative for communication during emergencies.
- Role-specific information clusters: Generating oriented/guided information clusters for specific first responder roles can enhance situational awareness and decision-making during emergencies.

9.5.6. Threats

- Heavy reliance on terrestrial telecommunication networks: This dependence could lead to issues during emergency situations, where network infrastructure might be disrupted or overwhelmed.
- Low industry awareness: A lack of awareness among industries (IoT, sensors, satellites, etc.) in preparing resilient systems for catastrophic events may limit the effectiveness of the federated system during emergencies.

- Lack of common standards: The absence of a common standard for COP data usage/display and understanding may hinder effective communication and collaboration among participating entities.
- Low understanding by policy makers: Policy makers may lack a comprehensive understanding of the federated system's requirements when designing or upgrading existing systems, leading to suboptimal implementation.
- Bureaucracy: Implementing the federated system may be slowed down by bureaucratic processes, particularly if member states have conflicting interests or concerns about sovereignty.
- Funding and Resource Allocation: Adequate funding and resources are required to develop and maintain the system, which may be difficult to secure given competing priorities and limited budgets in some member states.
- Political and foreign policy constraints: Political considerations or foreign policy issues may restrict the implementation or effectiveness of a federated information sharing system for emergency response in the European Union.
- Cybersecurity Risks: The centralization of information and resources in the FISSER may increase the risk of cyberattacks, potentially compromising the system and its effectiveness.

9.6. CO.WP5-3: Harmonization of alert and warning procedures in emergency response

9.6.1. Summary of the current situation in the EU

The purpose of alerts and warnings is to provide the necessary information to warn the public and effect the necessary actions that will lead to their safety and to deliver the messages to populations at risk of imminent threats with the goal of maximizing the probability that people take protective actions and minimize the delay in taking those actions. There are common elements that allow us to define Early Warning System as the set of tools, control devices, management capabilities, and technological tools, which key institutions identify to disseminate information in a timely manner to communities exposed to a risk. Effective incident response needs a structured and pre-planned public warning. Public warning is based on two functions: hazard monitoring and warning dissemination. It is also necessary to establish a mechanism for risk identification, hazard monitoring, decision-making, warning dissemination, and to evaluate and improve.

Alerts and warnings may be sent by government agencies, fundamentally Civil Protection, fire departments or Emergency Systems, regional or local administration, media station or private systems. The EU's early warning and information systems help the Emergency Response Coordination Centre monitor hazards and events worldwide. Examples of hazards that the Centre monitors are earthquakes and tsunamis, tropical cyclones, volcanoes, droughts, floods, and forest fires.

Article 110 of the European Electronic Communications Code (EECC)¹ made it mandatory for all the Member States of the European Union to deploy a Public Warning system using telephone networks to alert everyone located in a specific area of an ongoing crisis or upcoming disaster. Article 110 states that Member States shall ensure that, when public warning systems regarding imminent or developing major emergencies and disasters are in place, public warnings are

transmitted by providers of mobile number-based interpersonal communication services to end-users concerned.

EECC Article 110 indicates that Member States may determine that public warnings be transmitted through other different publicly available electronic communications services and other than broadcasting services, or through internet access service or a mobile application relying on an internet access service, provided that the effectiveness of the public warning system is equivalent in terms of coverage and capacity to reach end-users including those only temporarily present in the area concerned, taking utmost account of BEREC (Body of European Regulators for Electronic Communications) guidelines

The EU supports its Member States in the assessment of hazards by complementing their national early warning and information systems in real-time. These tools contribute to early analysis and actions through early warnings. Alerts allow the Emergency Response Coordination Centre to provide a comprehensive early assessment. It also enables early action within the framework of EU civil protection inside the EU and worldwide. These early warning and information systems are part of the **EU's Copernicus programme**. The Copernicus programme is developed by the European Commission (EC) with the support of the European Space Agency (ESA) and the European Environment Agency (EEA). Its main objective is to provide useful information for the efficient management of emergency situations, citizen security and mitigation and adaptation to climate change.

There aren't homogenous form in EU members with regard to risk communication, awareness raising and early warning systems. In European Countries there is a high availability of plans, procedures and tools for alerts and warnings, and there are technological means available to support it. We have seen that there are different means of communicating alerts and warnings. This communication ranges from more traditional systems, such as sirens, to the use of more modern technologies and the exploitation of social networks. The population alert system based on mobile, which is an integral part of the disaster crisis communication strategy, is an alert and information system via sending of a SMS or voice calls with national or even regional coverage and on a mobile application to inform and alert the population via notifications on mobile phones. The purpose of the SMS alert and information system for the population is to inform and alert the entire population or to inform and alert only a part of the population in the immediate environment of the danger (risk zone). This system also called Wireless Emergency alert (WEA) is widely used in several countries around the world including the United States of America (USA), formerly known as the Commercial Mobile Alert System, is an alerting network in U.S. designed to disseminate emergency alerts to mobile devices such as cell phones and pagers. The country's warning capabilities, such as mobile-based warning systems like WEA and IPAWS, will need to evolve and progress as the capabilities of smartphones and other mobile broadband devices improve and new technologies become available. This evolution will need to be based on both technical research and social and behavioral science research.

Internet and social networks, which represents both an opportunity thanks to the rapid dissemination of information and a challenge due to the large presence of falsehoods, hoaxes and fake news, which poses a significant threat to their usefulness any emergency responders cite misinformation on social media as a major concern and a barrier to adopting social media in their work. Disinformation includes false or misleading information purposefully spread to

mislead or confuse others—possibly for malicious purposes. Disinformation represents a particularly insidious threat, especially in connected information environments where malicious actors from outside of the affected area may try to interfere with response efforts or intentionally manipulate behaviour to put people in harm's way. Among the private initiatives to support administrations in the management of crises in a digital scenario, the Virtual Operation Support Team (VOST) appears. These teams are made up of professionals from the world of emergencies who collaborate altruistically with the accounts of the emergency services on Twitter in the monitoring of social networks to go viral prevention messages and the detection of hoaxes. These initiatives must be supported by governments.

Another point of interest are "high priority public warnings". This refers to alerts for situations in which people need to act immediately or within the next hour, in response to an extraordinary or significant threat that is already observed or is likely to occur. Although these are less than one percent of the alert messages typically accessible to the public, such high priority messages are crucial to enabling people to preserve life and protect property. Whether any particular alert should be treated as a high priority public warning is primarily a matter of policy. There is not universal definition in high priority warning nor is there a common approach or management, especially in EU.

In conclusion, the high availability of standardized warning and notification procedures, plans and tools is striking, but at the same time they are still supported by technological means that are far from those offered by the current state of technology. Alert and warning systems exist within a larger communication and technical ecosystem, and government-designed and maintained systems must fit within this larger ecosystem. A more cohesive and all-encompassing alert and warning system is needed that will integrate public and private communications mechanisms and sources of information, and continue to provide the necessary information for the purpose of preserving the health and safety of people, such that new technologies for alerts and warnings can be adopted quickly.

9.6.2. Review of previous harmonization, homogenization and standardization efforts

The Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015-2030 was adopted at the Third United Nations World Conference on Disaster Risk Reduction. In this Framework in order to support the assessment of global progress in achieving the outcome and goal of the document, seven global targets had been agreed, and the seventh consists on substantially increase the availability of and access to multi-hazard early warning systems and disaster risk information and assessment to people by 2030. <https://www.undrr.org/implementing-sendai-framework /what-sendai-framework>

HARMONIZATION OF ALERT AND WARNING PROCEDURES IN EMERGENCY RESPONSE

Harmonization of alert and warning procedures is critical for effective emergency response in the EU. Alert and warning systems enable emergency responders to quickly and effectively notify the public of potential or imminent threats, such as natural disasters, terrorist attacks, and other emergencies. Standardized alert and warning procedures ensure that the public receives consistent and clear information about the threat and the appropriate actions to take in response.

Several initiatives have been undertaken by EU institutions and organizations to harmonize alert and warning procedures in emergency response. Here are some examples:

- **INSPIRE Directive** - The INSPIRE Directive, adopted in 2007, aims to establish a European infrastructure for spatial information, including alert and warning systems. The Directive includes provisions for the development and implementation of interoperable alert and warning systems, based on standardized spatial data infrastructure (SDI).
- **European Civil Protection Mechanism** - The European Civil Protection Mechanism is a network of EU Member States and participating countries that work together to respond to emergencies and disasters. The Mechanism includes a system for alert and warning, which is based on standardized procedures and protocols for information sharing and communication.
- **European Emergency Number Association (EENA)** - The EENA is a non-governmental organization that works to promote effective emergency response in Europe. The organization has developed a set of guidelines and recommendations for alert and warning systems, including recommendations for standardized procedures for information sharing, communication, and coordination.
- **European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI)** - The ETSI is a European standards organization that develops standards for telecommunications and information technology. The organization has developed several standards related to alert and warning systems, including the Common Alerting Protocol (CAP), which provides a standardized protocol for the exchange of emergency alerts and warnings.
- **The International Telecommunication Union (ITU-T): ITU-T SG16** developed Recommendation ITU-T H.785.1 (ex H.DS-PISR) «Digital signage: Service requirements and a reference model on information services in public places via an interoperable service platform”. This technology can be used for early warning to lessen damages, reporting up-to-the-minute situations and announcing traffic status/evacuation sites.
- **OASIS: The OASIS Emergency Management TC** created the Common Alerting Protocol (CAP), used by crisis responders, weather prediction agencies and emergency management stakeholders for broadcasting data about crisis conditions and locations, over various media including SMS, police radio and weather radio. CAP also is approved as ITU-T Rec X-1303. A suite of related Emergency Data Exchange Language (EDXL) resource and crisis management XML standards have also been developed, supporting exchange of health facility availability information (HAVE), data sharing of information on situations, incidents, events and responses (SitREP) and sharing of emergency patient and tracking information (TEP)
- **EU Directive 2018/1972 on the European Electronic Communications Code** - This Directive, adopted in December 2018, sets out common rules for the provision of electronic communications services across the EU. The Directive includes provisions related to alert and warning systems, including requirements for Member States to develop and implement alert and warning systems based on standardized protocols and procedures.

EU ROLLING PLAN FOR ICT STANDARDISATION: PUBLIC WARNING SYSTEMS.

The Rolling Plan for ICT Standardisation is drafted by the European Commission in collaboration with the European Multi-Stakeholder Platform (MSP) on ICT Standardisation and is updated

annually. It lists all the topics identified as EU policy priorities where standardisation, standards, or ICT technical specifications may play a key role in the implementation of the policy. It covers technologies of 'horizontal importance', ones whose application have a wide impact across different technical fields, in the context of ICT infrastructures and ICT standardisation.

Regarding public warning systems, the article 110 of the European Electronic Communication Code requires that by 21 June 2022, Member States shall ensure that, when public warning systems regarding imminent or developing major emergencies and disasters are in place, public warnings are transmitted by providers of mobile number-based interpersonal communications services to the end-users concerned.

References:

- Directive (EU) 2018/1972 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2018 establishing the European Electronic Communications Code.
- COMMISSION DELEGATED REGULATION (EU) 2019/320 of 12 December 2018 supplementing of Directive 2014/53/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council with regard to the application of the essential requirements referred to in Article 3(3)(g) of that Directive in order to ensure caller location in emergency communications from mobile devices.
- Directive 2002/58/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 July 2002 concerning the processing of personal data and the protection of privacy in the electronic communications sector (Directive on privacy and electronic communications).
- Recommendation 2003/558/EC of the Commission of the European Communities of 25 July 2003 on the processing of caller location information in electronic communication networks for the purpose of location-enhanced emergency call Service.

The EECC (European Electronic Communications Code) Article 110 directive states that the public warning system must be mobile phone-based and capable of sending geo-located mass alerts. The alerts must be received by the mobile phones of everyone within an emergency area. These systems take time to implement as they require collaboration with the major mobile telecom carriers in each country. European member states are also given the option to implement alternate systems if it can be proven that they are just as effective as the phone based systems. Two years after the release of the EECC, BEREC (Body of European Regulators for Electronic Communications) released guidelines on <https://eu.genasys.com/resources/berec-guidelines/n> how to assess and compare effectiveness to ensure these potential alternate systems are viable.

Finally, In February 2023, a communication was made from European Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the regions in order to improve resilience in disasters, through five objectives or goals, one of this related to enhance early warning, because recent disaster have shown that warning local population in due time remains a challenge. Establishing an effective institutional setup that ensure the timely transmission of warning messages across the national, regional and local level is critical.

In addition, when crafting warning messages, Member States should take the specific needs of people in vulnerable situations, those with disabilities and children into account. Warning messages should be accessible, clear and actionable and, to the extent possible, should be

provided in several languages to make sure they reach all segments of the population including tourists, seasonal residents and migrants. Finally, complex transboundary disasters highlight the need for a wide-spectrum early warning system at Union level. The Commission intends to explore with Members States how early warnings could be made more accessible to all citizens of the Union, including travellers, tourists and communities in cross-border areas across the territory of the Union.

HARMONIZATION OF ALERTS

EU Civil Protection Mechanism brings together a total of 33 countries: 27 EU members States and 6 participants States (Norway, Iceland, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Serbia and Turkey) This EU Civil Protection shares operational challenges and similar approaches to managing disaster, while the structure and composition of emergency services varies considerably from country to country. Under the mechanism, countries stand ready and prepare to help each other when national resources for disaster response are overwhelmed or need to be reinforced.

The EU supports its Member States in the assessment of hazards by complementing their national early warning and information systems in real-time. These tools contribute to early analysis and actions through early warnings.

Alerts allow the Emergency Response Coordination Centre (ERCC) to provide a comprehensive early assessment. It also enables early action within the framework of EU civil protection inside the EU and worldwide.

The ERCC has developed a range of automated European and global early warning and detection systems through which it monitors events in and outside the Union territory. To translate warnings and alerts from those systems into user-targeted information for emergency response, the Union Mechanism support European scientific partnerships that provide 24/7 service for rapid impact assessments for detected or forecast events.

Close cooperation with various research institutes facilitates the development of disaster forecasting and disaster management tools for both natural and human-induced hazards:

- Global Disaster Alert and Coordination System: provides alerts and estimates impacts of earthquakes, tsunamis, tropical cyclones, floods, volcanos, and droughts worldwide. European and Global Flood Awareness Systems: give notifications on floods up to 15 days in advance in Europe and worldwide.
- European and Global Forest Fire Information Systems: forecast dangerous weather conditions up to 10 days ahead and provide near-real-time information on active fires and burnt areas. The systems analyse the severity and risk that each forest fire poses for the local population and the environment. This allows informed decisions on the deployment of the rescEU firefighting capacity.
- European and Global Drought Observatories: give information on droughts risks in Europe and worldwide, including meteorological indicators, soil moisture anomalies, vegetation stress and river low flows.

These early warning and information systems are part of the EU's Copernicus programme. <https://emergency.copernicus.eu/mapping/ems/what-copernicus>

The Copernicus programme is developed by the European Commission (EC) with the support of the European Space Agency (ESA) and the European Environment Agency (EEA). Its main

objective is to provide useful information for the efficient management of emergency situations, citizen security and mitigation and adaptation to climate change.

Users are entities and organizations at regional, national, European and international level active in the field of crisis management in the EU Member States, the States participating in the European Civil Protection Mechanism, the Directorates-General (DG) and the EU agencies of the Commission, the European External Action Service (EEAS), as well as international humanitarian aid organizations. WEA is a public safety system that allows customers who own compatible mobile devices geographically targeted, text like messages alerting them of imminent threats to safety in their area. Wireless companies volunteer to participate in WEA, which is the result of a unique public/private partnership between the Federal Emergency Management Agency, the Federal Communications Commission, and the U.S. industry in order to enhance public safety.

<https://www.fcc.gov/consumers/guides/wireless-emergency-alerts-wea>

Several countries in U.S have adopted the use of the Integrated Public Alert and Warning System (IPAWS). This System was created under Executive Order 13407 to integrate various alerting systems— Emergency Alert System, National Warning System, Wireless Emergency Alerts, and NOAA Weather Radio All Hazards—into one modern network. IPAWS takes advantage of the Common Alerting Protocol (CAP), an XML-based data format for exchanging alerts and warnings.

EU-Alert is the generic term for the European Public Warning Service based upon Cell Broadcast technology (this is a method of sending messages to multiple mobile telephone users in a defined area at the same time). EU-Alert is compatible with Wireless Emergency Alerts (WEA) formerly known as the Commercial Mobile Alert System (CMAS) standard as used in the United States. Since 2012, and by default, mobile phone OSes like Android, iOS, and Windows support EU-Alert/WEA/CMAS via Cell Broadcast for public warning messages.

TECHNICAL STANDARDS:

It plays an important role in communication systems. As such, a single emergency alert message standard is needed to communicate alerts over a variety of communications infrastructure (e.g., broadcast TV and radio, cellular, and wired media), thereby reaching the end user over variety of last-mile technologies (e.g., cellular, cable, DSL, WiFi, Bluetooth). The Common Alerting Protocol (CAP) attempts to serve this purpose. CAP, which is used by IPAWS, provides a standardized data profile that defines a consistent way for alert and warning messages to be distributed among the involved entities (alert originators, the Federal Emergency Management Agency, the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, public safety, broadcasters and mobile operators. This standard takes the form of an XML format and is one of the many standardized XML formats that the Organization for the Advancement of Structured Information Standards maintains. The CAP standard describes how the information is formatted. While CAP provides a common format, any changes in the type of information exchanged in CAP or any changes in how the carriers might communicate this information to a wireless subscriber requires additional standards and versions of those standards.

OASIS EDXL

OASIS project, an organization that supports open source communities in a wide range of open collaboration projects, has developed Technical Committees for member-developed works about information exchange to advance incident preparedness and response to emergency situations. The OASIS Emergency Management Framework (EMF) is a reference implementation

and toolkit for enabling standardized emergency information exchange using the OASIS Emergency Data Exchange Language (EDXL). With the EMF, developers and users can create, send, store, template, visualize, search, and organize emergency messages. EDXL provides standardized alerting, resource sharing, situation reporting, tracking of emergency patients and clients, hospital availability, as well as packaging and addressing of emergency messages and attachments. Emergency Data Exchange Language (EDXL) is a family of standards, providing a common language, or interface, for data exchange across emergency-related systems. https://www.oasis-open.org/committees/tc_home.php?wg_abbrev=emergency

EM-TC standard effort include *EDXL Common Alerting Protocol (EDXL-CAP)*

oneM2M

Some examples of features of oneM2M to enable communication in emergency situations are access controls, message prioritization, network congestion alleviation, group communication, subscription/ Notification and location tracking.

For more details see the oneM2M Technical Report in “TR-0046-Study_on_Public_Warning_Service_Enabler” and the oneM2M Technical Specification “TS-0037-IoT_Public_Warning_Service_Enablement”.

ISO STANDARDIZATION EFFORTS:

In the specific case of the warning systems there are various ISO standards (The International Organization for Standardization) that should be taken into account due to their special international relevance to the issue that we are reviewing: alert and warning:

- **UNE-EN ISO 22315:2018. Societal security. Mass evacuation. Guidelines for planning (ISO 22315:2014) (Endorsed by Asociación Española de Normalización in April of 2020):** In this document are given the following terms and definitions: incident management system, preparedness, community-based warning system, area at risk and affected area. There is a mention about the general aspects for mass evacuation planning, including how should be developed the risk assessments, the compliance with legislation and policies (operating at international, national, regional and local levels), the information gathering and analysis, the planning operational resource allocation and documenting processes, the effective multi-agency partnering arrangements and the training and exercising. There is also a mention about how should be prepared the public for mass evacuation. In the following section it focuses on the visualization of the areas that are at risk or affected. To achieve this, it describes the need to contribute with map data about the area that is at risk or affected, considering types of information to capture on maps and ensuring the compatibility of data to build maps, developing what criteria must be met.
- **ISO 22322:2015. Societal security. Emergency management. Guidelines for public warning. 1st edition. English version:** This ISO standard reflects the normative references and define the following terms: alert, all clear, hazard monitoring function, warning dissemination function, notification, people at risk, public warning system and vulnerable group. It relies on 2 figures to describe two main concepts: the public warning system and the public warning process. The public warning system is described with the enumeration of the steps to follow: design the framework, identify public warning objectives, implement the public warning process and evaluate and improve.

The result of the assessment made for the organization should determine the type of public warning that may be required and documented for future references. Speaking of the public warning process, it is described with the same steps structure: hazard monitoring process, operational decision-making, warning dissemination process and human factor considerations. In both cases the organization develop various interesting approaches in detail: how should be developed the planning, who are the responsible and what are their functions, what are the main characteristics included and what criteria should be met. This guide also included 2 annexes. In Annex A establish an interesting relationship between alert and notification in public warning. In Annex B makes reference to public awareness.

- **ISO 22324:2015. Societal security. Emergency management. Guidelines for colour-coded alerts. 1st edition. English version:** It reflects the normative references and define the following terms: alert, colour blindness, colour-code and hue. Colour-coded alerts are used to notify people at risk of status changes on a safety or danger continuum in allowing them to take appropriate actions. This ISO standard develops the guidance for use of colour coded alerts and describe the colour-coded alerts to express the status of hazard. There are mentioned the typical colours for colour-coding system, with several scales (with 3, 5 and 7 colours). It reflects the importance of the order and positioning for the red, yellow and green spectrum and the colour-codes to give supplementary information, explaining the use of each colour.
- **ISO 22328-1:2020. Security and resilience. Emergency management. Part 1: General guidelines for the implementation of a community-based disaster early warning system. 1st edition. English version:** It reflects the normative references and define the following terms: community vulnerability, early warning, community-based early warning system/community-based EWS (early warning system), evacuation command and evacuation drill. The community-based disaster early warning system should comprise five main sub-systems: risk assessment, dissemination and communication of knowledge, monitoring and warning service, response capability and commitment of the authority and community on the sustainability of the EWS. A special attention is focused on the development of the response capability. The community should be able to respond to disasters in sufficient time with the right manner. For that purpose, the authority should establish a disaster preparedness team, who could determine an evacuation shelter, developing an evacuation map and routes, developing standard operating procedures and conducting an evacuation drill.

9.6.3. Strengths

- In EU there are a **regulatory framework** for alerts and warnings. All procedures must be under this regulatory Civil Protection and Communications laws.
- The **EU Civil Protection Mechanism** coordinates pan-European assistance and ensures that all EU members states stand ready and prepare to help each other when national resources for disaster response are overwhelmed or need to be reinforces.
- In European Countries there is a **high availability of plans, procedures and tools** for alerts and warnings, and there are **technological means** available to support it.
- There are a **situational awareness in authorities** on that need.
- There is **commitment from EU in collaborative projects** to this objective (call H2020, Horizonte Europa).
- **There is already a basis** for carrying out measures against risks.

9.6.4. Weaknesses

- There are **different responses** to risks **depending on the country** where the alert is received
- **Different procedures** can give different indications to people for actions in risk situations
- **There isn't interoperability in first responders** in alerts and warning in cross border incident.
- There is **not a uniform availability nor use of technological means** across different state members.
- There is **no training** in alert & warnings **in general population**
- **Legal & political constraints:** warning procedures may be hindered by regulatory aspects (GDPR, jurisdiction, etc.) Lack of response feedback from alarms and warnings by the citizens

9.6.5. Opportunities

- **Technological communications means (5G, etc.):** they make easier to disseminate alerts.
- Technological **advance for information sharing** and C2 related to alert and warning
- Social Networks: represents an opportunity thanks to the rapid dissemination of information
- **Modern training tools:** LMS, Gamification, Virtual reality, Mateverse...: allows massive training for population and specialized training for FR.
- **Previously validated tools/efforts** to homogenize training /response: protocols, messages, codification: CAP...
- Private-public & military/civil **cooperation commitment** in alert & warning in MCI and disasters. **Volunteering:** population solidarity, mainly in disaster.
- Use of a common federated system (e.g. SIGRUN COP) for sharing mechanism to share mapped alerts between different agents in national or cross-border incidents
- Use "People-as-sensors" through apps to gather also responses in alerts, warnings or the consequences of a catastrophic event using existing mobile technologies.
- New development of social-media analysis on public response to alerts and warning

9.6.6. Threats

- **Different languages** in different / same countries
- **Socio-cultural differences:** population groups, age groups, culture (understanding of messages), unequal responses and may cause increased risks in cross-border areas.
- **Digital literacy** (technological issues)
- **Internet and social networks**, which represents both an opportunity thanks to the rapid dissemination of information and a danger due to the large presence of falsehoods, hoaxes and fake news.
- There is **no universal consensus (standards) in recommendations to high priority warnings** to the population.
- **No consensus in content/symbols/codes** to communicate messages in warnings.
- **The process of Standardisation is predominantly triggered and shaped by social, political, and economics factors, rather than in response to scientific needs specifics to a hazard;** and standardisation is difficult to implement due to the diversity and uncertain nature of hazard at different temporal and spatial scales.

10. Roadmap for pre-standardisation

10.1 WP5 roadmap

The following graphs present the common roadmap of the WP5 clustered opportunities that have been investigated in depth.

WP5 Clustered Opportunities joint roadmap (2023-30)	2023	2024				2025				2026				2027				2028				2029				2030			
	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4			
CO.WP5-1: Standardisation of terms in planning, preparedness and execution of the emergency response	DEVELOPMENT AND IMPLEMENTATION												REVIEW / UPDATING																
CO.WP5-2: Harmonization of emergency response plans	DEVELOPMENT AND IMPLEMENTATION												REVIEW / UPDATING																
CO.WP5-7: Harmonization of operating procedures in emergency response	DEVELOPMENT AND IMPLEMENTATION												REVIEW / UPDATING																
CO.WP5-12: Standardization of information sharing in emergency response.	DEVELOPMENT AND IMPLEMENTATION												REVIEW / UPDATING																
CO.WP5-13: Establishing a common federated system for sharing information in emergency response	DEVELOPMENT AND IMPLEMENTATION												R / U																
CO.WP5-3: Harmonization of alert and warning procedures in emergency response	DEVELOPMENT AND IMPLEMENTATION												REVIEW / UPDATING																

Figure 26 - WP5 Clustered Opportunities joint roadmap (2023-30)

WP5 Clustered Opportunities joint roadmap (2023-24)	2023		2024			
	3rd Trim	4th Trim	1st Trim	2nd Trim	3rd Trim	4th Trim
CO.WP5-1: STANDARDISATION OF TERMS IN PLANNING, PREPAREDNESS AND EXECUTION OF THE EMERGENCY RESPONSE	TECHNICAL COMITEE	COMMON TERMINOLOGY FRAMEWORK DRAFT			PUBLIC CONSULTATION	
CO.WP5-2: HARMONIZATION OF EMERGENCY RESPONSE PLANS	HARMONISATION TECHNICAL COMITEE	COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW	ERP HARMONISATION		TRAINING	STANDARDISATION TECHNICAL COMMITTEE
CO.WP5-7: HARMONIZATION OF OPERATING PROCEDURES IN EMERGENCY RESPONSE	TECHNICAL COMITEE	GAP ANALYSIS			REGULATORY AND TECHNOLOGICAL HARMONISATION	
CO.WP5-12: STANDARDIZATION OF INFORMATION SHARING IN EMERGENCY RESPONSE.	TECHNICAL COMITEE	COMMON TERMINOLOGY FRAMEWORK DRAFT			PUBLIC CONSULTATION	
CO.WP5-13: ESTABLISHING A COMMON FEDERATED SYSTEM FOR SHARING INFORMATION IN EMERGENCY RESPONSE					TECHNICAL COMITEE	NEEDS ASSESSMENT
CO.WP5-3: HARMONIZATION OF ALERT AND WARNING PROCEDURES IN EMERGENCY RESPONSE	TECHNICAL COMITEE	EVALUATE EXISTING SYSTEMS		COMMON FRAMEWORK		

Figure 27 - WP5 Clustered Opportunities joint roadmap (2023-24)

WP5 Clustered Opportunities joint roadmap (2025-26)	2025				2026			
	1st Trim	2nd Trim	3rd Trim	4th Trim	1st Trim	2nd Trim	3rd Trim	4th Trim
CO.WP5-1: STANDARDISATION OF TERMS IN PLANNING, PREPAREDNESS AND EXECUTION OF THE EMERGENCY RESPONSE	PUBLIC CONSULTATION		COMMON TERMINOLOGY FRAMEWORK DEFINITION		IMPLEMENTATION AND FOLLOW-UP			
CO.WP5-2: HARMONIZATION OF EMERGENCY RESPONSE PLANS	COMMON STANDARDS AND GUIDELINES.		PUBLIC CONSULTATION			COMMON LEGAL FRAMEWORK		
CO.WP5-7: HARMONIZATION OF OPERATING PROCEDURES IN EMERGENCY RESPONSE	REGULATORY AND TECHNOLOGICAL HARMONISATION						PRE-ESTANDARDISATION OF A SOP	
CO.WP5-12: STANDARDIZATION OF INFORMATION SHARING IN EMERGENCY RESPONSE.	PUBLIC CONSULTATION		COMMON TERMINOLOGY FRAMEWORK DEFINITION		IMPLEMENTATION AND FOLLOW-UP			
CO.WP5-13: ESTABLISHING A COMMON FEDERATED SYSTEM FOR SHARING INFORMATION IN EMERGENCY RESPONSE	NEEDS ASSESSMENT		SYSTEM DESIGN AND ARCHITECTURE					
CO.WP5-3: HARMONIZATION OF ALERT AND WARNING PROCEDURES IN EMERGENCY RESPONSE	CENTRAL AUTHORITY. STANDARDISE PROCESS, AND ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES.				DEFINE STRATEGY AND MECHANISMS, TESTING, TRAINING			

Figure 28 - WP5 Clustered Opportunities joint roadmap (2025-26)

WP5 Clustered Opportunities joint roadmap (2027-28)	2027				2028			
	1st Trim	2nd Trim	3rd Trim	4th Trim	1st Trim	2nd Trim	3rd Trim	4th Trim
CO.WP5-1: STANDARDISATION OF TERMS IN PLANNING, PREPAREDNESS AND EXECUTION OF THE EMERGENCY RESPONSE	IMPLEMENTATION AND FOLLOW-UP	REVIEW AND UPDATE						
CO.WP5-2: HARMONIZATION OF EMERGENCY RESPONSE PLANS	COMMON LEGAL FRAMEWORK		IMPLEMENTATION AND MONITORING			REVIEW AND UPDATE		
CO.WP5-7: HARMONIZATION OF OPERATING PROCEDURES IN EMERGENCY RESPONSE	PRE-ESTANDARDISATION OF A SOP		PUBLIC CONSULTATION			STANDARDISATION		
CO.WP5-12: STANDARDIZATION OF INFORMATION SHARING IN EMERGENCY RESPONSE.	IMPLEMENTATION AND FOLLOW-UP	REVIEW AND UPDATE						
CO.WP5-13: ESTABLISHING A COMMON FEDERATED SYSTEM FOR SHARING INFORMATION IN EMERGENCY RESPONSE	SYSTEM DESIGN AND ARCHITECTURE	PROTOTYPE DEVELOPMENT AND TESTING			IMPLEMENTATION AND INTEGRATION			
CO.WP5-3: HARMONIZATION OF ALERT AND WARNING PROCEDURES IN EMERGENCY RESPONSE	REVIEW AND UPDATE							

Figure 29 - WP5 Clustered Opportunities joint roadmap (2027-28)

WP5 Clustered Opportunities joint roadmap (2029-30)	2029				2030			
	1st Trim	2nd Trim	3rd Trim	4th Trim	1st Trim	2nd Trim	3rd Trim	4th Trim
CO.WP5-1: STANDARDISATION OF TERMS IN PLANNING, PREPAREDNESS AND EXECUTION OF THE EMERGENCY RESPONSE	REVIEW AND UPDATE							
CO.WP5-2: HARMONIZATION OF EMERGENCY RESPONSE PLANS	REVIEW AND UPDATE							
CO.WP5-7: HARMONIZATION OF OPERATING PROCEDURES IN EMERGENCY RESPONSE	STANDARDISATION	IMPLEMENTATION AND MONITORING	REVIEW AND UPDATE					
CO.WP5-12: STANDARDIZATION OF INFORMATION SHARING IN EMERGENCY RESPONSE.	REVIEW AND UPDATE							
CO.WP5-13: ESTABLISHING A COMMON FEDERATED SYSTEM FOR SHARING INFORMATION IN EMERGENCY RESPONSE	IMPLEMENTATION AND INTEGRATION							REVIEW AND UPDATE
CO.WP5-3: HARMONIZATION OF ALERT AND WARNING PROCEDURES IN EMERGENCY RESPONSE	REVIEW AND UPDATE							

Figure 30 - WP5 Clustered Opportunities joint roadmap (2029-30)

The individual roadmaps for each of these opportunities are further detailed in next corresponding sub-sections.

10.2 Opportunity roadmap

10.1.1. CO.WP5-1: Standardisation of terms in planning, preparedness and execution of the emergency response

The roadmap proposed by VALKYRIES to achieve standardisation of terms in emergency response planning, preparedness and execution in the European Union (EU) could include the following steps:

1. Conduct a gap analysis: Analyse the terminology used in the different EU countries in order to identify inconsistencies and gaps.
2. Identify the terminology used in the field of emergency response: To identify the terms and definitions that are commonly used and accepted in the field of emergency response, a review of relevant international standards, such as those developed by the International Organisation for Standardisation (ISO), the European Committee for Standardisation (CEN) and the European Standard (EN), should be carried out and the terms and definitions that are commonly used and accepted should be identified. At this point in the roadmap is the Valkyries project. A glossary of terms and semantic representations has been developed and is included in D 2.2.
3. Establish a technical committee or working group (October-2023): Establish a technical committee composed of experts from different EU countries, emergency services and other stakeholders to oversee the development of a common terminology framework. In addition to the working group defining terminology in English, competent committees should be set up to establish equivalence in each of the other EU languages.
4. Develop a draft common terminology framework (October-2024): This would be based on identified gaps and relevant international standards, in consultation with stakeholders. This draft terminology framework should have the following features:
 - o Multilingual terminology database structured in English - other EU languages.
 - o Supported by a solid knowledge base on emergencies and disasters.

- Identification of the conceptual structure underlying emergencies and disasters: the main concepts, the relationships between concepts and their multidimensionality, i.e. the fact that concepts can be classified differently, depending on the context.
- 5. Public consultation (October-2025): Publish the draft common terminology framework for public consultation, inviting comments and views from stakeholders, including emergency services, NGOs and other interested parties.
- 6. Define the Common Terminology Framework (April 2026): Based on the review of comments received during the public consultation, revise the draft Common Terminology Framework as necessary. Finalise the Common Terminology Framework and obtain the approval of the relevant EU bodies.
- 7. Implementation and follow-up (April 2027): Implement the Common Terminology Framework in EU countries and monitor its effectiveness through regular evaluations.
- 8. Review and update (onwards): To ensure that the Common Terminology Framework remains relevant and effective, a mechanism for continuous review and updating should be put in place.

Figure 31 - Roadmap for Standardisation of terms in planning, preparedness and execution of the emergency response

It is important to note that achieving standardisation of terms in the planning, preparedness and implementation of emergency response in the EU may require coordination and cooperation between different levels of government, as well as with international organisations, such as the World Health Organisation and the United Nations. The involvement of different stakeholders and the application of a risk management approach are also essential to ensure the effective implementation of the common terminology framework in the event of an emergency.

10.1.2. CO.WP5-2: Harmonization of emergency response plans

The roadmap proposed by VALKYRIES for the harmonization of emergency response plans (ERP) across the EU would involve the following steps:

1. Establish a working group (set up): comprising experts from different EU countries, emergency services, and other relevant stakeholders, to oversee the development of actions. (October 2023)
2. Conduct a comprehensive review: the first step would be to conduct a comprehensive review of the existing legislation and guidelines related to emergency planning in all EU Member States. This review should identify best practices and areas of convergence, as well as differences and gaps in the rules for the development of ERPs in EU Member States. (January 2024)
3. ERP Harmonisation: by analysing the commonalities and differences between existing ERPs in EU Member States and establishing mechanisms to improve their interoperability while advancing ERP standardisation processes. To improve cross-border cooperation and coordination in emergency situations, these mechanisms could be supported by the technological advances available for the exchange of information, expertise and resources. This could be facilitated by framing it within the EU Civil Protection Mechanism and other crisis response mechanisms, and could help ensure a more effective and coordinated response to emergencies affecting multiple countries or regions. (June 2024)
4. Provide training and capacity building: EU Member States could invest in training and capacity building for civil protection and emergency response personnel, in order to ensure a common understanding of the ERPs. This could include training on risk assessment, response procedures, coordination mechanisms, and the use of common terminology and communication tools. (October 2024).

Harmonisation of contingency plans would be a first objective, which could be followed by efforts to standardise ERPs in the EU. To this end, the steps we propose would be as follows:

5. Establishment of a technical committee: composed of representatives of the different Member States and experts from all relevant fields: political, legal, ethical, emergency services and other potential stakeholders. (Jan 2025)
6. Analyse in detail the existing emergency response plans: in the different EU countries for the different risks, both in terms of what they have in common and their differential contents, assessing the relevance of each section. (October 2025)
7. Identify relevant standards: Review relevant international and EU standards or guidelines, such as those developed by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO), European Committee for Standardization (CEN), and European Norm (EN), and identify best practices and common elements that can be incorporated into an emergency response plan. (October 2025)
8. Establish common standards and guidelines for emergency response planning in the EU: EU Member States could work together to develop common standards and guidelines for the preparation of civil protection emergency response plans. These standards and guidelines could include the methodology for planning and the key elements to be included in the ERP, such as risk assessments, response procedures and coordination mechanisms, etc. The ERP structure should be flexible enough to allow for local variations and priorities, but should also ensure a common approach to risk assessment,

- response procedures, and coordination mechanisms. They could be based on consulted standards, previously existing plans, best practices and lessons learned from previous emergencies. (October 2025)
9. Public consultation: Publish the draft ERP for public consultation, inviting comments and feedback from interested parties, including emergency services, NGOs, and other relevant stakeholders. (October 2026)
 10. Establish a common legal framework: Simultaneously with the progress in the previous steps, the EU institutions should work with Member States to establish a common legal framework for emergency response planning, which could help ensure coherence and consistency between the ERPs of different EU Member States. This could include the development of regulations and directives at EU level, as well as the harmonisation of national legislation. The time it takes for a new EU law to be adopted and implemented in all Member States can vary widely depending on a range of factors. However, the process typically involves several years of negotiation, transposition, implementation, and enforcement. (October 2027)
 11. Implementation and monitoring: to establish a mechanism for monitoring and evaluating the implementation of common standards and guidelines for emergency planning. This mechanism could involve regular assessments of the implementation of emergency plans in each EU Member State, as well as the exchange of best practices and lessons learned among Member States. The assessments could be carried out by independent experts or by a dedicated EU agency. (October 2028)
 12. Review: monitor their effectiveness, periodically reviewing and revising them as necessary to ensure that they continue to meet stakeholders' needs and keep pace with evolving regulatory requirements. (June 2029)

Harmonization of emergency response plans Roadmap

Figure 32 - Roadmap for Harmonization of emergency response plans

10.1.3. CO.WP5-7: Harmonization of operating procedures in emergency response

The roadmap proposed by VALKYRIES for the harmonisation of emergency services Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) across the EU would include the following steps:

1. Identify the need: Identify the need to harmonise the different SOPs across the EU and determine their priority. In the Valkyries project we are at this point in the roadmap. Through the study and analysis carried out, different gaps related to SOPs have been identified.
2. Create a technical committee/working group (October 2023): Composed of experts from different EU countries, emergency services and other relevant stakeholders, to oversee the development of the actions.
3. Conduct a gap analysis (October 2024): Aiming to identify any differences between existing emergency services operational procedures in EU Member States, identify best practices and determine areas where harmonisation is needed.
4. Harmonisation (October 2026): Analysing the differences between existing SOPs in EU Member States and establishing mechanisms to improve their interoperability while advancing SOP standardisation processes. These mechanisms could be mainly
 - Regulatory: Review relevant EU and national legislation, regulations and guidelines that apply to emergency services, in order to consider what regulatory changes might be most feasible and to ensure that decisions taken are in line with the relevant legal framework.
 - Technological: Explore the possibilities offered by new technologies to improve interoperability between services and territories where SOPs are different.

If it is decided to go beyond a simple harmonisation of these SOPs, the definition and implementation of a single unified SOP for emergency services across the EU would involve the following steps:

5. Identifying the need for a unified EU-wide SOP: The first step is to identify the need for a unified EU-wide SOP and determine its priority and scope (including the types of emergencies it will cover, the key principles and concepts to be incorporated and the expected outcome).
6. Homogenisation: Based on the results of the gap analysis and identified best practices, promote high-impact and feasible actions that favour the homogenisation of the different existing SOPs, so that with relatively minor intervention their coherence and consistency and the absence of conflicting requirements at EU level are favoured.
7. Pre-standardisation (October 2027): In two work streams:
 - Analyse and develop the necessary regulatory framework for the future implementation, at EU level and in each of its member states, of unified SOPs for emergency services in the planning, preparedness and execution of emergency and disaster response.
 - Develop a common draft EU SOP, based on the results of the gap analysis and identified best practices, preparing a preliminary draft for peer review and comment.
8. Public consultation (October 2028): Publish the draft common operating procedure for public consultation, inviting comments and feedback from stakeholders, including emergency services, NGOs and other relevant interested parties.

9. Standardisation (April 2029): Finalise the common operating procedure by preparing a final draft standard, based on comments received during the public consultation and peer review, and submit it for formal adoption as an EU standard.
10. Implementation (October 2029): Disseminate, train and implement the common operating procedure in the EU, with the possibility of initially testing it in a selection of these countries to refine it if necessary before its general implementation in the EU.
11. Review (October 2030 onwards): Monitor their effectiveness, periodically reviewing and revising them as necessary to ensure that they continue to meet stakeholder needs and keep pace with evolving regulatory requirements.

Figure 33 - Roadmap for Harmonization of operating procedure in emergency response

It is important to note that the standardisation of a unified operating procedure for emergency services in the EU is a very complex process that may require coordination and cooperation between different levels of government, as well as with international organisations. To offer the best chance of successful implementation and adoption, the initiative should be promoted or at least supported by the EU body or agency most competent to do so. This is likely to be the Emergency Response Coordination Centre (ERCC), which operates within the European Commission's Directorate-General for Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid (ECHO) and acts as the focal point for facilitating a coherent European response during emergencies. The involvement of different stakeholders and the application of a risk management approach are also essential to ensure the effective implementation of a unified EU SOP procedure in the event of a disaster.

10.1.4. CO.WP5-12: Standardization of information sharing in emergency response

A roadmap for such standardization include the following:

- Create a technical committee/working group (October 2023): Engage with key stakeholders (national emergency response agencies, policymakers, and relevant EU bodies) to identify specific requirements and desired features.
- Develop a draft common terminology framework (October-2024): This would be based on identified gaps and relevant international standards, in consultation with stakeholders and industrial entities. This draft terminology framework should have a multilingual terminology in system's architecture supported by a solid knowledge base on emergencies and disasters.
- Public consultation (October-2025): Publish the draft common terminology framework for public consultation, inviting comments and views from stakeholders, the IT industry including emergency services, NGOs and other interested parties.
- Define the Common Terminology Framework (April 2026): Based on the review of comments received during the public consultation, revise the draft Common Framework on workflows as necessary. Finalise the Common Framework based on the conclusions of the Valkyries project and obtain the approval of the relevant EU bodies. Introduce SIGRUN architecture and sharing of data as well as COPs as a standard related with workflows.
- Implementation and follow-up (April 2027): Implement the Common Architectural and procedural framework in EU countries and monitor its effectiveness through regular evaluations.
- Review and update (onwards): To ensure that the Common Terminology Framework remains relevant and effective, a data sharing mechanism for continuous review and updating should be put in place.

Figure 34 - Roadmap for Standardization of information sharing in emergency response

10.1.5. CO.WP5-13: Establishing a common federated system for sharing information in emergency response

This proposal outlines the development of a Common Federated Information Sharing System for Emergency Response in the European Union. The proposed roadmap comprises several key steps:

1. Create a technical committee/working group Stakeholder Engagement (October-2024): Engage with key stakeholders (national emergency response agencies, policymakers, and relevant EU bodies) to identify specific requirements and desired features.
2. Needs Assessment (September-2025)
 - Review related ICT tools, such as the Copernicus Emergency Management Service, the European Emergency Response Coordination Centre (ERCC), and other national or regional platforms. Evaluate their effectiveness, limitations, and compatibility, as well as their ability to work with the federated system.
 - Analyze potential legal, security, and privacy challenges.
 - Conduct a thorough needs assessment to ensure the system addresses the unique challenges faced by each member state.
 - Establish an oversight committee composed of representatives from each member state to guide the development process.
3. System Design and Architecture (March 2027)
 - Develop a federated architecture that enables secure, real-time information sharing among member states while adhering to data protection and privacy regulations (e.g., GDPR).
 - Develop a standardized data model and taxonomy to ensure consistent data representation and compatibility across different information sources.
 - Establish protocols and guidelines for data sharing, security, and privacy.
 - Leverage the latest ICT technologies, such as artificial intelligence, machine learning, or blockchain, to enhance data processing, predictive modelling during emergencies, security, and decision-making capabilities.
 - Design an intuitive user interface to facilitate seamless data access, visualization, and analysis.
4. Prototype Development and Testing (March 2028)
 - Develop a functional prototype of the federated system, incorporating the design and architecture established in the previous phase.
 - Conduct alpha and beta testing with a select group of stakeholders to validate system functionality, performance, and usability.
 - Use the pilot phase as an opportunity to discover new ways to enhance the functionality of existing tools through integration with the federated system.
 - Incorporate stakeholder feedback and refine the prototype as necessary.
5. Implementation and Integration (October 2030)
 - Deploy the system across the European Union, ensuring proper integration with existing emergency response systems and platforms.
 - Develop APIs and tools for third-party system integration.
 - Provide comprehensive training and support to end-users, focusing on system navigation, data sharing procedures, and best practices for information sharing during emergencies.

- Establish a dedicated technical support team to address any issues that arise during the implementation phase.
- 6. Evaluation and Continuous Improvement (Ongoing)
 - Develop a set of performance metrics and key performance indicators (KPIs) to assess the effectiveness of the federated system.
 - Conduct regular evaluations, collecting stakeholder feedback to identify areas for improvement and enhancement.
 - Implement updates and refinements based on evaluation findings, ensuring the system continues to evolve and adapt to the changing needs of the EU emergency response community.

Figure 35 - Roadmap for establishing a common federated system for sharing information in emergency response

10.1.6. CO.WP5-3: Harmonization of alert and warning procedures in emergency response

Harmonizing emergency alert and warning procedures across all EU Member States would require coordinated efforts and cooperation among the member states, as well as a clear framework for establishing standardized procedures.

The roadmap proposed by VALKYRIES for the harmonization of alert and warning procedures in emergency response across the EU would involve the following steps:

- Evaluate existing early warning systems: The first step would be to evaluate the existing early warning systems in each EU Member State to identify strengths, weaknesses, and gaps. This would help to identify the areas where harmonization is most needed. In Valkyries project we have begun the study of different EU alerts and warning system and the identification of related gaps. (April 2024)

- Develop a common framework: to develop a common framework for emergency alert and warning procedures that can be adopted by all member states. This would require extensive research and consultation with experts in the field. An example on common regulation is EU Directive 2018/1972 on the European Electronic Communications Code (EECC) - This Directive, adopted in December 2018, sets out common rules for the provision of electronic communications services across the EU. The Directive includes provisions related to alert and warning systems, including requirements for Member States to develop and implement alert and warning systems based on standardized protocols and procedures. The EECC Article 110 directive states that the public warning system must be mobile phone-based and capable of sending geo-located mass alerts, the alerts must be received by the mobile phones of everyone within an emergency area. This regulation obliges Members States to adopt actions aimed at implementing measures. The EU's early warning and information systems developed in these regulations will help the Emergency Response Coordination Centre monitor hazards and events worldwide (January 2025)
- Establish a central authority: A central authority could be established to oversee the implementation of the common framework and ensure that member states are complying with the agreed-upon standards. This could be facilitated by framing it within the EU Civil Protection Mechanism and other crisis response mechanisms. A national and supranational all-hazards committee on technical warning systems in place and linked to national disaster management and reduction authorities, including a national and supranational platform for disaster risk reduction. (During 2025 following the legislation and regulatory framework)
- Standardized process, and roles and responsibilities of all organizations generating and issuing warnings established and mandated by law. Agreements and interagency protocols established to ensure consistency of warning language and communication channels where different hazards are handled by different agencies. (Jan 2026)
- Train emergency responders: Emergency responders in each member state would need to be trained on the common framework and how to implement it in their respective jurisdictions. (2026)
- Develop a communication strategy: A communication strategy would need to be developed to inform the public about the new procedures and how to respond to emergency alerts and warnings. (2026)
- Collaborate with social media platforms: Social media platforms can play a key role in disseminating accurate information during emergencies. Emergency responders and officials should work with social media platforms to ensure that their messages are prioritized and that false information is flagged and removed. (2025)
- Establish testing and evaluation protocols: Testing and evaluation protocols would need to be established to ensure that the emergency alert and warning systems are functioning properly and effectively. Warning system subjected to system-wide tests and exercises at least once each year. (2026)
- Establish a mechanism for sharing information: A mechanism for sharing information about emergency situations across member states would need to be established to ensure that all member states are aware of any potential threats. This is particularly important in cross-border incidents. Warning Centres always staffed (24 hours per day, seven days per week). Applicable data and analysis from regional networks, adjacent

territories and international sources accessible. Warnings generated and disseminated in an efficient and timely manner and in a format suited to user needs. (October 2025)

- Establish a feedback mechanism: A feedback mechanism could be established to allow member states to provide feedback on the implementation of the common framework and suggest any necessary revisions. (2026-2027).

Figure 36 - Harmonization of alert and warning procedures in emergency response

11. Stakeholders evaluation

The results of the clustering, analysis and selection of opportunities carried out by the project researchers in WP5 were shared with EAB experts and stakeholders to obtain their assessment of the work done and its outputs, as part of the external validation process.

The findings received in this process are summarised below.

11.1 General level of acceptance:

The general level of acceptance of the VALKYRIES harmonisation strategy is: Agree - Strongly agree

11.2 Degree of agreement and contributions

The degree of agreement with the level of impact/feasibility assessment set out in the Project for the clustered opportunity in relation to its implementation in the EU is analysed below.

11.1.1. CO.WP5-1: Standardisation of terms in planning, preparedness and execution of the emergency response

- Degree of agreement: Strongly agree
- Outstanding contributions of the external validation process: One of practical things could be to issue a vocabulary (multilingual) of terms as a practical field manual. Not only terms but also their scope should be included in such standardization. In this case, sticking to the conceptual framework of response preparedness standardisation, this proposal is assessed as even easier to adopt in the near future. This more "academic" aspect has a better and easier development on paper than other aspects more linked to on-scene action.

11.1.2. CO.WP5-2: Harmonization of emergency response plans

- Degree of agreement: Strongly agree
- Outstanding contributions of the external validation process: Next level step. From an operational and functional point of view, no problems have been identified with this harmonisation of contingency plans, but the political aspects of the plan are another matter, where harmonisation work should perhaps be carried out at the appropriate decision-making levels.

11.1.3. CO.WP5-7: Harmonization of operating procedures in emergency response

- Degree of agreement: Strongly agree
- Outstanding contributions of the external validation process: First priority task. The best way to implement good practices. There is a strong belief that if a process proves its usefulness and advantage over others currently in use, there is nothing to stop it becoming the standard in the future, subject to technical difficulties and provided it has a favourable cost-benefit ratio.

11.1.4. CO.WP5-12: Standardization of information sharing in emergency response

- Degree of agreement: Agree
- Outstanding contributions of the external validation process: In line with the comments made earlier by the external experts consulted, the enormous difficulty and importance of sharing information on the ground between the different groups of participants was noted. This should be emphasised if there is to be no doubt about the usefulness of the project. It is the backbone of the whole VALKYRIES project. Information sharing should be in close relation to operating procedures.

11.1.5. CO.WP5-13: Establishing a common federated system for sharing information in emergency response

- Degree of agreement: Agree
- Outstanding contributions of the external validation process: Such system could be the backbone of international cooperation and far internal Integration of national systems. There is a belief that these and other technical issues can be resolved and do not pose insurmountable obstacles once the benefits and improvements to incident management through information sharing are confirmed.

11.1.6. CO.WP5-3: Harmonization of alert and warning procedures in emergency response

- Degree of agreement: Agree
- Outstanding contributions of the external validation process: In a similar way to the harmonization of the plans, the early warning and emergency notification procedures can be standardized and easily adopted by the participants, with the necessary adjustments that are adapted to the existing chains of command and control. At the first stage harmonization could cover alert and warning signals exchange at international level without procedures integration.

12. Conclusions

12.1. CO.WP5-1: Standardisation of terms in planning, preparedness and execution of the emergency response

Standardisation of terminology is a fundamental need for harmonisation, homogenisation and standardisation in emergency planning, preparedness and response, as highlighted in the analysis of the main opportunities for harmonisation, not only within WP5 but also in other WPs (notably WP6).

While there is no doubt that considerable efforts have been made in the past to standardise terminology in this area, the fact remains that first responders still perceive that there is an unresolved gap. This may reflect a certain mismatch between previous work and the practical needs or expectations of practitioners. Faced with this situation, the experts themselves suggest as a way forward the creation of a multilingual vocabulary of terms with a practical approach that includes the context in which they are applied.

In this deliverable D5.3, VALKYRIES proposes a roadmap for the establishment of a technical committee or working group to oversee the development of a common EU multilingual terminology database, supported by a solid knowledge base on emergencies and disasters, taking into account the conceptual structure underlying emergencies and disasters, and continuously updated. Such a common terminology would undoubtedly support standardisation in the planning, preparedness and response to emergencies in the EU.

12.2. CO.WP5-2: Harmonization of emergency response plans

Effective emergency planning and standardized logistics are critical to the timely and efficient deployment of resources during emergencies. The EU and other organizations have established guidelines and standards for civil protection logistics, but they require harmonization and coordination between different regions and countries. The roadmap proposes a comprehensive approach to harmonizing emergency plans within the EU, resulting in cross-border cooperation and coordination, more effective and coordinated responses, and greater cooperation between emergency plans in different EU-MS. Improves greater consistency and coherence. By implementing this roadmap, the EU will be able to improve emergency preparedness and response, save lives and minimize the impact of disasters.

12.3. CO.WP5-7: Harmonization of operating procedures in emergency response

The operational procedures of the emergency services are very diverse and there is no homogeneity in aspects such as the triage system used or the coding and labelling of victims. Improving these aspects would promote interoperability between services in cross-border and/or cross-sector multi-casualty incidents.

A thorough review of procedures would highlight both differences and commonalities, so that harmonisation could be achieved through different mechanisms while work on standardisation continues. Such standardisation would be achieved through the development of a common operating procedure that could be implemented across all emergency services, ensuring real interoperability between services.

12.4. CO.WP5-12: Standardization of information sharing in emergency response

Standardising the exchange of information during emergency management is essential to ensure interoperability between services and improve coordination. This is especially true if emergencies involve different countries, languages and procedures. The use of standardised information exchange systems improves the actions to be taken in the different phases of disasters by facilitating communication between agencies, regions and countries and the exchange of data between them.

This standardised system should be based on the development of a common terminology framework, with multilingual terminology and a solid knowledge base on emergencies and disasters.

12.5. CO.WP5-13: Establishing a common federated system for sharing information in emergency response

In order to be able to exchange information quickly, accurately and reliably between the countries involved during a disaster, it is necessary to implement tools that provide solutions to the problems encountered, be they legal, technological or procedural.

The development of a Common Federated Information Exchange System for Emergency Response in the European Union would allow for secure, real-time information sharing between member countries, while safeguarding data protection and privacy regulations.

Its development would take into account a standardised data model and taxonomy, and would establish protocols and guidelines for data exchange, security and privacy.

12.6. CO.WP5-3: Harmonization of alert and warning procedures in emergency response

Harmonization of alert and warning procedures is critical for effective emergency response in the EU. Alert and warning systems enable emergency responders to quickly and effectively notify the public of potential or imminent threats, such as natural disasters, terrorist attacks, and other types of emergencies. The standardisation of alerts and early warning is vital to convey information to a wide range of stakeholders. Standardized alert and warning procedures ensure that the public receives consistent and clear information about the threat and the appropriate actions to take in response.

The roadmap proposes a comprehensive approach to harmonizing alerts and warnings within the EU. To enhance early warning system in the EU, forecasting, detection and monitoring capacity and public alert system should be improved and a common framework should be developed for emergency alert and warning procedures that can be adopted by all member states. This would require extensive research and consultation with experts in the field. A central authority could be useful to promote and monitor the development of the common framework, as well this authority could be established to oversee the implementation of the common framework and ensure that member states are complying with the agreed-upon standards

Standardized process, roles and responsibilities of all organizations generating and issuing warnings established and mandated by law. Agreements and interagency protocols established to ensure consistency of warning language and communication channels where different hazards are handled by different agencies. A mechanism for sharing information about

emergency situations across member states would need to be established to ensure that all member states are aware of any potential threats. This is particularly important in cross-border incidents.

To collaborate with social media platform to ensure priority messages get through and fight against misinformation and fake news.

Finally, education, testing and measurement are necessary for the success of alerts and early warning systems.

13. Annex A – References and bibliography

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8. Valkyries D5.6 Harmonization opportunities on the operational and procedural landscape for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters
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14. Annex B – Glossary

Acronym	Description
APCO	Association of Public-Safety Communications Officials International
API	Application Programming Interface
ASTM	American Society for Testing and Materials
BEREC	Body of European Regulators for Electronic Communications
C2	Command & Control
CAP	Common Alerting Protocol
CBRNE	Chemical, Biological, Radiological, Nuclear, and Explosives
CECIS	Common Emergency Communication and Information System
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
CISE	Common Information Sharing Environment
CMAS	Commercial Mobile Alert System
COP	Common Operational Picture
DG ECHO	European Commission's Humanitarian Aid and Civil Protection General Direction
DSL	Digital Subscriber Line
EAB	External Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
EDRIS	European Disaster Response Information System
EDXL	Emergency Data Exchange Language
EEA	European Economic Area
EECC	European Electronic Communications Code
EENA	European Emergency Number Association
EMF	Emergency Management Framework
EMS	Emergency Medical Service / System
EMT	Emergency medical teams
EN	European Norm
ERCC	Emergency Response Coordination Centre
ERP	Emergency response plan
EU	European Union
EUCPM	EU Civil Protection Mechanism
EU-MS	EU Member States
FEMA	Federal Emergency Management Agency
FR	First responder
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
H2020	Horizon 2020
HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
ICT	Information and communications technology
IFRC	International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies
IoT	Internet of Things
IPAWS	Integrated Public Alert and Warning System
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ITU	International Telecommunication Union

Acronym	Description
ITU-T	ITU Telecommunication Standardization Sector
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KPI	Key performance indicator
LMS	Learning management system
MCI	Mass Casualty Incident
METHANE	M-Major incident declared? E-Exact location T-Type of incident H-Hazards A- Access N-Number, Type, Severity of casualties E-Emergency services present and those required
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
NATO	North Atlantic Treaty Organization
NENA	National Emergency Number Association
NFPA	National Fire Protection Association
NGO	Non-governmental organization
NIMS	National Incident Management System
OASIS	OASIS Open Europe Foundation
OCHA	United Nation's Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs
OSHA	US Occupational Safety and Health Administration
PSAP	Public Safety Answering Point
rescEU	EUCPM reserve of resources
SA	Situational Awareness
SOP	Standard operating procedure
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats
TCP/IP	Transmission Control Protocol/Internet Protocol
TETRA	Trans European Trunked Radio
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
UK	United Kingdom
UN	United Nations
UNDAC	United Nations Disaster Assessment and Coordination
UNECE	UN Economic Commission for Europe
UNHCR	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees
UNISDR	United Nations International Strategy for Disaster Reduction
USAR	Urban Search and Rescue
VOST	Virtual Operation Support Teams
WEA	Wireless Emergency Alerts
WHO	World Health Organization
WP	Work package

Table 26 – Glossary